

THE LIBERATOR

Mesut KAVAK

(V.1 2020. Under development)

Contents

I	Laws	6
1	Law Constitution of Kingdom	8
	The Beginning	8
	Article 1: Admission	8
1.1	Meaning of the name al-Lah	8
1.2	The Beneficent and The Merciful names of God	8
1.3	Obligatory principles arising from the names of God	9
	Matchless Cultural Principles of Management	9
	Article 2: Hierarchy	10
2.1	General shape	10
2.2	Some limits	10
	Article 3: Oligarchy	10
3.1	General shape	10
3.2	Some limits	11
	Article 4: Monarchy	12
4.1	General shape	12
4.2	Family motivation	14
	Article 5: Socialism	14
5.1	General shape	14
5.2	Basic application principles	14
	Article 6: Interreligious Dialog	15
6.1	General shape	15
6.2	Social relations and minorities	16
	International Relations	16
	Article 7: Expansionism Rejection	17
7.1	Cultural development process of humanity	17
7.2	Abrahamism	18
	Article 8: Internationalism	19
8.1	General shape	19
8.2	Some limits	19
	Article 9: Bilateral Relations	20
9.1	Obligation arising from economic phenomena	20
9.2	Obligation arising from bad administrations	20
	Cultural Administrative Adaptations	21
	Article 10: Organic laws	21
10.1	General shape	22
10.2	Some limits	22
	Article 11: Official language	22
11.1	Speaking language	22
11.2	Language of worship	22
	Article 12: Official Religion	23
12.1	Religion concept	23
12.2	Sufism	24
12.3	Religious sects	26
12.3.1	General shape	26
12.3.2	Sunni and Shia	27
	Article 13: Colonial Order and State System	28
13.1	General shape of colonies	28
13.1.1	Ponds	28
13.1.2	Underground Tunnels	28
13.2	Criminal colonies	28
13.3	Ideological distinction	29
13.4	State order	30
	Article 14: Council Order	30
14.1	Public Councils	30
14.2	State councils	30
14.3	Advisory council of the king	30
14.4	The Noble council	31
	Article 15: Voting Order	31
15.1	General shape	31
15.2	Some limits	31
	Article 16: Educational Order	31

16.1	General shape	31
16.2	Women's Education	32
	Article 17: Economical Order	32
17.1	General shape	32
17.2	Employer-worker law	32
17.3	Stock exchange	32
	17.3.1 Socialism or Communism?	33
	17.3.2 Perfect Capitalism	33
	17.3.3 Practical transition	34
	17.3.4 International competition	34
	Article 18: Security Order	34
18.1	General shape	34
18.2	Some limits	35
	Article 19: Death Penalty	35
19.1	General shape	35
19.2	Some conditions	35
19.3	Standard posture	35
	Interactive Laws	36
	Article 20: Dynasty	36
20.1	General shape	36
20.2	Some limits	36
	Article 21: Royal Committees	37
21.1	General shape	37
21.2	Price balance	37
	Article 22: Active Banking	37
22.1	General shape	37
22.2	Royal committee	37
	Article 23: Royal Academy	37
23.1	General shape	37
23.2	Some tasks	38
	Article 24: Working Order	38
24.1	General shape	38
24.2	Compulsory service	38
24.3	Salary	38
	Article 25: Trade Order	39
25.1	General shape	39
25.2	Export	39
	Administrative Laws	39
	Article 26: Rights and Responsibilities of the King	39
26.1	General shape	40
26.2	Some responsibilities	40
	Article 27: Advisory Council of the King	41
27.1	General shape	41
27.2	Some limits	41
	Article 28: Noble Council	41
28.1	General shape	41
28.2	Some conditions	41
	Article 29: Rights and Responsibilities of Managers	41
29.1	General shape	42
29.2	Some limits	42
29.3	Exclusive features	43
	29.3.1 Muhammad	43
	29.3.2 Mahdi	44
29.4	Wisdom	45
29.5	Beneficence	47
	Article 30: Courts	47
30.1	General shape	48
30.2	Judges	48
30.3	Practical Transition	48
	General Cultural Legal Principles	48
	Article 31: State of Emergency	48
31.1	General shape	48
31.2	General attitude of the public	49
	Article 32: Marriage	49
32.1	General shape	49
32.2	Divorce	50
32.3	Mother and father	50
	32.3.1 Carer service	50
	32.3.2 Retirement homes	50
	Article 33: Migration Status	50
33.1	General shape	50
33.2	Right to protection	50
33.3	Immigration law	51
	Article 34: Heritage and Testament	51
34.1	Heritage	51

34.2 Testament	51
Article 35: Loyalty and Witness	51
35.1 Loyalty	51
35.2 Testimony	51
Article 36: Social Citizen Rights	52
36.1 General shape	52
36.2 Some conditions	52
Article 37: Socialist Public Elements	52
37.1 General shape	53
37.2 Some limits	53
Article 38: Civil Defense Rights	53
38.1 General shape	53
38.2 Firearm	53
Article 39: Confidentiality of Private Life	54
39.1 General shape	54
39.2 Press	54
Article 40: Absurdity	54
40.1 General shape	54
40.2 Consultation	54
Article 41: Technology Policy	55
41.1 General shape	55
41.2 Measures	55
Article 42: Environmental and Animal Rights	55
42.1 General shape	55
42.2 Religious duties	55
2 Constitution of Nations	56
Article 1: General shape	56
Article 2: Religious Responsibilities	56
Article 3: Social Responsibility	56
Article 4: Civil Responsibilities	56
Article 5: Legal Rights and Responsibilities	57
Article 6: Rights and Responsibilities Related to War	57
II Technological Upgrades	58
4 Scientific Infrastructure	59
The Basic Functions	59
4.1 Energy	59
4.1.1 Sacred Geometry	60
4.1.2 Some results of the inequality	60
4.1.3 Progressive image	60
4.2 Motility	61
4.2.1 Centrifugal Force	61
4.2.2 Imbalance	62
4.3 Heating and Cooling	62
4.3.1 Heating	62
4.3.2 Cooling	62
5 Adaptations	63
Civil Engineering Elements Working on the Basic Functions	63
5.1 Construction methods of structures	63
5.2 Civil Environment	63
5.2.1 Buildings	63
5.2.2 Roads	64
5.2.3 Vehicles	64
5.3 New construction equipment	65
5.3.1 Drilling machines	65
5.3.2 Fire Truck	66
5.3.3 Agricultural vehicles	66
5.3.4 Transport	66
5.4 Industry	66
5.4.1 Water production: Type zero	66
5.4.2 Mine production	67
5.5 The Cryptobit	67
5.5.1 Selecting randomly	67
5.5.2 Encoding	68
5.5.3 Offline Calibration	68
5.5.4 Remote Calibration	68
5.5.5 Prevention against DDOS attacks: Spartan	68

Information

Actually this work is about 150.000 words that is unfinished; so I require translator but is very expensive for such a big word amount. I started to translate oneself and then noticed that also I had translated some of original version without copy. I must write it again and also I must translate it that takes too many times. I bored, and for months, I have not been interest that actually would share in 2019. I remembered this work and published as summary. I do not know when I will publish the rest. There may be mistakes in the language, and sorry about this. I will correct them over time, and publish the full version.

Part I
Laws

No word, do work!

The Monica

When dialectical relations or minimum, maximum, optimum and Utopian quality are put aside, laws and principles are binding absolute phenomena even for a single person who has no relation with social life, and moreover even for such a single animal. As different living things which belong to the same group at different times, all possible principles and laws are the same and certain; so principles and laws are cultural without changing over time.

Emerging rules regarding life in any area of social life are cult, religion or are cultural and religious phenomena. A second concept like religion cannot be created. Holy books are not filled with the orders which are completely foreign to people. God does not order only for the people do not know about rules or since people do not know about rules. God again underlines many phenomena which are currently active culturally when they have not been notified or which are degenerated. In this case, as a natural reaction; a sum of the rules which manage society, a reference which is consulted and written, a book of the rules of personal and social life is formed.

I will surely cut off your hands and your feet on opposite sides; then I will surely crucify you all.

Quran 7:124

For example this verse from Quran specifies order of the Egyptian Pharaoh who never knew another religious rules or Quran. Even if the rules were the same along the history of mankind, it can easily be corrupted.

Indeed, the penalty for those who wage war against Allah and His Messenger and strive upon earth [to cause] corruption is none but that they be killed or crucified or that their hands and feet be cut off from opposite sides or that they be exiled from the land. That is for them a disgrace in this world; and for them in the Hereafter is a great punishment.

Quran 5:33

And this verse is the law which God determined it oneself, and similarity is quite clear.

All the rules are underlined; because if God threatens us about a particle smallness sin, even if most of people know that the smallest sin and stay away from it currently, God must notify about that sin clearly and understandable because of the self defence right of human which arises threat originated. Theoretically at the place where trusted people live there, people live without any record, esoteric; but considering number of the people educated, education difficulties and application strategies, it is quite hard and it includes high risk. Because of these reasons, holy books had been used and are going to be used as written records.

The topics covered with these lines and in the below stated pages are not arguable, and they do not change over time, due to time. Religion is nothing but advice. The things to say are always the same, and the same things are always repeated with a serious discipline; because the same mistakes are always repeated by another civil or statesman. In this case, the closest one to forgiveness is heedlessness, and the unacceptable one is ignorance and being in the dark. As our portion, it is aiming cultivating to get better results by repeating the same things constantly without disrupting the essence and origin of the phenomena like a theoretical physicist or mathematician, or like a special force soldier who always does "reload and unload" and gun check like a beginner even if uses the gun masterly that owes own success to this discipline.

Chapter 1

Law Constitution of Kingdom

The Beginning

Names of God are the greatest verses about knowing God; God definitely governs all events according to these names, otherwise impossible. All events get shape in accordance with these names spontaneously. As all information and actions arise from wisdom of God, there is no alternative to this phenomenon; therefore even for infinite repeats, to have the secrets of being, and to apply natural information which protect us against mistakes in any area of social life, the names are important.

Article 1: Admission

In the name of al-Lah, the beneficent, the merciful.

1.1 Meaning of the name al-Lah

Indeed, your Lord is Allah, who created the heavens and earth in six days and then established Himself above the Throne.

Quran 7:54

From the first he was the Word, and the Word was in relation with God and was God. This Word was from the first in relation with God. All things came into existence through him, and without him nothing was. What came into existence in him was life, and the life was the light of men. And the light goes on shining in the dark; it is not overcome by the dark.

John 1:1-5

Word of Allah is a portmanteau word but it is generally used as one-piece. It is actually written as al-Lah like all the other names of God that "al" is definite article here like "the" in English. Al-Lah (al-Lâh) name has a meaning as loose, hanging and pendant, and it is the single name which describes God as a body which has all the other names.

A body has infinite size is expected to reach saturation for its each point; but there is one more option that, this body can be flexible being susceptible to density change. When density is the same and motionless at the each point of such an infinite body, density of a point can increase while density is decreasing at another point because of the increase in this conservative infinite area. By this was, the infinite can create another bodies being these bodies are imaginary part of infinite, and the infinite cannot be alone as it cannot be without creation as well. During this density change, God droops and together with a potential difference, a motion emerges from denser point to lower density point that is the source of motion and energy. By this way, the created things over God's body hangs on God. Everything which God creates is an imaginary part of God by this single and fixed rule, and absolute being is only God.

We have seen his glory, the glory of the one and only Son, who came from the Father, full of grace and truth.

John 14

And [remember, O Muhammad], when We told you, "Indeed, your Lord has encompassed the people."

Quran 17:60

Existence is either absolute or uncertain which is a part of the absolute body and repeats at a frequency formation motion to be more certain. As absolute one, there is only 1 absolute; so the name of "Allah" only belongs to 1 existence as there is no alternative as well.

1.2 The Beneficent and The Merciful names of God

The Entirely Merciful, the Especially Merciful.

Quran 1:3

One of the greatest names of God is The Beneficent or The Entirely Merciful (ar-Rahman) and the other one is the Especially Merciful (ar-Rahim). Each surah of Quran begins with these two the greatest names of God; because Quran is holy book of the being who have mind and are subjected to responsibilities. For different kind of existence, their book which includes the rules, it can begin like "In the name of God who is like this". If there was no freewill which is subjected to holding responsibilities, then a name like "ar-Rahman" would be meaningless directly and everybody would be the same for God, that God helps all of people by the name of "ar-Rahman" regardless of faith and helps the people who know and serve God by the name of "ar Rahim".

And if it were not that the people would become one community [of disbelievers], We would have made for those who disbelieve in the Most Merciful - for their houses - ceilings and stairways of silver upon which to mount.

Quran 43:33

For example this verse state that God helps even the people who do not believe in himself and can help more but it has negative results.

"In the name of God" does not mean moving with a decree from God at least for everybody. It means God gave the motion ability to the hanging body as a part of God; so "In the name of God" is a constant dhikr, is a faithful certifying and admission, as also is the character of God of people and states that they must comply. It is the result of God's posture which is difficult and disciplinary. As God creates human as a babe who is in need of his mother's breast, in the same manner and in the same discipline, he orders "In the name of God". This is a discipline.

Recite in the name of your Lord who created, Created man from a clinging substance. Recite, and your Lord is the most Generous, Who taught by the pen, Taught man that which he knew not. No! [But] indeed, man transgresses. Because he sees himself self-sufficient. Indeed, to your Lord is the return.

Quran 96:1-8

These verses show this discipline as well. Already these verses are the first ordered verses of Quran that the verses which prophethood was given to Muhammad by these. During this event, Gabriel squeezed Muhammad until he could not draw a breath and ordered "Recite!" because of the same discipline.

1.3 Obligatory principles arising from the names of God

The names of God are the greatest verses about knowing God; because God manages all events in accordance with these names definitely as there is no alternative. All events get shape in accordance with these names spontaneously. In this case, as it can be noticed, there always exist the people who do not believe in God as a result of "ar Rahman" name of God, and definitely there cannot exist a pure "kill" order which is not in accordance with this in holy books.

This condition is a matter of prestige for God and coexistence of good and evil is one of the most basic natural laws. It is a matter of prestige for God; because God is The Entirely Merciful and is the Especially Merciful as also has greatness. Greatness only belongs to him. Creating people of paradise in paradise and creating people of hell in hell without testing, are not in accordance with God's discipline and law. This is also a bad morality even for human.

And never think that Allah is unaware of what the wrongdoers do. He only delays them for a Day when eyes will stare [in horror].

Quran 14:42

And if it had not been for the favor of Allah upon you and His mercy... and because Allah is Kind and Merciful.

Quran 24:20

Human also meets some of the mistakes politely and some of them patiently, does not response quickly. As a requirement of God's greatness, God does not have to response quickly an enemy who harm innocent people to punish God. People have to response that enemy in the name of God being responsible, and God does not feel as responsible that things which good people experienced during this period. If good people die during this period, God gives them place from paradise as an award and if it requires, he does not recognize them as responsible about the things they realized at the world. In this case, the people died cannot recognize God as arrogant. As they have no right like this, also God can use bad people to test good people by arising sedition, and never can be responsible. God gives respite for each defiant; but at the end, he absolutely punishes by a matchless punishment which only God can.

And to Allah belong the best names, so invoke Him by them. And leave [the company of] those who practice deviation concerning His names. They will be recompensed for what they have been doing. And among those We created is a community which guides by truth and thereby establishes justice. But those who deny Our signs - We will progressively lead them [to destruction] from where they do not know. And I will give them time. Indeed, my plan is firm. Then do they not give thought? There is in their

companion [Muhammad] no madness. He is not but a clear warner. Do they not look into the realm of the heavens and the earth and everything that Allah has created and [think] that perhaps their appointed time has come near? So in what statement hereafter will they believe? Whoever Allah sends astray - there is no guide for him. And He leaves them in their transgression, wandering blindly.

Quran 7:180-186

Matchless Cultural Principles of Management

When you decide to create laws to manage society being the same is acceptable for all other phenomena regarding life, in the name of perfectness and maturity, both practically and theoretically you meet many problems and question which require solutions and answers. In this case, inevitably first of all you require chaotic approximations, and absolutely chaotic approximations requires. It does not mean we must follow each complexity. If you want to create a hill on a desert which there is constant winds, instead of chasing each sand particle, it is enough to tailor a bar which has the same length with the hill aimed to create. This also does not mean everything is okay; because like everything, also management is extremely dynamic even for the best management styles, and it must be, and as it is mathematical, also is dependent on the graphics which change over time. There is no simple way or there is no the end which we can say finished there. Neither math is simple as much as this not other scientific branches. All of these are requirement of methodological approximation. Even if its explorer is Descartes, the problem solving steps which I accept them as valid, general and matchless methods for all times also require this, that if you remember, Descartes states these steps as the following ones in Discourse on Method.

- The first was never to accept anything for true which I did not clearly know to be such; that is to say, carefully to avoid precipitancy and prejudice, and to comprise nothing more in my judgment than what was presented to my mind so clearly and distinctly as to exclude all ground of doubt.
- The second, to divide each of the difficulties under examination into as many parts as possible, and as might be necessary for its adequate solution.
- The third, to conduct my thoughts in such order that, by commencing with objects the simplest and easiest to know, I might ascend by little and little, and, as it were, step by step, to the knowledge of the more complex; assigning in thought a certain order even to those objects which in their own nature do not stand in a relation of antecedence and sequence.
- And the last, in every case to make enumerations so complete, and reviews so general, that I might be assured that nothing was omitted.

When we look at these matters in problem solving hierarchy, actually it is not so hard to see that chaotic and probabilistic approximation. Dealing simply with as much as possible parts of problems... We also must divide problems as much as possible, then think the laws must come to life as soon as possible, and then by chaotic methods, first of all we must determine some optimal rules which can prevent our mistakes that we could not predict in spite of our all experience and knowledge, and can show us the ideal picture even if is from far away. These rules can change over time as also can have fixed properties. As change of the rules, if theoretical infrastructure is strong and definite, it is not an excuse application minus. In spite of all possible negations, we must feel compelled, and change should not be made. We cannot

gain anything by constant changing; because the things which are going to be told and discussed about, are not complex more than enough according to the basic structure as also they have no many alternative.

Article 2: Hierarchy

Hierarchical order is basis in people and private or state institutions. In this case, the state uses general or special titles. The titles cannot be used by others that is not the title owner person or institution.

2.1 General shape

The free for the free, the slave for the slave, and the female for the female...

Quran 2:178

Hierarchy is basically superior and subordinate classification in the same group or in different groups. Actually, when we observe the general picture of the universe which is not homogeneous and isotropic, the most evident property of it is hierarchy. Sub-particles form particles or planets and stars form star systems and galaxies. Order of approach to problems and all the other priorities regardless life already sign matchless manner to a hierarchy. One thing is always more important and prior than another thing for human or nature. If there is no wave, there is no matter; if there is no electron, there is no atom; you must build firstly a building foundation to build an apartment; if you spend time with a foreign woman like your wife, then you lose your wife; safety is first during wars, otherwise you die without a single shot. There are much more examples to give. Already, otherwise is chaos, and does not have an identifiable category.

And if Allah had extended [excessively] provision for His servants, they would have committed tyranny throughout the earth. But He sends [it] down in an amount which He wills. Indeed He is, of His servants, Acquainted and Seeing.

So whatever thing you have been given - it is but [for] enjoyment of the worldly life. But what is with Allah is better and more lasting for those who have believed and upon their Lord rely.

Quran 42:27,36

As long as people are together with a learning need and realize it from infancy to old ages, always there are going to be some groups as experienced and more experienced. If the aim is learning in any area of society, this condition spontaneously creates a teacher-student law. To stay away from polyphony which is noise and chaos, in the point of being interlocutor or voting for interlocutor, for emergence of the leaders who represent the groups which there emerge voluntary consensus, sacrifice or adherence to rules obligatory in it, hierarchical order is inevitable.

In the emerging hierarchy, given general titles like "Doctor" or "Colonel" and special titles like "Scholar" or "Sir" cannot used but the owners even as nickname. The illegally users are sometimes condemned as also sometimes can be subjected to serious penalties.

2.2 Some limits

Do good to those whom your right hands possess. Indeed, Allah does not like those who are self-deluding and boastful.

Quran 4:36

In hierarchical order, superior and subordinate classification is completely methodological, and to provide work-efficiency. There is no absolute authority in any phase of hierarchy; but there is order-obey law, and these limits regardless these laws must be clearly stated.

O you who have believed, obey Allah and obey the Messenger and those in authority among you. And if you disagree over anything, refer it to Allah and the Messenger, if you should believe in Allah and the Last Day. That is the best [way] and best in result.

Quran 4:59

This verse orders that we must obey our leaders, and states that we must refer to our holy book. This already means pre-terminated rules in accordance with holy books. Even if obedience is right for leaders, there is no unconditional obedience in any level of hierarchy.

And do not obey the order of the transgressors.

Quran 26:151

This verse is a good example for this, and it subjected obedience to a rule. The state of soft-tempered always is ordered even for top of hierarchical order. Even if leaders are generous, they cannot be acceptable if they hurt people.

Kind speech and forgiveness are better than charity followed by injury. And Allah is Free of need and Forbearing. O you who have believed, do not invalidate your charities with reminders or injury as does one who spends his wealth [only] to be seen by the people and does not believe in Allah and the Last Day. His example is like that of a [large] smooth stone upon which is dust and is hit by a downpour that leaves it bare. They are unable [to keep] anything of what they have earned. And Allah does not guide the disbelieving people.

Quran 2:263-264

These verses are good examples for this. This discipline is one of the most important facts which keep hierarchy standing. Keeping hierarchy standing is not possible for both bottom and top, without sacrifice, generosity and quality dialogue.

Those who spend their wealth in the way of Allah and then do not follow up what they have spent with reminders [of it] or [other] injury will have their reward with their Lord, and there will be no fear concerning them, nor will they grieve.

Quran 2:262

And do not confer favor to acquire more

Quran 74:6

Article 3: Oligarchy

Aristocracy and oligarchy are basis between statesmen. Aristocrats can only exist in oligarchical order because of their wisdom. Family is not counted as the single reason of prestige to be a leader.

3.1 General shape

And within the land are neighboring plots and gardens of grapevines and crops and palm trees, [growing] several from a root or otherwise, watered with one water; but We make some of them exceed others in [quality of] fruit. Indeed in that are signs for a people who reason.

Quran 13:4

Say, "Are those who know equal to those who do not know?"

Quran 39:9

The student is not above the teacher, nor a servant above his master.

Matthew 10:24

Oligarchical managements are the managements which only elite people are placed as managers, and is one of matchless managements elements. Pre-eminence of the elite people is not only dependent on their family. Prior exclusiveness is dependent on wisdom that the following verse is a good example for this.

And [mention, O Muhammad], when Abraham was tried by his Lord with commands and he fulfilled them. [Allah] said, "Indeed, I will make you a leader for the people." [Abraham] said, "And of my descendants?" [Allah] said, "My covenant does not include the wrongdoers."

Quran 2:124

Family does not advance the person who left behind because of own action.

Words of Muhammad from Tirmidhi

As people, they are always uninformed and ignorant. Even if they do not have any information and do not will information when were born, all information prepared is presented, and also teachers were educated before by states. States make them informed by using family and actually by using social state institutions. As primary school student has no superiority to the teacher, in the same manner everybody has no voting right about state management. As has no voting right, if it is acceptable, states use them as slave, that slaves have no voting right even if they have the right to speak about and demanding rights.

Do they distribute the mercy of your Lord? It is We who have apportioned among them their livelihood in the life of this world and have raised some of them above others in degrees [of rank] that they may make use of one another for service. But the mercy of your Lord is better than whatever they accumulate.

Quran 43:32

Look how We have favored [in provision] some of them over others. But the Hereafter is greater in degrees [of difference] and greater in distinction.

Quran 17:21

5 fingers are not equal to each other, all fishes in sea are fishes but have different properties, ornamental dog is also dog as sheep-dog is dog as well; but they have different superiority, and thus have different place in hierarchical order. Even so, man is born, then before walking learns crawling; but when grew up, directly tries to stand. You cannot close the thread by saying like "We're all human."

But if you do not - and you will never be able to - then fear the Fire, whose fuel is men and stones, prepared for the disbelievers.

Quran 2:24**3.2 Some limits**

Look how We have favored [in provision] some of them over others. But the Hereafter is greater in degrees [of difference] and greater in distinction.

Quran 17:21

The Egyptian Pharaoh who is the enemy of Moses, is seized with sense of greatness, and separated his people into classes is a good example for the relation between people and their teachers. If a person recognizes the place where takes place in state as absolute, then it means that the person was wrong. If counts the place as temporary being the person is responsible and trustee, that person was right and spends time for taking people to own quality.

Your servants are your sibling. God made them at your disposal. Whoever if has servants as coreligionist such, he must feed from own, must rig out from own. Do not charge them works which are out of their power. If you charge, then you are going to help them.

Word of Muhammad from Bukhari

It is enough for an individual to see his Muslim brother as insult. The blood, property and dignity of every Muslim is forbidden to Muslims.

Word of Muhammad from Muslim

Everything they do is done for people to see: They make their phylacterieswide and the tassels on their garments long; they love the place of honor at banquets and the most important seats in the synagogues; they love to be greeted with respect in the marketplaces and to be called "Rabbi" by others. But you are not to be called "Rabbi" for you have one Teacher, and you are all brothers. And do not call anyone on earth "father" for you have one Father, and he is in heaven. Nor are you to be called instructors, for you have one Instructor, the Messiah. The greatest among you will be your servant. For those who exalt themselves will be humbled, and those who humble themselves will be exalted.

Matthew 23:5-12

Classification of people in oligarchical order, is not because of an absolute greatness or smallness; but it is completely methodological. It is for simplification of works and to serve for people better manner.

He said, "I was only given it because of knowledge I have." Did he not know that Allah had destroyed before him of generations those who were greater than him in power and greater in accumulation [of wealth]? But the criminals, about their sins, will not be asked.

Quran 28:78

In this verse, Croesus the king of Lydia, claims that information was only given to him because of knowledge he has that means he chose against God. It is not true. For God, first of all, all persons are souls who have no names. In this case, God chooses some leaders and workers as temporary for only this world; but God has already notified rights of people from each level, and forbidden sense of greatness for human.

So whatever thing you have been given - it is but [for] enjoyment of the worldly life.

Quran 42:36

And do not walk upon the earth exultantly. Indeed, you will never tear the earth [apart], and you will never reach the mountains in height.

Quran 17:37

Jesus said to them, "The kings of the Gentiles lord it over them; and those who exercise authority over them call themselves Benefactors. But you are not to be like that. Instead, the greatest among you should be like the youngest, and the one who rules like the one who serves. For who is greater, the one who is at the table or the one who serves?"

Luke 22:25-27

The student is not above the teacher, nor a servant above his master. It is enough for students to be like their teachers, and servants like their masters.

Matthew 10:24-25

Article 4: Monarchy

The basic management method is monarchy. The state is a kingdom. The king is elected from the nobles of the basic race. The state recognizes underground and above-ground resources and territorial waters as own property.

4.1 General shape

So they defeated them by permission of Allah, and David killed Goliath, and Allah gave him the kingship and prophethood and taught him from that which He willed.

Quran 2:251

And their prophet said to them, "Indeed, Allah has sent to you Saul as a king."

Quran 2:247

Monarchy which is natural result of hierarchy and oligarchy, and which is the most compatible with these as cultural structure, is the optimal method which is the most efficient, is the most secure and simple, and is for educating people who are subservient to the rules which everybody has to comply. It has been used as culturally since antiquity; so Magna Carta, is a real human rights declaration which is effective in development process of mankind. Even if it interests England, it is accepted as universal since monarchy is the accepted matchless management which people use it without strange. Magna Carta had done its mission, as laws of motion should have discovered by some one, it did its mission by giving what it should give and the thread closed. The flexibility about monarchy must be maximum as much as this. Absolute authority is not for persons, that such an authority emerges according to consultation in accordance with religion and mind as well. In spite of all their hard positions, religions recognize leadership as service and order consultation. Religions state that leaders have to be sweet-natured, and state otherwise they are going to be subjected to penalties. By these conditions, leadership is almost forced labor and is strenuous more than enough.

So by mercy from Allah, [O Muhammad], you were lenient with them. And if you had been rude [in speech] and harsh in heart, they would have disbanded from about you. So pardon them and ask forgiveness for them and consult them in the matter. And when you have decided, then rely upon Allah. Indeed, Allah loves those who rely [upon Him].

Quran 3:159

This verse is a good example for consultation, and God also orders to his prophet consultation. This condition of course does not block dialectical relation. Still a behaviour can easily be accepted by someone as soft, as also accepted by another one as hard or harder. Everything is with a balance. For example, following verse is about the clear behaviour against grim people, that in this case, someone can accept you as hard and it does not mean anything.

Then do not obey the deniers. They wish that you would soften [in your position], so they would soften [toward you]. And do not obey every worthless habitual swearer. [And] scorner, going about with malicious gossip, A preventer of good, transgressing and sinful, Cruel, moreover, and an illegitimate pretender. Because he is a possessor of wealth and children, When Our verses are recited to him, he says, "Legends of the former peoples." We will brand him upon the snout.

Quran 68:8-16

Ideal states are basically managed according to sacrifice and volunteering principles if you accept them as just. People make sacrifice when they are not pleased, and they show voluntariness when they are pleased, and the third option is not possible as it includes crime as well.

Take away the waste from the silver, and a silver pot comes out for the workman. Take the sinful away from the king, and his throne will stand on what is right and good.

Proverbs of King Solomon 25:4-5

There is a most basic principle in the standard posture of states, and the main expectation is not voluntariness. States do not have to spend time and search about you that are you an ignorant or willful enemy; because already it must have taken the required precautions and must have written the required functions the states handle over them and give healthy results, that protect and survive states about this subject when states could not predict. Right this point, monarchy is the most basic cultural touchstone against such a condition.

Have you not considered the assembly of the Children of Israel after [the time of] Moses when they said to a prophet of theirs, "Send to us a king, and we will fight in the way of Allah"

Quran 2:246

In this verse, people demand their leader as monarch without strange, and is a good example.

There exist three matters, that I'm worried about my ummah: They believe that it will rain when the stars enter some signs, sultan's cruelty, and they deny fate.

Words of Muhammad from Musnad

These words of Muhammad also accepted the leaders as monarch like all the other words and verses as traditional.

As it can be seen over the above stated verses, monarchy is from the regimes which prophets which are the actual representatives of male domination as patriarchs assign monarch or which prophets are both patriarchs and monarchs, that male domination is one of matchless cultural phenomena, and can never be ignored especially for monarchy.

And We sent not before you except men to whom We revealed [Our message]. So ask the people of the message if you do not know.

Quran 16:43

Women can never be leader of men in any religion. This is one of the most basic and matchless principle for God.

Men are in charge of women by [right of] what Allah has given one over the other and what they spend [for maintenance] from their wealth.

Quran 4:34

Women cannot be president or army commander which require male domination; so even God did not give prophethood them which were matured from women. Even so Gabriel visited some of that matured women like Miriam who is mother of Jesus regardless hard hierarchical rules of angles.

And [mention, O Muhammad], when your Lord said to the angels, "Indeed, I will make upon the earth a successive authority." They said, "Will You place upon it one who causes corruption therein and sheds blood, while we declare Your praise and sanctify You?" Allah said, "Indeed, I know that which you do not know."

Quran 2:30

This verse is a good example for this.

Many people were matured from men. As women, no one of them was matured except Miriam who is daughter of Amram, the Pharaoh's wife Asiya, Khadija who is daughter of Khuwaylid, Fatimah who is daughter of Muhammad.

Word of Muhammad from Muslim

The greatest one of these four women is Miriam according to Muhammad. Even so, she could not be given prophethood; but Gabriel visited her by saying "We are trusted ambassadors who God sent to you.", this is an evidence of their "like-prophet" status. These hard disciplines are right of God. The people who believe in these otherwise are insufficient. Even if a reckless mafia leader demands something politely, he is predictable against otherwise, and he does not have to cry out. Also God is like this.

O you who have believed, do not prohibit the good things which Allah has made lawful to you and do not transgress. Indeed, Allah does not like transgressors.

Quran 5:87

This verse is a good example. This is a serious threat. Even you cannot understand how you get off your right way.

As democracy, it is Utopian. If monarchy is used as the first step, then democracy can be positive result of it over time, that is almost impossible.

A sedition which is seduced by word is like the sedition which is seduced by sword.

Words of Muhammad from ibn Majah

As also you can see over this hadith, in the nations who could not achieved required informational and moral grade, democracy causes fatal results in such states. You cannot talk about maturity level of democracy in such states, as also management game is going to be extended and complicate needless manner against us.

No body gets off the right way but insists on struggle.

Words of Muhammad from ibn Majah

This hadith touches one serious damage of these negativity. Political parties can easily turn into a phenomenon which consume all of our labor to keep state standing, that the main aim of parties is becoming a consultation element for state duty to bring the right solution out. Emerging different consensus in the same party or between parties are for state duty, and the otherwise is the work of separatists that is not acceptable. They are clowns

infiltrated into the state. It is almost impossible to block this, that corruption starts publicly or lawfully. This means that sedition appears in the heart of people there, injustices and dissatisfaction increase and state order is jerked.

People think simple, and most of them demand basic things. Their basic missions is not criticizing historical and philosophical information and making decisions about today and future. This is nothing to condemn. Each one of people wants to save a patient by making a heart transplant; but only the persons who are authorized are accepted for the operation.

Leaving what is not own concern is because of being good Muslim of that person.

Words of Muhammad from Tirmidhi

This is a good example for this, and this does not mean herding like sheep of people.

The fact which I fear most is the leaders who drift people into perversity.

Words of Muhammad from Muslim

Everything is with a balance, and order-obedience law needs to be calibrated correctly against destruction which is both from people and leader.

Stop arguing. Your predecessors perished just because of this.

Words of Muhammad from Tirmidhi

Additionally, three matter stated below can easily occur in democratic orders, and are good examples for right to speak of people in the balance of order-obedience law and order superiority of the leaders. "Stinginess obeyed" means people lost self-defense faculty and means people cannot educate own leader. "Desire and whim followed" means stimulating people got lost from both top and bottom of the hierarchical order, and means people follow unreferenced and uncategorized facts instead of right information. "Every viewer likes own idea" means state lost its disciplinary identity on people, and is another destructive minus.

The facts which I fear most, are these three destructive danger: stinginess obeyed, desire and whim followed, every viewer likes own idea.

Words of Muhammad from Tirmidhi

Additionally, it can easily cause the facts which are signs of apocalypse. The following hadith is a good example for this; because as it was said above, political party is risky, and people are not resourceful enough. There is no sentence starts by "You" or "I" in ideal states. There is only socialist structure which starts by "We", and people know that they do their own works as duty.

Apocalypse does not take place unless people bragging against themselves in mosques.

Words of Muhammad from Nasa'i

Otherwise is sign of the apocalypse as you can see it over the above stated hadith as well; because Islam or the other religions are not democratic. There is nothing like political party or voting, that is forbidden.

[Adhere to it], turning in repentance to Him, and fear Him and establish prayer and do not be of those who associate others with Allah [Or] of those who have divided their religion and become sects, every faction rejoicing in what it has.

Quran 30:31-32

And whoever is an ally of Allah and His Messenger and those who have believed - indeed, the party of Allah - they will be the predominant.

Quran 5:56

4.2 Family motivation

I swear by the father and that which was born [of him],

Quran 90:3

As male is leader in male dominant people, traditional educating method is educating son who is father of future by father of today. This is one of the most basic hierarchical rules. It includes deep meanings in people, and also is a strong motivation between statesmen. Because of the same reason, family motivation is important for the elite family who manage state. There is not such motivation in democratic orders which cause frequent manager exchanges; so elected people can charge own responsibilities to people as also can work undisciplined since they are going to change.

And We gave to Him Isaac and Jacob and placed in his descendants prophethood and scripture. And We gave him his reward in this world, and indeed, he is in the Hereafter among the righteous.

Quran 29:27

This verse also has the same motivation since statesmen have prophetic profession. Additionally, in holy books, there are many sentences which are addressed people as family which persons lead them because of the same service motivation.

Indeed, Allah chose Adam and Noah and the family of Abraham and the family of Imran over the worlds - Descendants, some of them from others. And Allah is Hearing and Knowing.

Quran 4:33-34

This verse is a good example for this. Additionally, there are many other people addressed with family such as Moses, Aaron, David, Jacop, Lut and even the cruel Pharaoh who is enemy of Moses.

And [recall] when We saved your forefathers from the people of Pharaoh, who afflicted you with the worst torment, slaughtering your [newborn] sons and keeping your females alive. And in that was a great trial from your Lord.

Quran 2:49

Additionally, Muhammad entrusted his family to his ummah like kings entrust their people.

I leave to you two charge. If you follow them, you do not get off the right way. One of them is the book of God. The other one is my family.

Words of Muhammad from Muslim

God also recognize economy right of family o Muhammad by verses, that this also signs monarchs to spend for family.

And what Allah restored to His Messenger from the people of the towns - it is for Allah and for the Messenger and for [his] near relatives and orphans and the [stranded] traveler - so that it will not be a perpetual distribution among the rich from among you. And whatever the Messenger has given you - take; and what he has forbidden you - refrain from. And fear Allah ; indeed, Allah is severe in penalty.

Quran 59:7

Respect to King must be at the highest level in monarchy. Another statesman cannot be accepted equal to the king whatever they did. Already important things are waited for from important people, and states educate his managers for this. In the same manner family of king must be protected and people must respect them.

Article 5: Socialism

The state is a social constitutional state. The state is obliged to organize people by laws, and the people are obliged to make the necessary effort in accordance with the laws which were determined for them.

5.1 General shape

And Allah has favored some of you over others in provision. But those who were favored would not hand over their provision to those whom their right hands possess so they would be equal to them therein. Then is it the favor of Allah they reject?

Quran 16:71

You cannot be Muslim unless you wish for your Muslim brother the facts you wish for your own.

Words of Muhammad from Bukhari

As the name implies, they are the systems which people govern themselves and are trained for human beings there. Basically, the systems that can prevent statesmen or members of society who will hide behind strict laws and make excuses for inadequacies or intentions are sensitive social systems that have high standards in social relations and do not accept the rest.

And from their properties was [given] the right of the [needy] petitioner and the deprived.

Quran 51:19

These and more verses are good examples of this social relationship.

Although socialism is a philosophy with a more economic background, it can bring non-alternative moral rules for both society and the state, which is the natural result of this philosophy that regulates our lives. Hereby, socialism, which has a wide wealth of meaning, can be applied easily and harmoniously in republics or kingdoms, and it can manifest itself in an obvious and successful way.

5.2 Basic application principles

And what Allah restored to His Messenger from the people of the towns - it is for Allah and for the Messenger and for [his] near relatives and orphans and the [stranded] traveler - so that it will not be a perpetual distribution among the rich from among you. And whatever the Messenger has given you - take; and what he has forbidden you - refrain from. And fear Allah ; indeed, Allah is severe in penalty.

Quran 59:7

As can be seen from this verse, Allah has given the prophet the control of money in all Muslim lands. He cited the possibility that the land was the only place where the rich lived. While this does not limit the earnings of capitals, in fact, the control of money is in the state, and the state must ensure justice through appropriate transformations. Despite the capitals it contains, the state should still be a socialist state as "Social-Capitalist", although not authentic to the needy.

This verse also says that the land is the common property of people; but this is again with some agreements, and it may varies by time. For example, when Khalif Omar was conquered around Syria, Khalif Ali said, "Let us divide the land among the veterans,

as Muhammad did in Khyber." He opposed the proposal by this verse and said "What people will do in the future.", and made the property of the state. Islam allows you to use and sow as much power as you can, and if you don't sow it for a certain time, it takes away from you and gives it to someone else. There was not even a known title deed and it emerged in the Ottoman Empire in a very advanced period. This concept of title deed also depends on time and is not an absolute share. It's like saying, "I made my plan, and I gave it to you for 500 years because the population and therefore the land won't be a problem.". Today, however, it is completely deviated from its purpose and only small measures are taken to prevent the fields from shrinking. When the world population is 300 million in the Omar Era and even if there is no land problem even if it is inherited from the family, we should know that we have to make new transformations in order to distribute justice to 8 billion people, if we look at the sensitivity of Omar. We need to reconsider the situation and owe it to the people we need to borrow and redefine what it can inherit from things like houses, land or factory buildings.

O you who have believed, do not consume one another's wealth unjustly but only [in lawful] business by mutual consent.

Quran 4:29

Whether the slave-master law, the law of exchange in the market or the social and economic sanctions imposed by the states, the boundary that should not be surpassed is the mutual consent except for the deliberate or incompatible persons who must be forced. In this case, the ideal social states must spontaneously recognize the basic needs of people, such as food and shelter, even if they do not work; because the states that there is no person who does not know own job because of the emerging high potential, are ideal states and it is difficult to find such. The state can acquire workers within the framework of the opportunities it provides. It is impossible for almost every state to provide job guarantee to every student or any citizen who has graduated from their schools even if they are of the same quality. In this case, states should recognize the right to not work and restrict the rights when necessary according to the potentials arising. The state should derive socialist laws with the necessary transformations according to the basic principles it sets in practice.

Article 6: Interreligious Dialog

The state recognizes, encourages, and takes the necessary measures for interreligious dialogue in accordance with the laws it sets. The State recognizes all religions that do not contain orders contrary to human rights and protects its members in the area of responsibility.

6.1 General shape

Allah does not forbid you from those who do not fight you because of religion and do not expel you from your homes - from being righteous toward them and acting justly toward them. Indeed, Allah loves those who act justly.

Quran 60:8

O you who have believed, be persistently standing firm for Allah, witnesses in justice, and do not let the hatred of a people prevent you from being just. Be just; that is nearer to righteousness. And fear Allah ; indeed, Allah is Acquainted with what you do.

Quran 5:8

But those who break the covenant of Allah after contracting it and sever that which Allah has ordered to be joined and spread corruption on earth - for them is the curse, and they will have the worst home.

Quran 13:25

As explained in Article 1, there will be two different ideas that may arise from the possibility of disagreement as an absolute phenomenon due to the names of Rahman and Rahim, and there must be a law between these two different communities. For this reason, interreligious dialogue; it is a compulsory religious duty among states, among social organizations or among members of society.

And for their houses - doors and couches [of silver] upon which to recline, And gold ornament. But all that is not but the enjoyment of worldly life. And the Hereafter with your Lord is for the righteous.

Quran 43:34-35

As can be seen from this verse, as all people cannot become a single nation who has allied in profanity, also there will be no end to people who do not believe.

The highest of jihad is to tell the truth to president.

Words of Muhammad from Tirmidhi

Everything they do is done for people to see: They make their phylacteries wide and the tassels on their garments long; they love the place of honor at banquets and the most important seats in the synagogues; they love to be greeted with respect in the marketplaces and to be called "Rabbi" by others. But you are not to be called "Rabbi" for you have one Teacher, and you are all brothers. And do not call anyone on earth "father" for you have one Father, and he is in heaven. Nor are you to be called instructors, for you have one Instructor, the Messiah. The greatest among you will be your servant. For those who exalt themselves will be humbled, and those who humble themselves will be exalted.

Matthew 23:5-12

Since different ideas will never come to an end; therefore, the greatest jihad should be to tell the president the truth, considering that every act of the believer is a jihad and must be included in a jihad category. According to Muhammad, the small jihad is the jihad made with the sword and the big jihad is the jihad with the exquisite.

On the way back from a war, he addressed those who said: "You have returned from a good place! You have returned from a small jihad to a great jihad." The companions said: "O Messenger of Allah! What is the great jihad?" The Messenger of Allah said: "It is the struggle of the servant against oneself."

Words of Muhammad from Bayhaqi

None of this is as superior to the jihad against the president. It is a product of ignorance to understand this as saying a few words by boldly shouting in front of a president; because it is not meant to trigger a human being who can only activate his quantity by means of a single command and thus be the means of the greatest good. This also means that the greatest enemies always come out of our own. Those who do wrong are not a reference or defense tool for truths. People referring to inaccuracies are not mature. Those who look at the wrong people and do wrong are also lost.

I asked three things of my Lord. He gave me two of what I wanted, and he gave me one. I asked my Lord not to perish my nation with famine, and promised that he would fulfill my will. I also asked him not to perish my nation by drowning in water, and promised to fulfill my wish. Then I asked my nation not to fight among themselves and let them fight, and he denied it to me.

Words of Muhammad from Muslim

I have asked my Lord not to destroy my nation. My Lord commanded to accept my prayer. He said: "Their law will be among them. When they sin, I will bring them down and make them shoot." I wished it would go away; but my Lord did not lift it.

Words of Muhammad from Muslim

As can be seen from these hadith, God will not always prevent corruption among Muslims; because God's greatest enemy will not emerge from the faithless countries. When Muslims fall against each other, God tells them that he will inflict cruelty on them.

[Mention] when he ran away to the laden ship. And he drew lots and was among the losers. Then the fish swallowed him, while he was blameworthy.

Quran 37:140-142

In these verses, the story of the prophet Jonah is told. When he did not come from God, he left the mission and fled. God said to Him "Do you know what does creating mean?". He wanted him to empathize and try to understand God. This is irrational to God, as stated above.

O people! Do not wish to encounter the enemy! Ask God for your pleasure! But be patient when you encounter the enemy! Know that heaven is under the shadow of the swords!

Words of Muhammad from Bukhari

This hadith is actually a summary of the things described above and is a good ending. "Heaven is under the shadow of the swords." is the last word to say in case of war. This should be the slogan of the soldiers. Soldiers should be known with the same discipline every day; but if we look back from one day in the future, blood should not be shed for years if necessary.

6.2 Social relations and minorities

States, whether religious or not, will always have religious and citizens of different religions. In this case, there must be a line in human relations.

And do not insult those they invoke other than Allah, lest they insult Allah in enmity without knowledge. Thus We have made pleasing to every community their deeds. Then to their Lord is their return, and He will inform them about what they used to do.

Quran 6:108

And the servants of the Most Merciful are those who walk upon the earth easily, and when the ignorant address them [harshly], they say [words of] peace,

Quran 25:63

And not equal are the good deed and the bad. Repel [evil] by that [deed] which is better; and thereupon the one whom between you and him is enmity [will become] as though he was a devoted friend.

Quran 41:34

Then did they feel secure from the plan of Allah ? But no one feels secure from the plan of Allah except the losing people.

Quran 7:99

The above verses are some examples in this line. However, people may, for some reason, always have to live in other states to become their own religion as a minority. In this case, states have the right to protect and raise people from their religion. It examines their situation and takes necessary precautions or warns them. As long as every nation has people in another nation, inter-religious dialogue stands out as a mandatory duty.

There are also some characteristics of the Mahdi, and this is a good morality that is complex, patient and challenging. It takes its own right and does not interfere with anyone else. This is the morality of the Quran. The Quran commands us to behave away from the claim of being even to the salute in war, which is blasphemy.

He will not shout or cry out, or raise his voice in the streets. A bruised reed he will not break, and a smoldering wick he will not snuff out. In faithfulness he will bring forth justice; he will not falter or be discouraged till he establishes justice on earth. In his teaching the islands will put their hope.

Isaiah 42:2-4

Then declare what you are commanded and turn away from the polytheists.

Quran 15:94

O you who have believed, when you go forth [to fight] in the cause of Allah, investigate; and do not say to one who gives you [a greeting of] peace "You are not a believer," aspiring for the goods of worldly life; for with Allah are many acquisitions. You [yourselves] were like that before; then Allah conferred His favor upon you, so investigate. Indeed Allah is ever, with what you do, Acquainted.

Quran 4:94

International Relations

The main purpose of life for the human being is to live in peace and providing possibility to oneself. Also every action creates a law. For example, when you turn to a person, there emerges a law between you and that person. As a requirement, you cannot lie to that person or you cannot make a bad decision if you have no information about. If you enter a foreign land to fight, regardless of the outcome of the war, there is accepted as your homeland. If you win the war, you really have a new homeland. If you plunder, rape women or kill old and children, you will be accepted as a traitor to every nation. Laws, whether we know it or not, or misinterpret it, are absolutely certain for the conservation of information.

If this is the case; then we have to live in institutions, states or even within the family according to the rules that are binding and, of course, there will also be law between the nations who want to live together and have defined borders to realize the basic purpose of life; this is not an obstacle to acting as a single state despite all our differences, considering the abundance and diversity of laws that bind us in daily life.

In addition to the principles governing and managing our lives in the land we live in, one of the principles that apply to nations can be more effective, safer and more valuable than the other; therefore, in order to establish and maintain healthy relations, we must put all our problems on the table without transitioning, and when we are not satisfied, we must make sacrifices or voluntarily when we agree, but in all cases we should create fair laws.

Article 7: Expansionism Rejection

The state does not recognize expansionism policy for resources or for the sake of religion; but it protects its own religion internationally and defends it with own army when necessary.

7.1 Cultural development process of humanity

Proclaiming the good news of the kingdom of God

Luke 8:1

According to Jesus, the Bible is to preach the gospel of the Kingdom of God, as it is written in the lines above. This is a separate function and characteristic of the Bible and the period of Jesus. Its basic task is to remind people of the social rules they have forgotten, as in all religions, and to scare them into taking into account their work. It is, however, a warning and preparation for future events. They tell people that the King will come soon and that Jesus will be both a leader and a helper. The King, according to Jesus, is another helper from God, which means that Jesus and the Mahdi will be assistant prophets of Muhammad.

Jesus replied, Anyone who loves me will obey my teaching. My Father will love them, and we will come to them and make our home with them. Anyone who does not love me will not obey my teaching. These words you hear are not my own; they belong to the Father who sent me. All this I have spoken while still with you. But the Advocate, the Holy Spirit, whom the Father will send in my name, will teach you all things and will remind you of everything I have said to you. Peace I leave with you; my peace I give you. I do not give to you as the world gives. Do not let your hearts be troubled and do not be afraid. You heard me say, I am going away and I am coming back to you. If you loved me, you would be glad that I am going to the Father, for the Father is greater than I. I have told you now before it happens, so that when it does happen you will believe. I will not say much more to you, for the prince of this world is coming. He has no hold over me, but he comes so that the world may learn that I love the Father and do exactly what my Father has commanded me. Come now; let us leave.

John 14:23-31

Jesus is a prophet of Israel. The religion of the Israelites actually binds only the Israelites. In the Torah, for example, God always speaks openly to the Israelites. This means that even if there is a stretch, one of the other nations cannot be responsible for Torah. There is a stretch for each religion; because it is the fundamental duty of religions to teach the rules and introduce Him to someone who is unaware of God and the laws. If someone who is not one of you comes to you to learn God, you cannot turn your back on that person, even if the address in your book only connects your nation. If you return, it is a profanity and the greatest cruelty to be done. You have to teach that man religion, and he is now counted from your nation, you cannot separate from your own brothers.

And We have not sent you except comprehensively to mankind as a bringer of good tidings and a warner. But most of the people do not know.

Quran 34:28

Nevertheless, Christianity has to be a national religion, but as a preparatory religion, it has gained the status of Islam, a global

religion. The biblical appeals never bind only the Israelites. There are even threats that other nations will protect it if they does not claim the Bible, which is the same in Islam.

Jesus said to them, Have you never read in the Scriptures: The stone the builders rejected has become the cornerstone; the Lord has done this, and it is marvelous in our eyes? Therefore I tell you that the kingdom of God will be taken away from you and given to a people who will produce its fruit. Anyone who falls on this stone will be broken to pieces; anyone on whom it falls will be crushed.

Matthew 21:42-44

O you who have believed, whoever of you should revert from his religion - Allah will bring forth [in place of them] a people He will love and who will love Him [who are] humble toward the believers, powerful against the disbelievers; they strive in the cause of Allah and do not fear the blame of a critic. That is the favor of Allah; He bestows it upon whom He wills. And Allah is all-Encompassing and Knowing.

Quran 5:54

The Bible appeals not only to Jesus' own disciples, but also to future people. It is all believing people that Jesus speaks about, when you speak of the future.

All of these preparations are to prepare mankind for the Peace Period, which is a phenomenon in all times in the cultural development of humanity. Even though the sufferings will be experienced, in the end, all authentic leaders and insights will be removed and human beings will continue to live in peace in the security provided. Jihad with the army will no longer be a duty.

I will take away the chariots from Ephraim and the warhorses from Jerusalem, and the battle bow will be broken. He will proclaim peace to the nations. His rule will extend from sea to sea and from the River to the ends of the earth.

Zechariah 9:10

All the prophets; Moses, Jesus and Muhammad have again told us that this will happen in the near future and it is said that humanity will be filled with peace as the container is filled with water.

The earth will be filled with peace. There will be no hostility among anyone. All hostilities, struggles, envy, and will certainly disappear.

Words of Muhammad from Muslim

And We have already written in the book [of Psalms] after the [previous] mention that the land [of Paradise] is inherited by My righteous servants.

Quran 21:105

Allah has promised those who have believed among you and done righteous deeds that He will surely grant them succession [to authority] upon the earth just as He granted it to those before them and that He will surely establish for them [therein] their religion which He has preferred for them and that He will surely substitute for them, after their fear, security, [for] they worship Me, not associating anything with Me. But whoever disbelieves after that - then those are the defiantly disobedient.

Quran 24:55

I will not say much more to you, for the prince of this world is coming. He has no hold over me.

John 14:30

Three things are the basis of faith. First, we cannot annoy the person who says "there is no god except Allah", that is, we do not declare as non-Islam because of an act that does not conform to Islam. Secondly, Jihad by sword will continue from the moment God sends me as a prophet until the generation of my ummah will fight the Dajjal. The justice of the justice cannot eradicate Jihad by sword, nor can the persecution persecute it. The third is believe in destiny.

Words of Muhammad from Abu David

As can be seen from the above verse, the Peace Period also takes place in the Psalms and Torah besides the Bible. It is explained in detail and there is no harm in its use. The following hadith is a good example.

Even if it is a sign by me, bring it to the people. You can also inform from the Israelites. There's nothing wrong with that. Anyone who deliberately denies me lies, prepare for his place in hell.

Words of Muhammad from Tirmidhi

7.2 Abrahamism

Judaism, Christianity or Islam are Abrahamic religions. All Abrahamic religions are the continuation and renewal of Abraham's religion.

And We gave to Him Isaac and Jacob and placed in his descendants prophethood and scripture. And We gave him his reward in this world, and indeed, he is in the Hereafter among the righteous.

Quran 29:27

This verse is good evidence for this. This verse means that no prophet will come from any lineage that is not a descendant of Abraham, and all religions are therefore connected to Abraham. This is the only feature of Abrahamic religion, except for superstitious religions. If Monotheistic religion is included to superstitious religions for comparison, it is inadequate; because all religions are monotheistic and call to God, the only god.

Say, [O believers], "We have believed in Allah and what has been revealed to us and what has been revealed to Abraham and Ishmael and Isaac and Jacob and the Descendants and what was given to Moses and Jesus and what was given to the prophets from their Lord. We make no distinction between any of them, and we are Muslims [in submission] to Him."

Quran 2:136

This verse also determines the necessary creed. Moses and Jesus are the prophets of Israel. This means that since Israel is the nickname of the prophet Jacob, in fact they are the son of the prophet Jacob, and Jacob is the son of Isaac. Isaac is the brother of Ishmael and the sons of Abraham, and the owner of the last book is from Ismail's descendants, and is the prophet Muhammad, and his deputy is the king of all nations mentioned in the Torah and the Gospel that is actually not a king, is on prophethood, is a liberator or ruler who rules by the information already existing.

And [recall, O People of the Scripture], when Allah took the covenant of the prophets, [saying], "Whatever I give you of the Scripture and wisdom and then there comes to you a messenger confirming what is with you, you [must] believe in him and support him." [Allah] said, "Have you acknowledged and taken upon that My commitment?" They said, "We have acknowledged it." He said, "Then bear witness, and I am with you among the witnesses."

Quran 3:81

The helpers of the prophets, ie the prophets who follow the same book and do not bring a new verse, do not have to live or be chosen by them in the time of their prophet. Allah shows them their glad tidings, and glorifies them. Allah chooses the helpers.

And appoint for me a minister from my family. Aaron, my brother. Increase through him my strength. And let him share my task. That we may exalt You much. And remember You much. Indeed, You are of us ever Seeing. [Allah] said, You have been granted your request, O Moses. And We had already conferred favor upon you another time. When We inspired to your mother what We inspired, [Saying], Cast him into the chest and cast it into the river, and the river will throw it onto the bank; there will take him an enemy to Me and an enemy to him. And I bestowed upon you love from Me that you would be brought up under My eye.

Quran 20:29-39

In this verse, we can see that Moses asked God for his brother Aaron as a partner in his work, that is, as an assistant prophet.

And We gave him out of Our mercy his brother Aaron as a prophet.

Quran 19:53

In return, God accepted his prayer and made Aaron help him. As it is said, if he wishes his mercy, he accepts the proposals but if he imposes his choice on the prophet, he had already taken the word of the prophets.

Mahdi is a chosen prophet, and Muhammad has no will with regard to Mahdi.

So the angels called him while he was standing in prayer in the chamber. "Indeed, Allah gives you good tidings of John, confirming a word from Allah and [who will be] honorable, abstaining [from women], and a prophet from among the righteous."

Quran 3:39

For Muhammad, Mahdi is like Solomon of David, John of Jesus, or Aaron of Moses.

Muhammad is not the father of [any] one of your men, but [he is] the Messenger of Allah and last of the prophets. And ever is Allah, of all things, Knowing.

Quran 33:40

The verse saying that Muhammad was the last prophet says that he is last of the prophet. The correct translation should be "last of the prophets". "the" here does not mean black-haired prophets for the prophets are either the owner of the book or the helper.

Mahdi is one of the children of my daughter Fatima and one of my family.

Words of Muhammad from Abu David

Mahdi is not a prophet of Israel; but is Abrahamic prophet.

And We gave to Him Isaac and Jacob and placed in his descendants prophethood and scripture. And We gave him his reward in this world, and indeed, he is in the Hereafter among the righteous.

Quran 29:27

They say, "Be Jews or Christians [so] you will be guided." Say, "Rather, [we follow] the religion of Abraham, inclining toward truth, and he was not of the polytheists."

Quran 2:135

Abraham was neither a Jew nor a Christian, but he was one inclining toward truth, a Muslim [submitting to Allah]. And he was not of the polytheists.

Quran 3:67

As can be seen from these verses, Islam is also Abrahamism; but neither Christianity nor Judaism. He is the easiest religion of all time and may Allah curse those who make it difficult, and let him run the hardest slopes in the world and the Hereafter. And over-simplifying.

And Allah wants to lighten for you [your difficulties]; and mankind was created weak.

Quran 4:28

Allah intends for you ease and does not intend for you hardship.

Quran 2:185

He has chosen you and has not placed upon you in the religion any difficulty.

Quran 22:78

Muhammad describes Islam as simplified Abrahamism.

Religion is convenience.

Words of Muhammad from Bukhari

I was sent with simplified Abrahamism.

Words of Muhammad from Musnad

Article 8: Internationalism

The state acquires strategic partners to protect the world order in order primarily to protect its interests. Recognize and apply international laws.

8.1 General shape

The Byzantines have been defeated. In the nearest land. But they, after their defeat, will overcome. Within three to nine years. To Allah belongs the command before and after. And that day the believers will rejoice. In the victory of Allah . He gives victory to whom He wills, and He is the Exalted in Might, the Merciful.

Quran 30:2-5

Since states will have to submit to the unity of ideas in the world, one of the conditions of keeping the state order alive is to preserve the world order. For this reason, instead of acting strictly, international relations should be social; but this should not be done so that only menstruation can be found. The necessity of the agreements made when necessary, even in the war, should be agreed and be kept to the end.

Righteousness is not that you turn your faces toward the east or the west, but [true] righteousness is [in] one who believes in Allah, the Last Day, the angels, the Book, and the prophets and gives wealth, in spite of love for it, to relatives, orphans, the needy, the traveler, those who ask [for help], and for freeing slaves; [and who] establishes prayer and gives zakah; [those who] fulfill their promise when they promise; and [those who] are patient in poverty and hardship and during battle. Those are the ones who have been true, and it is those who are the righteous.

Quran 2:177

8.2 Some limits

And whoever is an ally to them among you - then indeed, he is [one] of them.

Quran 5:51

A friend is a person or a state that can deliver arms and star-board. Even the people of the states are not friendly to them. States hold the police force against their own people. Apart from that, the ignorant people who consider themselves friendly to the state can gnaw at the background despite all the services you provide; therefore, not everyone is respected, even from his own people. The alliance with foreign states may not mean true friends. Their people can be bigger enemies; therefore, people who do not actively fight with you about religion at once are kindly or trusted if they make a deal.

Allah does not forbid you from those who do not fight you because of religion and do not expel you from your homes - from being righteous toward them and acting justly toward them. Indeed, Allah loves those who act justly.

Quran 60:8

In short, religion teaches man to live in accordance with the law without being crushed with gratitude, and in many cases God points to the other world in return; because someone must put his hand under the stone and must be patient until the end of the claim. What religion taught in a nutshell is, "Saddle is not load to Donkey." means.

If you do good, you do good for yourselves; and if you do evil, [you do it] to yourselves.

Quran 17:7

"Don't come to me by mistake and give you the following." God says. The person who claims the right to defend religion is exactly the same as the person who expects God's reward for having sex, and for sex, God is writing good deeds and encouraging marriage. In this case, when the person claiming cannot get own right, he cannot say that I am not having sex anymore, and to be honest, it is foolish. Friendship begins only when you accept religion in this way, and despite all the possible loneliness and suffering that appear in your eyes, the prophet is the greatest friend, and Allah says in the pain of his life when the Prophet Zechariah says during sawing, "Oh no more!". "If you moan, I will erase your name from prophecy!" he threatened; therefore, friendship is not an easy-to-understand phenomenon, and most people are

not already friends. No verse in any holy book prevents an international attitude or an ally. The degree of rapprochement between the two foreigner states may not seem to be a degree of friendship to many, since they themselves are not trained and are not voluntary, but incapable of being broad.

Never will you attain the good [reward] until you spend [in the way of Allah] from that which you love. And whatever you spend - indeed, Allah is Knowing of it.

Quran 3:92

s

Article 9: Bilateral Relations

The State is not involved in any strategic alliance except for a consortium with one or more international states. The state adopts bilateral relations in its international relations.

9.1 Obligation arising from economic phenomena

O you who have believed, do not consume one another's wealth unjustly but only [in lawful] business by mutual consent. And do not kill yourselves [or one another]. Indeed, Allah is to you ever Merciful.

Quran 4:29

As long as there is a second state in the world other than you whose first priority is the development of the possibilities of the state itself and the next priority is to rise to the top of the international markets, the established economic associations have no theoretical benefit in today's understandable state; because in this case, regardless of whether money or exchange is used, the phenomenon we call "exchange rate" today will always occur. This means that situations like the single currency, the same currency in the bilateral relations, or the same currency between the states that have established partial unions will not be of any use all over the world. In all of them, one state will certainly feel the need to compete with the other state or a desire to give up and will be grateful if it is superior to you during trade. It will either not sell goods or sell it in part and will demand, for example, 1 unit of labor versus 2 units of labor, or will charge tax.

As for federations, the type of federation between economically independent states poses a risk both for the reasons mentioned above and for security reasons. The form of independence in internal and external affairs is extremely important to maintain the level of friendship in both international relations and the federation. If the federation is responsible for the behaviors of the members of the federation which are considered to be the cause of war in the case of independence given in the foreign affairs, there must be a single line in the foreign relations. This, in fact, is extremely conservative and unnecessary both for the members of the federation and therefore for the development of the federation and for maintaining international relations. The independence of foreign affairs is meaningless if the economic strategy is not in a position to attract all members to the same level; because economically, federations or confederations also have a special case that the state or federation gathered around; If federations and confederations have the power to apply the constitutional and legal standards determined in the phenomena such as urbanism, economic infrastructure and army modernization to every member of the federation or confederation. Otherwise, states should make their own decisions to their partners, and even in wars, they should act solely with consensus. On this occasion, it is possible

to prevent the hostility that may arise in the world and gray spots can be formed for peace.

9.2 Obligation arising from bad administrations

And those who join that which Allah has ordered to be joined and fear their Lord and are afraid of the evil of [their] account, And those who are patient, seeking the countenance of their Lord, and establish prayer and spend from what We have provided for them secretly and publicly and prevent evil with good - those will have the good consequence of [this] home - Gardens of perpetual residence; they will enter them with whoever were righteous among their fathers, their spouses and their descendants. And the angels will enter upon them from every gate, [saying], "Peace be upon you for what you patiently endured. And excellent is the final home." But those who break the covenant of Allah after contracting it and sever that which Allah has ordered to be joined and spread corruption on earth - for them is the curse, and they will have the worst home.

Quran 13: 21-25

One of the most basic scientific disciplines is to try to falsify the right information; because the truth of a knowledge is most clearly revealed only if you are unable to falsify that information. The same applies to all possible units. Unions are good if theoretically dialectic relations are formed correctly; but this is practically impossible; the dynamics of keeping the troops alive must then be different from a simple consensus. It also matters how unity is.

In this case, instead of misleading the whole unity with possible false thoughts that will arise in time, the opposition "must" always be allowed as guarantor.

So race to [all that is] good. Wherever you may be, Allah will bring you all together. Indeed, Allah is over all things competent.

Quran 2:148

And if it were not that the people would become one community [of disbelievers], We would have made for those who disbelieve in the Most Merciful - for their houses - ceilings and stairways of silver upon which to mount.

Quran 43:33

Mankind was [of] one nation [before their deviation]; then Allah sent the prophets as bringers of good tidings and warners and sent down with them the Scripture in truth to judge between the people concerning that in which they differed.

Quran 43:33

If the union is right, the opposition does its job wrongly, but it will not harm the union. If the unity is wrong, the opposition will surely sooner or later win by defending the truth; because although people are prejudiced and ignorant, those who insist on wrong will be regarded as extremists over time, and truth will prevail, both for its precise lines and for gray points, for reasons of supportive indirect interest, and for people who believe, with the help of God who manages events, with the help of God. The hadith of Muhammad that "My ummah does not gather on the branch." is a good example. In this case, extremist conservatism will be considered extremism and conservative individuals in the union claim will gain direct divisive status regardless of their intentions.

Indeed, those who have divided their religion and become sects - you, [O Muhammad], are not [associated] with them in anything. Their affair is only [left] to Allah ; then He will inform them about what they used to do.

Quran 6:159

This verse is a good example of this; because in such conception of conservative unity, people will have to be put under pressure, and although the unity grows as a result of pressure, different and hostile groups will be formed, unrest will increase and the conservatives will not accept the others from themselves, even if they do not have the rights to separate the prophets have.

Whoever tries to learn a word which a group does not want to be heard, melted bullet is poured into his ears on the Day of Resurrection.

Words of Muhammad from Bukhari

This hadith is a good example of the importance of keeping the troops alive, along with all other examples. However, the motivation of different groups or states to stand on their own feet should be respected, since it is a human or a state that you cannot do everything you say, it is also in line with the basic principle of opposition and should be supported despite all possible setbacks.

Indeed, those who have divided their religion and become sects - you, [O Muhammad], are not [associated] with them in anything. Their affair is only [left] to Allah ; then He will inform them about what they used to do.

Quran 6:159

Despite this right of separation as a prophet, Muhammad said, "If I did not know that you would perish, I would say who I will leave." and he did not leave the caliph in his place. Omar bin Abdulaziz, one of the few Rashid caliph that can be counted throughout Islamic history, fearlessly said, "I don't like the word that the companions did not dispute. If they did not dispute, no issue would be issued." he says. The Caliph Omar would take a decision and address the society to announce his decision; but when he encounters a contradictory opposition, he immediately steps back and condemns himself harshly, saying to people by meaning himself, "You don't know your religion as much as a woman." and even stepped back. Caliph Omar, when asked the questions of his own advisory committee, they said "you know better," he fired from his presence and condemned as a jerk.

The person who responds to goodness does not see and follow his relatives. The real visit is that one sees and follows those who cut their interests.

Words of Muhammad from Bukhari

And I swear by the reproaching soul.

Quran 75:2

So do not claim yourselves to be pure.

Quran 53:32

A wise man speaking strong words to a listening ear is like a piece of gold for the ear and a beautiful object of fine gold. A faithful man who carries news is like the cold of snow at gathering time to those who send him, for he makes the spirit of his owners feel new again.

Proverbs of King Solomon 25:12-13

These verses and hadith is one of the most important dynamics that keep the troops alive despite all the disagreements. If the implementation results of decisions taken not only as individuals but also as states or unions are not good, the error is not persisted, account is given if necessary and the price is paid or apologized.

And hold firmly to the rope of Allah all together and do not become divided.

Quran 3:103

In summary, even if the order is like this, we must determine the dynamics of unity well and determine strategies that will keep us as one despite all our differences.

And if it were not that the people would become one community [of disbelievers], We would have made for those who disbelieve in the Most Merciful - for their houses - ceilings and stairways of silver upon which to mount.

Quran 43:33

This verse is a good example of the dangers of unity and the danger of people turning into a single nation by unanimously influencing each other in consensus. The following hadiths and verses may be added.

What I fear most about my ummah is the leaders who lead them to the branch.

Words of Muhammad from Abu David

There are three things that I fear about my nation in these respects: the belief that it will rain when the stars enter some signs, sultan's cruelty and deny fate.

Words of Muhammad from Musnad

So would you perhaps, if you turned away, cause corruption on earth and sever your [ties of] relationship? Those [who do so] are the ones that Allah has cursed, so He deafened them and blinded their vision.

Quran 47:22-23

Cultural Administrative Adaptations

Some other laws on management, which work on the basis of matchless cultural principles, are supportive and meaningful, should also be derived. These laws are also derived from the name of governing the society and religion, language, campus and economic order that govern our lives, such as some adjustments made to some phenomena such as security and order.

Article 10: Organic laws

The state recognizes the state organs independently depending on the constitution. The state develops and applies organic laws in state organs. The form of theoretical work, the rights and responsibilities of responsible people are determined by organic laws separately in state institutions. Unconstitutional measures cannot be taken.

10.1 General shape

He said, "Our Lord is He who gave each thing its form and then guided [it]."

Quran 20:50

This kingdom constitution is a state constitution. These laws are laws that are not appropriate to be changed continuously, require the majority of the votes of the people, does not comply with the principles of consultations continuous discussion, and will constitute an offense since they will be engaged in abuses. These laws are the most basic and general legal principles as well as the sum of the functions that the state operates through. Some laws that are meaningful and supportive by these laws are developed and implemented independently in state organs only for methodological reasons, as organic laws are often subject to change and development as special legal principles. Since organic laws consist of state and state organs, they belong to state organs. We must remember that our duty is to be morally moral with God and act as in the above verse and concentrate on the concept of autonomy and recognize and develop all state institutions, even though they are interrelated.

10.2 Some limits

Indeed, Allah commands you to render trusts to whom they are due and when you judge between people to judge with justice.

Quran 4:58

Education in cultural state structures should and should be carried out in hand-to-hand form, even after all available informational education in schools; but it should not be forgotten that our line is neither the line of the Pharaohs nor the Snowmen. As can be seen from the above verse, our duties are a trust and we must sit with our asses' side.

Apart from this, autonomous state institutions do not mean that they cannot be tried like any other person or institution; however, work is given to the competent person or group and is not disturbed. In order to save time and labor and achieve faster results, the control mechanism must have such flexibility and an appropriate balance mechanism must be developed.

Article 11: Official language

The language of speech and worship is the officially announced language. The only language that must be learned is the official language. There is no coercion in the language of worship. The state language must be protected and developed by the state. The State shall take the necessary measures for this.

11.1 Speaking language

Who taught by the pen - Taught man that which he knew not.

Quran 96:4-5

Since states are social institutions, of course there must be a common language in order to reach agreement and communication in every field. This language is taken into account by God when it is used for believing people. If God has taught it to you, you will certainly be reckoned with how you use language as a people or protect it as a state.

For states with minorities of different nationalities, it is imperative to preserve their language. If the nation as a minority does not have its own territory in the world, autonomy must be given or released. Otherwise, an imperial error incompatible with religious culture is made and they lose all their cultures along with their language, these differences are the verses that God must protect.

And of His signs is the creation of the heavens and the earth and the diversity of your languages and your colors. Indeed in that are signs for those of knowledge.

Quran 30:22

If these minorities have their own states, then proceed with a single language; because it is in their hands to live or not to live in their own land. If they remain indefinitely in a foreign nation that is not of their own religion, they shall be deemed to be forbidden, except in special cases. If they remain indefinitely in nations of their own religion, they are counted among them, which is not forbidden; but he cannot complain about losing his culture.

11.2 Language of worship

And if We had made it a non-Arabic Qur'an, they would have said, "Why are its verses not explained in detail [in our language]? Is it a foreign [recitation] and an Arab [messenger]?" Say, "It is, for those who believe, a guidance and cure." And those who do not believe - in their ears is deafness, and it is upon them blindness. Those are being called from a distant place.

Quran 41:44

As it is said in the verse, the books are guidance and healing for believers. Even though its magic is impeccable, it is not in the language, but in the truths it contains. There was no problem with language and could be sent verses in any language; but naturally it should descend with the language of the prophet's people so that the communiqué can begin.

And We will surely cause you to dwell in the land after them. That is for he who fears My position and fears My threat.

Quran 14:14

Indeed, We have sent it down as an Arabic Qur'an that you might understand.

Quran 12:2

Although all this brings freedom in the language of worship, it can also be worshiped in the language of the prophet because of respect for the prophet in the story and must be learned later as a maturity. The worship of the state in the official colloquial language will prevent ignorance and educate religious scholars, considering that the worship is performed every day. It's enough to steal people's ears. Allah has not imposed an obligation to learn languages.

Indeed, Allah does not wrong the people at all, but it is the people who are wronging themselves.

Quran 10:44

We have not sent down to you Quran that you be distressed.

Quran 20:2

Article 12: Official Religion

Quran 24:22

The religion of the state is Islam. The state does not accept sects. The state recognizes, protects and develops sects.

Allah does not charge a soul except [with that within] its capacity.

Quran 2:286

From everyone who has been given much, much will be demanded; and from the one who has been entrusted with much, much more will be asked.

Luke 12:48

12.1 Religion concept

Indeed, the religion in the sight of Allah is Islam.

Quran 3:19

We have certainly sent down to you a Book in which is your mention. Then will you not reason?

Quran 21:10

Due to the discipline and service institutions of the states, the important issues such as religion, which is the most sensitive point of the people, should be taken under protection by the state and statesmen.

Religion, as mentioned above, is not something to be avoided. It is the sum of all rules formed in the social field and is cultural. However, the Islamic religion, which is one of the Abrahamic religions, aims to establish an Islamic civilization that tolerates all other cultures as a simplified Abrahamism, not a simple culture that is difficult and conservative in terms of its concept.

Islam is not an ideal religion either. It is a relatively simple and optimal religion compared to other religions.

And Allah wants to lighten for you [your difficulties]; and mankind was created weak.

Quran 4:28

This verse is a good example. One of the main reasons for this is the prophet.

There has certainly come to you a Messenger from among yourselves. Grievous to him is what you suffer; [he is] concerned over you and to the believers is kind and merciful.

Quran 9:128

God says I am as my servant knows me. God is ashamed of his prophet, and because of his devotion to the ummah and duty of his prophet, he gives people less than the punishment they deserve or makes it easier for them. People are also like that. Some people always hold on to life thanks to others.

Another reason is that Islam is a global religion. Orders can be naturally different in different cultures; because when a nation grows its people more quality and durable and never accepts the rest, very high quality people grow in time and this becomes a habit for the nation. The orders are not heavy for them. Another nation does not care about any of the issues of learning, implementation and development, and if it only spends time, of course, that nation is weakened and the next generation is weak. Thus, religious orders are also easy.

But once they are sheltered in marriage, if they should commit adultery, then for these slave wife is half the punishment for free [unmarried] women.

Quran 4:25

And let not those of virtue among you and wealth swear not to give [aid] to their relatives and the needy and the emigrants for the cause of Allah, and let them pardon and overlook. Would you not like that Allah should forgive you? And Allah is Forgiving and Merciful.

These verses are good examples. Therefore, even if Islam is applied individually, both as a state and as a state, there is still something that we will be responsible for; because it does not mean that we will not be taken into account because God did not command it hard. The reason for not ordering difficult is the problem of failure of those who can not.

O you who have believed, fear Allah as He should be feared and do not die except as Muslims [in submission to Him].

Quran 3:102

A servant cannot rise to the rank of mutants, unless he is away from the ranks when he is not inconvenient wherever you want, for fear of sin.

Words of Muhammad from ibn Majah

These verses and hadith are good examples of this. In short, if a nation comes to religion, the religion of Atlantis, and the religion and orders of an African country cannot be the same. Possibly a great prophet such as like Idris or maybe King Tooth in Atlantis, the commandments may be Utopian in nations sent by nation religion, and the death penalty is much higher; but God can show them miracles so that they can never be alienated, or they will have a long life or increase their knowledge. In such nations, religious practice and punishments are very strict; because the threat is to destroy them collectively.

Have they not seen how many generations We destroyed before them which We had established upon the earth as We have not established you? And We sent [rain from] the sky upon them in showers and made rivers flow beneath them; then We destroyed them for their sins and brought forth after them a generation of others.

Quran 6:6

For the Islamic religion, the destruction all together has been abolished.

I have asked three things of my Lord; He gave me two of what I wanted, and one of those who denied me: I asked my Lord not to perish my nation with famine; promised to fulfill my request. I also asked him not to perish my nation by drowning in water, and promised to fulfill my wish. Then I asked my nation not to fight among themselves and let them fight, and he denied it to me.

Words of Muhammad from Muslim

This hadith is considered evidence; however, there will be partial penalties such as sinking or surrogate.

When the benefit of certain circles of state property is made, when the safety of bargaining and alms is considered chore, when science is charged for other purposes, when the person obeys his wife and rebels to his mother, and when father is away from friend, the noise in the mosques, and when the vile man is the leader of the nation, when he is offered to the

man for fear of evil, when the female singers and instruments reproduced, drinking wine and when those who came at the end of the ummah cursed those who came before; then let them follow successive signs, such as a red wind, earthquakes, sinking to the ground, deformation in face shape, stoning like the succession of the grains of a rope-breaking necklace.

Words of Muhammad from Tirmidhi

12.2 Sufism

Indeed, this is a reminder, so whoever wills may take to his Lord a way.

Quran 73:19

And it is not for any human being that Allah should speak to him except by revelation or from behind a partition or that He sends a messenger to reveal, by His permission, what He wills. Indeed, He is Most High and Wise.

Quran 42:51

One of the reasons why Islam is so easy is that it is a global religion as mentioned above; because in this case all possible quality will give people gold orders. The word gold here means golden ratio. If you are told to draw a triangle or rectangle, one side is too short and the other side is not too long. Usually people draw according to the golden ratio. In this respect, Islam is not an ideal but a golden religion; but it also addresses idealistic people who need to experience with God, like prophets, and as a necessity, someone must surely live like a prophet in a pure sacrifice without any right to the Islamic line. He has to assume the responsibility of others, such as Moses, who is an occasion to reach God, and become an intercessor.

And Moses chose from his people seventy men for Our appointment. And when the earthquake seized them, he said, "My Lord, if You had willed, You could have destroyed them before and me [as well]. Would You destroy us for what the foolish among us have done? This is not but Your trial by which You send astray whom You will and guide whom You will. You are our Protector, so forgive us and have mercy upon us; and You are the best of forgivers.

Quran 7:155

This verse is a good example of this situation. God does not do anything without mediation because of His greatness. This is not because he needs it; but his wish is to create and manage man, there are many curtains, many things as a cause, or people become obedient, far from being asserted. This is the law of Allah and it is just like creating a human in need and trusting baby for his parents.

And it is not for any human being that Allah should speak to him except by revelation or from behind a partition or that He sends a messenger to reveal, by His permission, what He wills. Indeed, He is Most High and Wise.

Quran 42:51

The duty of the people who are close to God is the same, that is to say that Moses is the intermediary in prayer.

And know that among you is the Messenger of Allah.

Quran 49:7

Scholars are the heirs of the prophets.

Words of Muhammad from Bukhari

This verse and hadith, this is a good evidence. It is forbidden to remember the death of Muhammad. It is necessary to seek Him by Sufism.

Certainly, at the beginning of each century, Allah will send a mujaddid to the ummah to renew his religious works.

Words of Muhammad from Abu David

The death or abuse of these idealist people is, according to Muhammad, a breach of Islam.

The death of the scholar is a breach opened in Islam.

Words of Muhammad from Darimi

When those who come in the last time of this ummah disparage their previous scholars, they conceal the Quran which Allah revealed.

Words of Muhammad from ibn Majah

It is these esoteric institutions that educate the idealist, our sects and education in which Muhammad himself is located. This esoterism is not like the Kabbalists of the Israelites. According to the Quran, Muhammad also states each verse has an apparent and a hidden meaning; It does not contain unlawful orders, as in the case of the deviated from the Israelites. The fact that sects are esoteric is due to the abundance of information. The question of where should I begin is a pre-compiled ready-to-read answer to both the divine experience and the theoretical setting, and the fact that it is a religious necessity for man. It's a school, and it's on the way to the people's network, showing people the short way.

The status of scholars on earth is similar to the stars in the sky, which look at it on land and sea at dark nights. It is only a matter of time before the stars get dark.

Words of Muhammad from Suyuti

There are people like that that are the key to good, and evil is the locks. There are also the keys of evil, are the locks of good. Good news to those whom Allah has given the key to goodwill. Shame on those who gave the keys of evil.

Words of Muhammad from ibn Majah

These hadiths also refer to religious congregations from Sufism; because their leaders live only in the moment, that is, they are always in control and awake. So they make a difference to other people in terms of both learning and teaching and become guides for people.

So ask the people of the message if you do not know.

Quran 16:43

The thing to be aware of is the false scholars; because, of course, as in every field, false teachers will emerge in the field of sects. It is not surprising that even the false prophets appeared, and Muhammad has informed us that these will happen.

They have taken their scholars and monks as lords besides Allah, and [also] the Messiah, the son of Mary.

Quran 9:31

This verse is sent for those who deviate from Christians and Jews. One of the old Christians said that there was no worship when Muhammad came down to this verse, and Muhammad said, "If Allah makes forbidden that He has forbidden, then you would have accepted it as halal. That is worship." He said. Again, real scholars and sects are the way to protect them.

Those who live after me will witness many differences. I recommend my circumcision, the circumcision of the caliphs guided, who have found the right path. Hold him firmly, hold him with your teeth, avoid anything that comes out. Because every fitting foreign custom, every foreign custom is perversion.

Words of Muhammad from Abu David

This hadith is a good example. The way to get rid of heresy is to do the same as the prophet and the people who follow the path of the prophets; because it has been thought many times in our name and is a blessing.

Jesus answered, "I am the way and the truth and the life. No one comes to the Father except through me. If you really know me, you will know my Father as well. From now on, you do know him and have seen him." Philip said, "Lord, show us the Father and that will be enough for us." Jesus answered: "Don't you know me, Philip, even after I have been among you such a long time? Anyone who has seen me has seen the Father. How can you say, Show us the Father? Don't you believe that I am in the Father, and that the Father is in me? The words I say to you I do not speak on my own authority. Rather, it is the Father, living in me, who is doing his work. Believe me when I say that I am in the Father and the Father is in me; or at least believe on the evidence of the works themselves. Very truly I tell you, whoever believes in me will do the works I have been doing, and they will do even greater things than these, because I am going to the Father. And I will do whatever you ask in my name, so that the Father may be glorified in the Son. You may ask me for anything in my name, and I will do it.

John 14:6-14

Enmity towards them is the same as the enmity of God, and the worship they call salvation is of no use; because there is nothing to confront people with real scholars. They have no condemnation and you're probably wrong. Even if you do not know, you will suffer damage; because most people do not pay attention to things such as asking for morality and virtue, investigating and the possibility of being wrong. Most move with suspicion. In this case they become guilty; because if he plays a move with the suspicion and otherwise, you are responsible. When a person accidentally touches an electrical wire, electricity can kill it and nobody blames it.

Allah said: "Whoever is hostile to my servant, I declare warfare upon. Among the things that bring my servant closer to me is the things I make him obliged to. My servant continues to approach me with vain prayers, and my love for him ends. When I love him, I become the ear that he hears, the eye he sees, the hand he holds, the foot he walks on. When he asks me for asylum, I take him under protection. In one thing that I will do, I have not hesitated as much as I hesitate in accepting the soul of my believer: he does not love death, and I do not love what he does not.

Words of Muhammad from Bukhari

This hadith is a good example of this. Enmity towards them is enmity to God.

And of the people is he who disputes about Allah without knowledge or guidance or an enlightening book [from Him],

Quran 22:8

This verse is a good example of those ignorant. The guide here is also the scholars. If you fight without these conditions, you will be harmful.

The order of the sects is jihad. This does not mean jihad with the army. Even a smiling face is considered jihad.

And let not those of virtue among you and wealth swear not to give [aid] to their relatives and the needy and the emigrants for the cause of Allah, and let them pardon and overlook. Would you not like that Allah should forgive you? And Allah is Forgiving and Merciful.

Quran 24:22

This verse also means that the emigration will continue and therefore the memory of the work of the prophets is not a religious obligation for everyone, but that one should do it as a religious obligation because of the status of Islam, a global religion. Helping them is also encouraged by God and encouraged for virtue owners. Not everyone is obliged to.

This religion will always stand. A community of Muslims will never stop fighting for this religion until the apocalypse breaks.

Words of Muhammad from Musnad

This hadith is a good example for this and points to the sects. Sects are an occasion to reach God.

O you who have believed, fear Allah and seek the means [of nearness] to Him and strive in His cause that you may succeed.

Quran 5:35

The teachings are made hand-to-hand and with a reference as non-alternative in religion as mentioned above, whether it is the Papal or Naqshbandi.

Muhammad is not but a messenger. [Other] messengers have passed on before him. So if he was to die or be killed, would you turn back on your heels [to unbelief]? And he who turns back on his heels will never harm Allah at all; but Allah will reward the grateful.

Quran 3:144

And know that among you is the Messenger of Allah .

Quran 49:7

Ask smart people to show the right path so that you can find the right path. You will regret not opposing them.

Words of Muhammad from Baghdadi

Religion does not consult every person and it is not appropriate to be consulted. This is the case of the Papacy, and it has already been.

Jesus said to them, "The kings of the Gentiles lord it over them; and those who exercise authority over them call themselves Benefactors. But you are not to be like that. Instead, the greatest among you should be like the youngest, and the one who rules like the one who serves."

Luke 22:25-26

Jesus, like Muhammad's choice of Abu Bakr, chose Peter to prophesy and teach the prophethood, not the kingdom, for the prophethood.

Peter was hurt because Jesus asked him the third time, "Do you love me?" He said, "Lord, you know all things; you know that I love you." Jesus said, "Feed my sheep."

John 21:17

Follow those two after me! Abu Bakr and Omar.

Words of Muhammad from Tirmidhi

But I have prayed for you, Simon, that your faith may not fail. And when you have turned back, strengthen your brothers.

Luke 22:32

I poured into the chest of Abu Bakr everything that God poured into my chest.

Words of Muhammad from Acluni

And I tell you that you are Peter, and on this rock I will build my church, and the gates of Hades will not overcome it. I will give you the keys of the kingdom of heaven; whatever you bind on earth will be bound in heaven, and whatever you loose on earth will be loosed in heaven.

Matthew 16:18-19

Muhammad, "Abu Bakr and Omar. If you two alliance in a consultation I do not oppose you." said.

Words of Muhammad from Musnad

Close all of the gates in this Masjid besides Abu Bakr's gates!

Words fo Muhammad from Bukhari

Both Jesus and Muhammad treated their closest and superior disciples alike. Even today, all Sufism accept Abu Bakr as the spiritual leader, and Christians accept Peter as the leader.

There is, however, that both the pope and the caliphate are political leadership in the most obvious sense; but conditioned. Neither the republic, nor the kingdom, nor any other government. He is a prophetic profession.

Caliph Omar expressed his concern and asked Salman: "Am I a king or a caliph?" Salman answered him; "If you take more or less money from the land of the Muslims and then make it unjustly, you are not a caliph, you are a melika.

Words of Muhammad from Tabari

Other conditions are described in more verses below, and they are fair officials who give fair judgments to every soulless Muslim country "bought" into the language of the Bible and the Quran.

Is thirty years the caliphate on prophethood after me.

Words of Muhammad from Abu David

This hadith refers to the caliphate to Muhammad's prophets after Muhammad, that is to say his own disciples, who then say that biting sultans will come. This is not appropriate. On the one hand he knew that this would be inevitable and would otherwise perish in an otherwise divine commandment, and on the other hand, he established a holy Prophet's Quarters called Ashab al-Suffah to be raised only as religious advisers and statesmen, but not as rulers. The future left to the Mahdi. Their masters, teachers and owners is Abu Bakr. Those who are the most capable Salman or Abu Ubeyda such as, that for example, for Salman, Khalif Ali says "Salman was given the science of previous and subsequent. This science can not be reached." or even if he is Iranian, "He is from family of Muhammad. His position among us is like Luqman. He read the first and last book. It is an endless sea." He said. Also Muhammad "Salman is saturated with science." He said. Abu Bakr also said about the following.

There is no one among me who has goodness and bestowings on me, rather than Abu Bakr bin Abu Kuhafe, with self-esteem and possessions. If I had obtained a state from the people, I would have obtained Abu Bakr to myself. However, the friendship and brotherhood of Islam is superior. Close all the gates of this Masjid besides Abu Bakr's door!

Words of Muhammad from Bukhari

They were meant not only to learn Quran, but to live like a prophet, and it could also be called as ordeal companions, who had aimed to educate themselves appropriately. If their numbers changed, their purpose sometimes deviated and not valid for all, their preoccupation was their religion and their needs were met by the public. They would listen and learn from Muhammad. This is the reason why Abu Hurairah narrated so many hadiths, He said, "Do not be surprised my narration of hadith much. Because Muhacir brothers in the bazaar and market trade, while the Ansar brothers engaged in the fields and gardens, I memorized the blessed advice of Muhammad." He said.

He cared so much that when Fatima the daughter who Muhammad called one of the eldest of the women of Paradise, asked her father Muhammad for a servant, Muhammad said "My daughter! What are you saying? I haven't been able to get the people of Suffah yet." and rejected her request. The sects today try to live and keep the Quran and the Sunnah traditionally taught by the teachers and students of this holy hearth. Although this is not suitable for the caliphate phenomenon in the public sense today, the caliphs have to emerge from these people. As can be seen from the above hadith, the father of this way is Abu Bakr.

Today, the situation will change.

The prophethood continues in you as long as Allah wills; then he removes it at any time. Then there will be a caliphate in the prophetic system. This will continue as long as Allah wills; then Allah will destroy it when He wills. Then the nipping reign occurs. It will continue as long as He wills. then Allah destroys it when He wills. Then it becomes a cruel reign; it will continue as long as Allah wills, then Allah will eliminate it whenever He wills. Then there is a caliphate in the prophetic system.

Words of Muhammad from Musnad**12.3 Religious sects**

Indeed, those who have divided their religion and become sects - you, [O Muhammad], are not [associated] with them in anything. Their affair is only [left] to Allah ; then He will inform them about what they used to do.

Quran 6:159

12.3.1 General shape

There is no other way to convey information to the future than to narrate. People say that they have heard from their prophets and the narrations of respected people are accepted. This may cause different case-law; but it also does not require a separate religious formation. People can use any different information that is considered to be correct, either continuously or alternatively. It does not mean that what is common does not mean absolute right, nor does it mean that less commonly used is absolutely wrong.

The sect scholars who gather rumors and try to mold the social rules as a result of various consultations in order to preserve the information and the social order are not infallible; but it is not possible to have an alternative if it is thought to be started from the beginning. Usually it is only up to us to accept them, as they

think from every angle imaginable and make the necessary analyzes and adaptations with all their knowledge base. In this case there is still obedience as a religious commandment due to the order of obedience to the leaders; but it is not compulsory as a matter of fact except for individual disintegration; because none of the sect scholars were heralded. Neither Quran nor the prophet gave orders to obey their future. Even if they can be killed in individual separations, they are allowed instead. Criminal sanctions may be applied instead.

It is not permissible to shed the blood of a Muslim except those three things; adulterer married, people who knowingly kill people unjustly and people who left religion.

Words of Muhammad from Bukhari

12.3.2 Sunni and Shia

Help your brother even is cruel or oppressed. One man: What? If my brother is oppressed, let me help him. But if he's cruel, can you tell me how to help him? said. Our Prophet said: "You will keep him from persecution and prevent him from persecution. Surely this is to help him."

Words of Muhammad from Bukhari

Three things are the basis of faith. The first is that we do not hesitate to tease anyone who says, "There is no god other than Allah." In other words, if there is an act that does not comply with Islam, it is not to declare it non-Islam. Secondly, Jihad with sword continues until the moment when Allah will fight the Dajjal from the moment he sends me as a prophet. Just as the justice of the justice cannot lift him away, the cruelty of the cruel cannot bear it. The third is to believe in Fate.

Words of Muhammad from Abu David

Sunni and Shia should seek ways to live together and agree. In my opinion, the real problem stems from Shia; because everyone except Khalifa Ali says something especially about this dispute; because he knows that the superiority of Abu Bakr, including Ali, is fixed by verses.

And the first forerunners [in the faith] among the Muhajireen and the Ansar and those who followed them with good conduct - Allah is pleased with them and they are pleased with Him, and He has prepared for them gardens beneath which rivers flow, wherein they will abide forever. That is the great attainment.

Quran 9:100

This is the most pioneer of the first pioneers of Muhajirs mentioned here, the greatest faithful, Abu Bakr. When Abu Bakr became a Muslim, Ali was only 9 years old and was not a taxpayer. Ali saw Muhammad praying and asked what he was doing. Muhammad explained the situation and told him to be Muslim. Ali wanted to consult with his family, but he hesitated and said, "Did God ask my parents when he created me?" He was still a child. He therefore said that he was the greatest faithful; but Muhammad said that he was Abu Bakr, that actually becoming first is not only reason to be the greatest one.

If you do not aid the Prophet - Allah has already aided him when those who disbelieved had driven him out [of Makkah] as one of two, when they were in the cave and he said to his companion, "Do not grieve; indeed Allah is with us." And Allah sent down his tranquillity upon him and supported him with angels you did not see and made the word of

those who disbelieved the lowest, while the word of Allah - that is the highest. And Allah is Exalted in Might and Wise.

Quran 9:40

In this way, the only person directly mentioned in the Quran is Abu Bekr.

The event called Ghadir Khumm is also an inclination to misunderstand.

Whoever I am owner of, Ali is also the owner.

Words of Muhammad from Tirmidhi

Muhammad said this about Ali; but if I did not know Omar congratulated Ali by saying "You have become the owner of all Muslims.", I would say that "Muhammad left a new head of the household." that mothers already, while the father of the house is not at home, say to the boys like "you're our father". Already Muhammad said to Ali, "Your divorce of Aisha, let me be my divorce." He said that this is because of Ali's closeness. When Ali was angry with Aisha he said this, that Aisha had behaved poorly against Muhammad meanwhile.

Ownership, if not so, is not always leadership. Mahdi is the owner of Jesus; but He is His servant. All this is not evidence for Ali's absolute superiority. Because Ali is the gateway to knowledge and he is at the forefront of heroic works, he is a true owner. He is indeed a person who can be the owner and assistant of all Muslims above or below himself. Shia makes this an absolute advantage, which is wrong. They are partly right; because all caliphs are equivalent in one place and can easily assume each other's duties. For these reasons, the true fiction should be like "Ali is superior for the following reason and Abu Bakr is superior for the following reason, but this is the real superiority."

Muhammad said during this event that Ali is going to be the caliph after him; but the companion chose Abu Bakr to the caliph, who all knew that Abu Bakr was the greatest authority after Muhammad, according to Muhammad. This promotion does not mean right after. This is Ali's introduction, since is publicity. In any case, Ali has not said anything otherwise about it.

In any case, Sunni and Shia have no right to regard each other as heretics; because there is no intent but there is neglect and misunderstanding. Allah did not send the book in one piece and say, "Take this book and punish everyone.". There is a reference in this regard, and this reference is extremely low in some people.

So would you perhaps, if you turned away, cause corruption on earth and sever your [ties of] relationship?

Quran 47:22

But none is granted it except those who are patient, and none is granted it except one having a great portion [of good]. And if there comes to you from Satan an evil suggestion, then seek refuge in Allah. Indeed, He is the Hearing, the Knowing.

Quran 41:35-36

If the whirling dervish and the people of the earth all participate in shedding the blood of a believer, Allah will drive them all to the prickly hell to protect the rights of the only innocent believer whose blood is shed!

Words of Muhammad from Tirmidhi

Muslims must follow the path of Islam. These warnings and cautions are compelling even for the most muslim Muslims in determining the reference, and should make us think many times and step back, just like the punishment for adultery.

Muslims will return to the infidels who hit each other's neck because of the adherence of Dejjals.

Words of Muhammad from Bukhari

If this does not discourage, most of the Muslims living now are infidels; because they do not know that the Mahdi, who is heralded in all the holy books, is a helper prophet and they call it a great guardian. Some say he is not as superior as the savage who killed Hamzah. He is a helper prophet, as I have explained above and below.

In short, Ali is the father of all religious people; but Abu Bakr is considered his teacher. In fact, this is like an honorary president. Their work is a bit like this; because they have different advantages over each other. Muhammad, for example, "Ali is the best judge." and Omar says, "I take refuge in Allah from ruling where Ali is not." He says; but again, for example, Muhammad, "Omar is the best practice of religion." he says.

Shia sources of information are underestimated that they sometimes add their own interpretation according to the basic principles of Ahl al-Bayt. This is a traditional method and we cannot say wrong.

Three things are the basis of faith. The first is that we do not hesitate to tease anyone who says, "There is no god other than Allah." In other words, if there is an act that does not comply with Islam, it is not to declare it non-Islam. Secondly, Jihad with sword continues until the moment when Allah will fight the Dajjal from the moment he sends me as a prophet. Just as the justice of the justice cannot lift him away, the cruelty of the cruel cannot bear it. The third is to believe in Fate.

Words of Muhammad from Abu David

And this worldly life is not but diversion and amusement. And indeed, the home of the Hereafter - that is the [eternal] life, if only they knew.

Quran 29:64

Article 13: Colonial Order and State System

The state uses 4 main settlements as the North, South, East and West States. Settlements in the states are provided by colonies surrounded by walls with gates of North, South, East and West. There is no village, town or district. Governors are responsible for the states. There is a presidential system in the colonies. Secular and religious are obliged to establish their own colonies. Moving between colonies is only possible by interview and according to the form in organic laws. It is the main economic potential in forming colonies. The state necessarily transfers people between the colonies when it deems necessary.

13.1 General shape of colonies

So race to [all that is] good. Wherever you may be, Allah will bring you all together.

Quran 2:148

In order to provide occupational health in accordance with the hierarchical order, the settlements should be divided into the simplest and most efficient parts together with the people. A picture is perfect if you're working hard on all pixels and have enough pixels.

Although all the actions that can be carried out on behalf of the state are carried out according to the fundamental functions that are basically determined, the main thing that carries out the works is job tracking. The quality of all actions from economy to education is highly dependent on the business conductor. All

of this work requires good management, planning and control. In this case, due to the social and cultural hierarchical state structure, we must break down the population as small as possible and find more leaders with a more powerful hierarchical order to easily cope with all activities from finding workers to marriage, opening university departments and mediation.

For security and service, colonies have also a great importance. The absence of settlements other than colonies means that all services that the state is obliged to provide will be provided or developed only in certain regions for all hikes. This means saving both time and, therefore, money and labor. Security will always be at the highest level, as there is always control at the entrances and exits in the colonies surrounded by walls. First security, then movement. The walls will be as high as the apartment, and there will be a road or paths that can be used for racing or driving courses. There will be patrols and cameras on the walls.

O you who have believed, persevere and endure and remain stationed and fear Allah that you may be successful.

Quran 3:200

It is also socially important. The issue of what should be the minimum and maximum population that people can express themselves is an issue that has been discussed since ancient times and is important. As with a shirt, a car or any other item, buildings or cities are the same as before, and if necessary, cities that we will entrust our present and tomorrow will be redesigned.

13.1.1 Ponds

Each colony without exception should contain extremely large ponds. These ponds should be supported by a water network carrying water from the sea to each colony. Since the engines I mentioned below are very powerful and already have a thrust motor and can provide higher torque when the radius is arranged around a large circle, water can be transported even on steepest slopes in the shortest way. The amount of water should always be adjustable with water from the sea. This water is converted into drinking water by treatment plants and methods installed next to the ponds and treated by the methods described in the technology section below.

Since these ponds will be filled with salt water, they will be suitable for living creatures living in sea water, which means that fishing is also possible. However, living things like dolphins or whales can also be grown in suitable climates.

These ponds can also be used as holiday lands. Both floating small buildings and facilities to be established on the coast can be made available to the public.

13.1.2 Underground Tunnels

Colonies must also have underground tunnels. These tunnels should be accessible by truck or car. Tunnels should also have cheap air-conditioning devices for colonial climate, gigantic and possibly glass drinking water lines and sewer lines that use the simple methods I have discussed below, which heat or cool the entire colony because energy is not a problem.

13.2 Criminal colonies

Criminals can't find a place to escape in the colonial system. However, they can live alone in the mountains so that they will always have patrols and will have to get help from the colonies. Moreover, it is not difficult to prevent them from escaping. They can always be controlled from a screen with a solid wrist to be worn on their arms. Criminal colonies, even if they are big cities, can roam completely free; but they can't go anywhere else. The doors of these colonies are not always open as in other colonies, and security is at the highest level.

Criminals lose their liberty if they do not require death penalty, they are sent to these colonies and they are employed as workers. Their work returns as a criminal discount. All kinds of factories can be established and all kinds of jobs can be taught to them.

I, the LORD, have called you in righteousness; I will take hold of your hand. I will keep you and will make you to be a covenant for the people and a light for the Gentiles, to open eyes that are blind, to free captives from prison and to release from the dungeon those who sit in darkness. I am the LORD; that is my name! I will not yield my glory to another or my praise to idols.

Isaiah 42:6-8

The person mentioned in these verses is the Mahdi, the king of all nations, and some of his actions are seen by Allah's command. In other religions, prison visits are encouraged; because in fact you can find neither rapists nor rigid disruptors. So is Islam. A person is either beaten or killed or crippled and imprisoned. However, there are arrests at some gray points, which are also worthy of compassion. Therefore, it would be more appropriate to use them more freely in the works that will benefit humanity.

13.3 Ideological distinction

There shall be no compulsion in [acceptance of] the religion.

Quran 2:256

As the verse says, there is no compulsion in religion. This is only so if you do not face any coercion when you want to experience all religious conditions, from the economy to the state administration, from education to social relations. All prophets and believers in Him are therefore innocent. They demand their rights according to the command and otherwise they will fight and enslave with you. There is no such thing as half or a quarter of religion. If religion is not practiced publicly, it is a place of war; for the implementation of all possible religious orders for minorities in states of different religions depends on the governors there.

Fight them until there is no [more] fitnah and [until] worship is [acknowledged to be] for Allah . But if they cease, then there is to be no aggression except against the oppressors.

Quran 2:193

However, it is withdrawn when necessary and does not interfere.

Not upon the Messenger is [responsibility] except [for] notification. And Allah knows whatever you reveal and whatever you conceal.

Quran 5:99

Jesus replied, "Anyone who loves me will obey my teaching. My Father will love them, and we will come to them and make our home with them. Anyone who does not love me will not obey my teaching. These words you hear are not my own; they belong to the Father who sent me."

John 14:23-24

These verses are good examples. The fact that God interferes with the work of the prophets is similar to the defense of oppressed people, regardless of the religion or race encouraged by God, and is indeed a universal stance for humans. God has all rights reserved. When he wants to establish order or when his order is broken, the duty of the believers is to struggle and the opposite one requires punishment.

Say, [O Muhammad], "If your fathers, your sons, your brothers, your wives, your relatives, wealth which you have obtained, commerce wherein you fear decline, and dwellings with which you are pleased are more beloved to you than Allah and His Messenger and jihad in His cause, then wait until Allah executes His command. And Allah does not guide the defiantly disobedient people."

Quran 9:24

I swear to Allah, who is in my soul, that you command the good and forbid the evil! Or Allah will send a punishment from His own land, and then you pray to Allah to remove that punishment, and you will not be respected.

Words of Muhammad from Musnad

This verse and hadith is a good example. In this case, the people who come from us, who are actually keen on the world, who have made up the elements of make-up as religion, who are prone to the yoke and who do not allow, will also come out.

And of the people is he whose speech pleases you in worldly life, and he calls Allah to witness as to what is in his heart, yet he is the fiercest of opponents.

Quran 2:204

This verse is a good example. Under these circumstances, different opinions should be respected; but should not be allowed to be persecuted.

As for he who thinks himself without need, To him you give attention. And not upon you [is any blame] if he will not be purified. But as for he who came to you striving [for knowledge]. While he fears [Allah], From him you are distracted. No! Indeed, these verses are a reminder; So whoever wills may remember it.

Quran 80:5-12

This verse is a good example. The colony system is a system that can prevent all of these situations for all times. In fact, according to religious law, it is the only way to gain my bloodless rights, which, if necessary, must be defended with blood. Otherwise, winning bloodless means renouncing your right, accepting the cruel yoke and losing your honor. Everything is in balance.

O you who have believed, do not take your fathers or your brothers as allies if they have preferred disbelief over belief. And whoever does so among you - then it is those who are the wrongdoers.

Quran 9:23

This verse is a good example of the practical application of religious separation in the colony system. Religion is a real human rights phenomenon. The hostility towards aggressive religious opponents is therefore very severe in all religions. Death penalties, exiles or punishments are applied. Religion recognizes and introduces God and His rules as the founding founder, and teaches us to be a virtuous person with all his rules in social life.

I have come to bring fire on the earth, and how I wish it were already kindled! But I have a baptism to undergo, and what constraint I am under until it is completed! Do you think I came to bring peace on earth? No, I tell you, but division. From now on there will be five in one family divided against each other, three against two and two against three. They will be divided, father against son and son against father, mother against daughter and daughter against mother, mother-in-law against daughter-in-law and daughter-in-law against mother-in-law."

Luke 12:49-53

Do not suppose that I have come to bring peace to the earth. I did not come to bring peace, but a sword. For I have come to turn a man against his father, a daughter against her mother, a daughter-in-law against her mother-in-law— a man's enemies will be the members of his own household. Anyone who loves their father or mother more than me is not worthy of me; anyone who loves their son or daughter more than me is not worthy of me.

Matthew 10:33-37

This is the words of Jesus, which is consistent with the previous verse, and some of the things Jesus will do on his second coming. Again, colonies are absolutely necessary for this application to be performed perfectly. Jesus or anyone else will not do it with angels from heaven. What we have to do is to apply the truths that we accept theoretically and truthfully on the table in the worst case in terms of sacrifice or volunteering. These only happen if we want to. Otherwise, extinction will come.

Indeed, Allah will not change the condition of a people until they change what is in themselves. And when Allah intends for a people ill, there is no repelling it. And there is not for them besides Him any patron.

Quran 13:11**13.4 State order**

Federal systems, when used purely methodologically, ensure work efficiency as required by the hierarchical order. This federalism is not a contractual commitment like that between foreign states. This federal system requires unconditional commitment and, as it is said, is only methodological as an administrative solution.

There will be federal authorities. There will always be federal agents or sanctioners on security intelligence, economic and judicial matters. They are directly attached to the King.

Article 14: Council Order

The highest council is the advisory council of the King. Advisory Council has legislative, executive and judicial authorities. There are state councils in the states, and as representatives of the representatives committee, consists of colonial presidents as Sanjak Lords and their leaders who are as assistant of governors. There are public councils in the colonies and the colonial leader presides as the Sanjak Lord. The delegation of representatives consists of the Sanjak Lord in the colonies, the head of the justice commission, the police chief, the director of national education, the director of religious affairs and the director of finance. The other members are elected by the public. The number of deputies in the public councils is determined by "enough-votes" of preselected deputies and there is no limit. The council can issue any one from the council. The delegation of representatives is responsible to the Sanjak Lord. Gentleman The Lord is the deputy governor and is responsible for the multiple colonies in the states as leaders of Sanjak Lords. The judiciary is executed by the judicial councils. The noblest council is the Noble Council as judicial council.

14.1 Public Councils

And those who have responded to their lord and established prayer and whose affair is [determined by] consultation among themselves, and from what We have provided them, they spend.

Quran 42:38

The Hierarchical and Oligarchic structures have been appointed by the Royal, but the authority to change the delegation of delegators is still popular in the colonies; because the assembly can issue any one. As it is said in the verse, they follow orders; but their work is also in consultation with each other.

The people can derive local laws in the colonies, subject to the basic laws. We take whatever they want into their assemblies and thus increase the likelihood of people going out, which can lead to exemplary actions, both for the other colonies and even for the King and his assembly. The only assembly in the current order is a very wrong and empty distraction. The same should apply to states, so that we can increase the chances of good work. There is no need for unnecessary restraint. When you go out for a walk while raising a dog and pulling the dog left and right, you voluntarily move in that direction.

14.2 State councils

So by mercy from Allah, [O Muhammad], you were lenient with them. And if you had been rude [in speech] and harsh in heart, they would have disbanded from about you. So pardon them and ask forgiveness for them and consult them in the matter. And when you have decided, then rely upon Allah. Indeed, Allah loves those who rely [upon Him].

Quran 3:159

Although the King is the greatest authority, the King does not possess absolute power. God commands the King to consult, just as He commanded His prophet. The governors are the heads of the states as the King's deputies and their work is in consultation.

14.3 Advisory council of the king

She said, "O eminent ones, indeed, to me has been delivered a noble letter."

Quran 27:29

A wise man speaking strong words to a listening ear is like a piece of gold for the ear and a beautiful object of fine gold. A faithful man who carries news is like the cold of snow at gathering time to those who send him, for he makes the spirit of his owners feel new again.

Proverbs of King Solomon 25:12-13

The Advisory Council consists of the nation's nationals and notables. This is a traditional posture without alternatives. They have the right to save on people. New members are selected from both trained and self-educated people. The King has the right to choose them; it does not pose a problem in cultural oligarchic state structures because there is no voting concern, and even the King will be raised and consulted by scholars.

14.4 The Noble council

But I tell you that anyone who is angry with a brother or sister will be subject to judgment. Again, anyone who says to a brother or sister, "Raca," is answerable to the court. And anyone who says, "You fool!" will be in danger of the fire of hell.

Matthew 5:22

Justice is the basis of property.

Khalifa Omar

Property is the state and justice is the most fundamental principle that keeps the state alive. There is chaos where there is no justice. Protecting society from chaos is the duty of justice organs.

Article 15: Voting Order

The state does not recognize party-building. The state shall be based on the majority of votes in all its organs, subject to the constitution. The King has the right to save money. The state recognizes the majority of the people in the referendum on all matters except religion. Votes to elect, elect or expel members may be at any time or frequency.

15.1 General shape

It is not halal for one of the three people to stand in an open field without assigning orders to one of them.

Words of Muhammad from Musnad

If a decision is made, only three basic situations arise. An agreement, a disagreement or a war as a result of disagreement; therefore, this applies to any majority, and, as can be best expressed by the majority of votes, the majority must be fair. It is ensured that there are no even numbers in the assemblies.

Although the state is a kingdom for certain reasons, the people make the real decision when the conditions determined by the constitution and organic laws are matured, since there is no absolute jurisdiction except for the people. Other than that; it does not interfere with the work of a master, doctor, engineer or artisan, nor can it interfere with the duties and powers of statesmen.

15.2 Some limits

The decision is only for Allah. He relates the truth, and He is the best of deciders.

Quran 6:57

As stated above, religion never accepts the existing democratic order. Religion, you can clearly choose that in leadership choices; but he says no, and does not give everyone the right to choose. Some may use slaves as he does not recognize. Apart from these, you or I do not already have the purpose to manage the state. Work is one and will be done together. The debate is prohibited.

The apocalypse will not break unless people brag about each other with the masjids.

Words of Muhammad from Nasai

Party systems cause such an unnecessary action. People unnecessarily enlarge the game, and in time they fade each other, even enmities arise, and even blood sheds. However, everyone should be free to build the city and choose the leader. They can all defend one thing in consultation under one roof.

Article 16: Educational Order

The Royal Academy is the only binding and binding institution of the state. The main education system, except as permitted by the state; It is a semi-boarding education system for primary, secondary and high school. Compulsory education is the same as in organic law. Education is a fundamental birthright for women and men and is free of charge. The compulsory education time for women is lower and as in organic law. The state is obliged to open sports schools. In sports schools, education is provided at primary school level. Entrance exams for primary, secondary, high school or university cannot be made except as allowed by the state. The registration priority for all schools is the current colonies.

16.1 General shape

No mother should be harmed through her child, and no father through his child.

Quran 2:233

This order is a target for statesmen, but it is one of the good examples of the duty of the state on the people. Family is the core community for the state. It is the essence of society and the place where education begins. The state is entitled to absolute savings on families. It may decide to kill, arrest and divorce spouses or leave their children. In this case, what is expected from the lowest level of the punished party, even if the death penalty to accept the guilt and regret, indicating that otherwise already the penalty will be imposed. In ideal states, all families should tremble at the same frequency if we do not want our efforts to be wasted. Uneducated families gnaw at the background of all efforts to keep the state alive and hinder our development.

In the relationship between the state and family, the rights of the child, the rights of parents, the rights and responsibilities of the state to the family and the family towards the state should be accepted by the state according to its philosophy. As can be understood from the verse state; must feel responsible for the practices within the family, the development and protection of the family.

The best thing to do in this situation is to keep people away from their families since childhood. This, of course, does not mean indefinitely loneliness. Considering that students spend time with their parents only on weekends, if you include summer and mid-holidays, they will be spending half of the year with their families and the other half with their other families at school.

On the Day of Resurrection, a ring made of fire is passed to him, who is asked for knowledge and hides it.

Words of Muhammad from Abu David

Training should be absolutely free of charge first. States can often forget about socialist relations and transform them in the name of justice as they are required by the philosophy of being a state. This can be extremely extravagant in profit and loss calculations compared to what is essential. Even for the state's self-control, it can be difficult, unpredictable, and insecure. In this case, estimates do not hold, frequent plans change and unrest increases. Considering this situation, education should be at the beginning of the services that should be provided free of charge with the necessary transformation as required by the socialist structure.

The above hadith states the principle of scholarship. As a law of God, we have knowledge of other people's rights in our property. Information must not be appropriately transmitted to the public and should not be charged to the public, except for private educational institutions on a voluntary basis allowed by

the state, and neither learner nor teacher should be allowed. For these reasons, none of the prophets and the people who follow them will charge and advise anyone against their light work.

And I do not ask you for it any payment. My payment is only from the Lord of the worlds.

Quran 26:109

16.2 Women's Education

Men are in charge of women by [right of] what Allah has given one over the other and what they spend [for maintenance] from their wealth.

Quran 4:34

Allah did not hold women responsible for working and earning money and supporting families. This is a constant law for all times. Always male dominated and otherwise unacceptable. That doesn't mean she can't work.

Never will I allow to be lost the work of [any] worker among you, whether male or female; you are of one another.

Quran 3:195

This verse also points to this. In marriages, this is based on mutual consent. If the woman does not work, she does not have the right to ask the father for a childminder or to have the privilege to cook and see the household chores and is the cause of divorce. Life is common, and this verse, the laws that it imposes, obliges the mother to do housework and childcare. However, in case of multiple marriages, other spouses may be exempted from this right by the request of the man, depending on the voluntary agreement between the man and the second or more spouses.

For these reasons, women may tend not to work instinctively, marry early as a housewife and have children. In this case, it is irrelevant to force every woman to undergo more education; but it should never be given the impression that this is the general stance of women. In many places from military service to hospitals, many women are needed and will be heard. Due to their ownership, they also work very efficiently as workers.

Article 17: Economical Order

It is forbidden to earn money from interest, and the exchange of value of money or barter goods. Organizations engaged in economic activities directly with the public must provide protection services for movable goods with standards set by organic laws. These organizations cannot give credit for any reason and may charge service fee for all the services they provide. It is forbidden to create usury and black market. The state does not limit the profit. The law between the employer and the worker is as defined by organic laws. No drudgery. The state recognizes the need for shelter and food as a natural right and takes the necessary measures. The state adopts the international and domestic "stock exchange" method. The state does not charge tax on its people. In accordance with the stock exchange, grant is given to the business owner. Agricultural areas belong to the state. People are not entitled to savings in agricultural areas. The state must continuously produce agricultural products according to the form and limit specified in organic laws. The state is obliged to make animal husbandry according to the form and limit specified in organic laws. People can breed animals. The center of attraction cannot be created, except what the state has created.

17.1 General shape

Allah has permitted trade and has forbidden interest.

Quran 2:275

Interest is an extremely important issue. This is only one example, although it has traditionally been known to be a share of the money lent over time. Muhammad even considered replacing bad dates with a smaller number of good dates, saying that the bad dates should be sold first and then the good dates.

Shopping or money and trade is not like the exchange of goods. Interest itself creates a second potential and is an unjust gain. Regardless of what is used for the exchange of goods, their potential to do business without labor is the worst enemy of the economy. The presence of the potential to do work for the labor, regardless of whether the winner or the loser, means that the efforts spent for the peace of the people and the survival of the state are not reaching their places.

17.2 Employer-worker law

And when We intend to destroy a city, We command its affluent but they defiantly disobey therein; so the word comes into effect upon it, and We destroy it with [complete] destruction.

Quran 17:16

As it is clearly stated in the verse, people are weakly created in terms of winning and managing. The capitals that pursue mastery will derive without forgetting the socialist rules and serving as they should. The goods will only appeal to one segment, and the services provided will be spent only to expand the business and the rights will be distracted by excuses. Therefore, the state must protect workers' rights with employers as they must.

17.3 Stock exchange

O you who have believed, do not consume one another's wealth unjustly but only [in lawful] business by mutual consent.

Quran 4:29

In order to say something about money management, some determinations should be made about money. Although money is itself a vehicle, it can never be the real purpose. The real goal is to create potential for yourself. The same thing can be one day 1 money the other day 2 money that you can not get that much with 2 money while you can get more goods with 1 money. In this case, the simplest thing to do is to keep the necessary amount of cash in our hands by taking into account the change in the value of money or to invest in the appropriate way and to borrow and invest, if possible to pay our debt with our investments. This is pretty unsafe. In doing so, at least on the one hand, we need to find definite solutions to our needs that consistently cost us money, otherwise our labor will evaporate and we will not be able to work and earn so that we have developed.

This change in the value of money always causes evaporation for the countries that are behind; because as long as there is a second country other than you, you will naturally be asked for 2 labor versus 1 retirement product and you will have to give up foreign trade in order to keep the foreign trade alive and to ensure the development of the country. To give an example of the simplest, we can consider a mine production facility for this. This mining facility will cost 1 coin and bring in 5 coins annually. When another state asks you to do this, you make a facility that will bring you 1 money a year for 1 currency so that you

don't break your trade potential in the world. This is the essence of winning. The gain is such, and even if the samples are randomly selected, their upper and lower limits will always exist and competition laws will do their job both domestically and internationally. In the meantime, the money of the country where you make the facility will lose value. When this is indexed in real life, as long as strong economies are strong enough to feed both themselves and the world, weaker economies will be exploited helplessly and without alternatives, and all labor will consistently benefit only one. Strong economies will be like your government offices, from agriculture to industry, from clothing to education, and you will always be asked for more labor.

If we give an example from the situation in the country, we can start with price hikes, which often come up as an inflation hike, and it is only a balance and does not make sense. As the welfare level of people starts to rise, the prices of all elements, especially house prices, rise further and people do not change because of this mutual foolishness. Instead of these raises, we must find the exact solutions to our needs, which we spend the money that we earn and which constantly cost money, so that we have fulfilled the condition of winning properly. Win, however, becomes possible and otherwise linger.

All of these effects have fatal consequences for countries that cannot share production. They don't stand a chance. As they have no chance, they lose people and brains to do business because of the opportunities they cannot provide for the capital in question. These countries have no choice but to hang signs that say "closed" to the entrances and exits and to meet their needs with social projects.

When all these factors are taken into consideration together with the others, the question of what kind of monetary policy we should follow should state that the state should not follow the money.

17.3.1 Socialism or Communism?

Theoretically the most powerful governments are communist governments; because there is no personal concept and it controls and appropriates all the money or labor. States, except for other taxes, usually receive about 1/5 of the money earned as a tax, and the rest of the money does not account for both foreign or domestic investors, nor tell them what to do. In particular, foreign investors, you can use the share of the money returned in the world can invest in their own countries. Then they start to take your brains and work force from you. Communism does not allow it and controls all the money. Thus, the evaporation of money has no effect; because people won't need it even if they earn little.

Although it sounds nice, it can also have fatal consequences; because it requires a very high condition despite being breathless. It also requires a high and wide technological infrastructure and a strong education system for ideal systems, that danger is still not distant.

As a major deficiency in communism, the limits of people's earnings are limited. People who are always waiting for someone else's labor can leave the country behind despite the coercion so that we cannot always wait for a hero to come out. There is no doubt that you will never see the true face of people from workers to statesmen in such a system where there is no future concern and people may tend to work at lower capacity; therefore, certain feelings, characteristics and characteristics, such as victory, belonging, reward and freedom, which are essential for being human, should never be blunted.

To sum up, given the laxity of people, non-communist socialism in general seems softer and safer; and communism seems more ideal, in which ideal people are raised and the necessary technological infrastructure exists there. Apart from the speed of development of the state and the upbringing of the people, people will not necessarily be needed in this non-communist socialist system.

17.3.2 Perfect Capitalism

In summary, such a system is required that it had taken the necessary measures indirectly as basic functions except for monitoring against all adversities and continues to improve itself despite the lack of statesmen and private companies, if any. This system will protect us against the high condition of communism, will not interfere with people's desire to earn money and compete, while meeting the basic needs of people. Such a system is possible by intersecting socialism and communism at an uncertain point when necessary transformations are made. In a matter of seconds a private company can become a government agency on paper and in this case neither the leader nor the staff changes.

Banks can be the cornerstones for such a system. Banks will receive shares from all active business according to the agreements they make. It can be %0.01 with one company or %10 with another. The state itself sets the upper limit. Banks, in turn, find jobs for companies, engage in advocacy, advertise and improve their business because of the fixed rate of profit, which they themselves earn more as long as improve companies. Banks also prepare those who wish to establish business in interviews with the Royal Committees. The Royal Committees see all active trade and potential, know the needs, and either accept or reject the job or propose another job. Again according to the potential, either the money gives less than the right of the job, it gives the right or more. He can give one more at a time, and another time, can give less, and on this occasion he only looks at his work being done. He doesn't care who's helping the country. Although it is not needed, it can also provide an acceptable level of assistance to help people gain experience with less money. Thus, an equal opportunity is created and the state has fulfilled its duty. It is no longer worried about, whether they are affiliated with other companies or sink.

No application can be made to any institution other than the banks. The state shall set an application deadline of 15 days for example; because these tasks require planning. Maybe they collectively hold all applications for a new job, maybe another reason. During this period, people cannot apply to another bank; because planning is broken. Agreements can be made with varying salaries at varying times; but there are lower and upper limits and exorbitant prices cannot be given, which means that the necessary infrastructure is incomplete and contrary to standards. The amount that the Royal Committee can allocate for the workers is already clear. The employer employs 3 workers and gives 3 pounds. There isn't much choice and a wide range anyway; because either work does not work, workers cannot be found or the necessary infrastructure cannot be established.

Interviews are important, but the quality of the bank is also important; because you have to convince the committee that you can do the job. In this case, the banks will teach you how to proceed and may also give you the money you cannot get by showing them the potentials or conditions that committees cannot see.

Perhaps employers are encouraged to trade foreign banks by their minds. As banks are busy developing their businesses, including their machinery, they may start a foreign or domestic trade with a second and temporary agreement, such as "zero risk", and take all the risk on themselves. In the meantime, he will give you new machines, make workers' reinforcements, or run your machines for 2 instead of 1 time and bring a shift system. It will be for a short time, but at the end of the work, it will give you the machines and say that "you can throw them in the trash"; because earned was earned.

Banks plan these things through economists. Economists are always engaged in the development of workplaces in the area of responsibility. The more economists earn, the more they earn. Workplaces give a permanent share in the limit set by the state and give it from their earnings. The state's limited and flexible share will allow the opening of new banks; because the share of banks that provide better quality services will be high and not everyone will accept it.

Banks must be obliged to hire a lawyer. Every job has to look at the number of attorneys appointed by the state. The costs of

the lawyers are also paid by the bank. Banks should also hire industrial engineers; because banks may want to use the money received from the committees in the most efficient way. Factories are ultimately regarded as trade commodities and delivered to the employer through banks on a turnkey basis. Banks can also get a second share from industrial engineers for this job; but industrial engineers can only establish business through banks. The state leaves the business of building factories to them. It is decided that there will be old or new machines according to the money received and the job. The bottom of the plate is thus peeled off and the production is used in the most efficient manner.

17.3.3 Practical transition

Practical transition is possible in the fastest way, but simply by borrowing within the state, and the state has to show certain determination. The state buys what it has to buy and owes it to its owners. Over time, the land, home or work as well as realizes the payment of money. The state becomes the guarantor of the basic needs and then gives the share of the market to the business owner in a controlled manner by holding the pulse of the market.

Even in the worst case, when the rules are as follows, no condition can harm us while obeying religion.

In which neighborhood a person becomes hungry, the people of that neighborhood fall away from Allah's protection.

Words of Muhammad from Musnad

Therefore, some scholars, "If a person in a town will starve to death, all the people of that town is considered the killer of the deceased and the diet of the deceased are charged from them." they have ruled. For the same reasons, we must communicate our needs to our leaders and criticize them when necessary due to our greatest jihad and standard stance; because they have no other work. There is no end to this, and it will always repeat.

Gabriel kept advising me to do good to the neighbor. I almost thought the neighbor would make the neighbor a heir.

Words of Muhammad from Bukhari

This hadith is another information about the neighborhood.

The person is not a believer that the neighbor next door is hungry when is full.

Words of Muhammad from ibn Abi Shaybah

This hadith also serves as a good example of the socialist and caring structure of Islam. It was seen that the rich neighbors fed the poor neighbors not rights but grace. It is one of the principles that should be implemented even if there is no transformation. In short, "employee wins." or "everyone in the same situation." such a word is not the word of the believer; because it is not that simple and does not reflect the truth.

For these reasons, we should share our bread with our neighbors if necessary. We should seek ways to use our land and labor more efficiently with a common and fair agreement. A more practical transition is not possible.

It also works internationally. The shape of the swap may vary. When someone buys something from a state, the seller state pays its money to its own people. States then periodically review the debt situation and make an agreement. Relative limits are determined by mutual interests. While a state has the potential to trade 1 unit from another state, another state may have a potential of 5 units because it has a higher potential in response. Developed states should be challenged for extra potential in spite of the groupings formed, and lower states should benefit more from them.

17.3.4 International competition

When it comes to international practice, competition rules must be defined with absolute certainty in order to prevent unfair gains. States should be grouped according to their developed level due to the essence of the exchange rate difference mentioned above. While the lower-level states are exchanging cheaper prices among themselves, the developed state should only be able to receive the same good for more goods. Thus, unfair gains and exploitation are prevented. Each class must pursue self-improvement with absolute certainty.

When this is done, there will be abundance and therefore the price decrease all over the world. Once, they came to Muhammad to bid on the market prices. He asked God for abundance and blessing, and rejected it; because this is a temporary solution and is not intended. People should make the necessary effort and statesmen should make the necessary transformations. The only way to develop is not to defeat a state and take responsibility for it. This is a chore in all religions and is also tiring. If you cooperate with good people in the world, even the armies do not hurt, today the state you feed tomorrow will sell to you cheaper goods and sank your government apartment.

In order for all these works to be carried out in the best way, a large database should be established, where all active trade and potentials appear both at home and internationally and followed by everyone. Everyone who wants to see everything the employer knows about their own business, such as the jobs that the smallest workplace on the other side of the world does, the jobs to do, the number and gender of workers, agreements and more. It is not always feasible to build a factory due to factors such as workers, material, raw materials, construction time or logistics, in short, even the largest companies may need even small seconds. Such a system makes them work in such cases.

Article 18: Security Order

The state is obliged to take defense measures. It allocates budget for it and educates the necessary people. All institutions responsible for security are attached to the Ministry of Defense and its leader is the Minister of National Defense. The Minister of National Defense is selected from among the generals who only know the current national or international order best and can manage the army when necessary. State accepts the right to life and defense as an innate right.

18.1 General shape

And prepare against them whatever you are able of power and of steeds of war by which you may terrify the enemy of Allah and your enemy and others besides them whom you do not know [but] whom Allah knows. And whatever you spend in the cause of Allah will be fully repaid to you, and you will not be wronged.

Quran 8:60

Military service is a mandatory duty for every individual with power. The security provided by someone must be provided by you when you arrive. If so, the state should not require compulsory military service except in special cases determined by organic laws. The state should be obliged to train voluntary security forces.

18.2 Some limits

The main purpose for wars is to spread God's consent in order to establish God's order; but man is not sincere, patient and fair enough to do so. We always accumulate hatred in the hearts of our enemies, giving birth to absolute hostility. State maps, one of the most changing things in history, are the best indicators of this. For these reasons, we must always give order messages and work for it.

If one considers the situation of a prophet in ancient times, there is no possibility of communicating firstly in an unprotected or later unarmed manner in such a situation in which the people can be very sensitive and unconcerned. A war can break out somehow easily; but the abundance of opportunities in our circuit does not even require being there for the notification. If there was a prophet in our revolution, he would have used social media except in special cases, even if there was a possibility of war, and they would follow him. Fighting for the need for raw materials is also irrelevant. We can separate and produce any matter in the electric field without a problem of energy, or we can bring asteroids such as mountains into the world without a problem of energy and propulsion, or make Mars and other favorable worlds a habitable world without energy problems.

Article 19: Death Penalty

The state imposes the death and ordinary punishments according to the form specified in the organic laws. The state uses the organs of the killed when it deems necessary according to organic laws, without first asking their own nation and then the people of other nations without thinking.

19.1 General shape

Indeed, the penalty for those who wage war against Allah and His Messenger and strive upon earth [to cause] corruption is none but that they be killed or crucified or that their hands and feet be cut off from opposite sides or that they be exiled from the land. That is for them a disgrace in this world; and for them in the Hereafter is a great punishment,

Quran 5:33

Death is likely to come anytime and is with us all the time. Death comes and does its job, regardless of age or superiority. Theoretically, people have the right to enjoy God's blessings as they wish under the law. For example, the liberation of this freedom by unjust killing requires the same punishment in return but is not sufficient; because a person who is willing to die cannot kill someone unjustly in return.

19.2 Some conditions

The King does not have to know every man at his disposal and every man who rules himself. Everyone shapes himself according to the law, so that a colonel knows another colonel or a doctor knows another doctor like himself. In the face of the loosening of this situation and the souvenirs that may occur within the state, the King can impose the death penalty on his own. Thus, the environment of trust is ensured despite the people we don't know as it should.

On the other hand, the internal organs of people who cause unfair multiple deaths, such as gangsters, terrorism and serial murder, should be legally taken away without being asked after being executed by the state. It is not worthy of this degree to seek the right of people who benefit from all the blessings of humanity and give us nothing, as well as those who suffer with severe

crimes such as death. It is best to make families happy with these organs.

19.3 Standard posture

People should have a standard stance in punishments such as death and imprisonment if the punishment is fair. This is a loyal stance against broken bonds of kinship or friendship, which is one of the most dangerous things that will disrupt society and create a distorted, jealous culture.

A good example of this posture is the prophet Noah. Noah wanted to save his son from the flood; but Allah opposed Him.

He said, "O Noah, indeed he is not of your family; indeed, he is [one whose] work was other than righteous, so ask Me not for that about which you have no knowledge. Indeed, I advise you, lest you be among the ignorant."

Quran 11:46

Again, Noah's wife and Lut's wife are a good example.

Allah presents an example of those who disbelieved: the wife of Noah and the wife of Lot. They were under two of Our righteous servants but betrayed them, so those prophets did not avail them from Allah at all, and it was said, "Enter the Fire with those who enter."

Quran 66:10

Abraham's father is also a good example.

And the request of forgiveness of Abraham for his father was only because of a promise he had made to him. But when it became apparent to Abraham that his father was an enemy to Allah, he disassociated himself from him. Indeed was Abraham compassionate and patient.

Quran 9:114

Muhammad's uncle is a good example.

May the hands of Abu Lahab be ruined, and ruined is he. His wealth will not avail him or that which he gained. He will [enter to] burn in a Fire of [blazing] flame. And his wife [as well] - the carrier of firewood. Around her neck is a rope of [twisted] fiber.

Quran 111:1-5

These are not excuses for returning from the path of Allah or the order of society; because the situation is clearly stated in the Quran.

O you who have believed, indeed, among your wives and your children are enemies to you, so beware of them. But if you pardon and overlook and forgive - then indeed, Allah is Forgiving and Merciful.

Quran 66:14

This is evidence. For the same reason, Muhammad said, "Do not offend your children by condemning their father and saying unnecessary words about them." He said. For the same reasons, Muhammad, "Even if my daughter Fatima cut off his hand for theft." He said. For the same reasons, "The people who destroyed before you; their privileged and noble when commit a crime, are left unpunished; a poor and weak of them committed a crime, are punished." He said. In this case, the only thing to be given is the one of Omar: "We are pleased with Allah as Lord, Islam as Religion, and Muhammad as prophet."

Interactive Laws

Article 20: Dynasty

The King is the only king of all places in the universe. The state is the property of the king, and the king has the right to save the state property for his family and for whom he wishes. These rights cannot be transferred. The kingdom passes from the father to the eldest son, unless he renounces the right to the eldest son. If there is no son, people choose king from other family members. The king may change only if a majority of the votes in the referendum are achieved and the person who does not defend religion cannot be elected as king. The king can be chosen as a king at any age if his mental, spiritual and gender states are all healthy. The woman cannot be elected as king even by referendum. If the king wears an accessory that prevents it from being recognized, the entire council of advisory is required to vote, as specified in organic law. The life, property, trade and rape security of the former king are preserved. The high betrayed king has no right to life; but the state protects the life, property, trade and rape security of the family. The dynasty is the honor of the people and all people and institutions are responsible for the safety of life, property, work and rape of the members of the dynasty. Deliberately damaging them is high treason. Governors are elected only from the members of the dynasty and cannot vote.

20.1 General shape

And [by] the father and that which was born [of him],

Quran 90:3

As described above, dynasty is a traditional form of government and, if not the best, it becomes an alternative form of administration.

Of course, not even people with psychological problems, even the kingdom, ordinary management can be prevented at least partially for occupational health and safety; therefore, the King must be able to reign only when he is healthy in all respects. Even though women may be the head of state due to teamwork, they cannot bear the heavy burden of presidency and cannot be as comfortable as men due to a number of other feminine features belonging to women.

20.2 Some limits

And what Allah restored to His Messenger from the people of the towns - it is for Allah and for the Messenger and for [his] near relatives and orphans and the [stranded] traveler - so that it will not be a perpetual distribution among the rich from among you. And whatever the Messenger has given you - take; and what he has forbidden you - refrain from. And fear Allah ; indeed, Allah is severe in penalty.

Quran 59:7

The cultural practice of this verse is, as mentioned before, a dynasty. Instead of being a King prophet, Muhammad wished to become a prophet with a sign from Gabriel.

Gabriel was sitting next to the Messenger of Allah. Then an angel came down from the sky. Gabriel said: "This is an angel that has not descended to earth from

the day it was created." After that angel landed He said to the Prophet: "O Muhammad! My Lord has sent me to you. Do you want to be a king prophet, or a servant?" he asked. Gabriel; He said to the Prophet: "O Muhammad, show humility to your Lord." The Prophet said: "I do not want the king to be a prophet, I want to be a servant prophet."

Words of Muhammad from Al-Khaysam

Apart from some rights granted by the Quran, he asked only for his family's respect.

Say, [O Muhammad], "I do not ask you for this message any payment [but] only good will through kinship." And whoever commits a good deed - We will increase for him good therein. Indeed, Allah is Forgiving and Appreciative.

Quran 42:23

Apart from that, he made us partners.

Know that Allah and His Messenger are free from counsel. But Allah has made this a mercy for my nation. Whoever consults them shall not be deprived of the right path. Whoever leaves will not get rid of the mistake.

Words of Muhammad from Bayhaqi

So by mercy from Allah, [O Muhammad], you were lenient with them. And if you had been rude [in speech] and harsh in heart, they would have disbanded from about you. So pardon them and ask forgiveness for them and consult them in the matter. And when you have decided, then rely upon Allah . Indeed, Allah loves those who rely [upon Him].

Quran 3:159

All this is because He is a global prophet, not a nation, so that people do not fall into profanity and become enemies to Allah and not be killed. This is also the case of "Caliphate on prophethood" or at the same status "Narrow Gate" of Bible; but states cannot do this in themselves. His caliphs should behave like this.

Jesus said to them, "The kings of the Gentiles lord it over them; and those who exercise authority over them call themselves Benefactors. But you are not to be like that. Instead, the greatest among you should be like the youngest, and the one who rules like the one who serves."

Luke 22:25-26

For these reasons, the city may be elected by the people except the King and the Governor; but only that and the rest is forbidden.

When taken in a country of 100 million inhabitants, this would mean almost 1,000 colonies. Considering that there are 4 states, only 250 Sanjak Lords or in Turkish "Bey" and enough Lord of Sanjak Lords or in Turkish "Beyler Beyi" will come to the state council. If deemed necessary, representatives from the delegation and the people's council may be elected. Such would be more appropriate, at least outside of special status meetings; because people need to know things like that spoken in the same court. We should pay attention to this sensitivity during, such as writing our laws. This should also apply to the same Consultative Assembly. Everything is in balance.

WARNING

It is forbidden not to raise them with the right knowledge and stance. The state should be considered the property of the dynasty.

Do not honor yourself in front of the king, and do not stand in the place of great men. For it is better to be told, "Come up here," than to be put down in front of the ruler whom your eyes have seen.

Proverbs of King Solomon 25:6-7

Article 21: Royal Committees

The State shall give to the wishing to do business through the Royal Committees the amount it deems appropriate. The money is given according to the interviews in the committees at the end of the preparation in the banks. The Royal Committee shall control the exorbitant price increase where necessary and take the necessary measures.

21.1 General shape

And Allah has favored some of you over others in provision. But those who were favored would not hand over their provision to those whom their right hands possess so they would be equal to them therein. Then is it the favor of Allah they reject?

Quran 16:71

The main task of the Royal Committees is to provide the necessary money for the people who are prepared to interview by the banks to which they are affiliated, and to keep the market prices in their regions under control. Committees; It gives prices according to the needs of the regions, colonies and the raw materials and industry in the country.

21.2 Price balance

And it is He who has made you successors upon the earth and has raised some of you above others in degrees [of rank] that He may try you through what He has given you. Indeed, your Lord is swift in penalty; but indeed, He is Forgiving and Merciful.

Quran 6:165

The stock exchange method basically targets abundance both within the nation and internationally. It targets the single price even in the long term and prevents the deficiencies that cause price increase with production, by this way cash money will be a good investment material when it is not used and cannot lose value. It controls the supply and demand fluctuations that may occur over time to maintain these fundamental principles. If necessary, exorbitant prices will be prevented and sanctions will be made.

Article 22: Active Banking

The state recognizes banks as an institution for establishing and finding a business. Banks cannot lend for any reason. Banks may receive money for their services. Banks find work for the job seeker or prepare the person who wants to start a business to make a presentation to the Royal Committee. Banks shall receive a continuous share in accordance with the mutual agreement of all active trade as specified in organic laws.

22.1 General shape

O you who have believed, do not consume one another's wealth unjustly but only [in lawful] business by mutual consent.

Quran 4:29

The state is obliged to take care of its people. The state is like a nuclear family. All members of the family work for one thing, that is to advance the family. When the day comes, all family members, for example, cut down wood or carry stone from the mountain to build house only to meet the need of a person in need. Together, it meets the need of that person.

The situation in the state plan is not very different, and justice and laws come into play here. One order may be more fair than the other. In this case, the correct transformations will be life-saving. In this case, banks cannot lend according to stock exchange and colonial order; because the state has already undertaken all the work of its people and has set fair and directing principles for them.

22.2 Royal committee

Banks work like an employment agency. The only binding institutions are banks. People who want to find a job can find jobs only through banks. They cannot apply directly to employers. In case of application, the banks make the necessary planning and submit their suggestions within the specified period. The person applying for a job within this period cannot apply to another bank.

People who want to start a business also apply to banks. They are informed about the work they want to do, prepare the necessary documents and prepare for an interview with the Royal Committees. The Royal Committees will give the money necessary to start a business, if deemed appropriate by the interview.

Article 23: Royal Academy

The highest and only binding institution of education and training is the Royal Academy.

23.1 General shape

Say, "My Lord, increase me in knowledge."

Quran 20:114

The superiority of the scholar is like my superiority to the lowest of you. Certainly, Allah, the angels, the people of heaven and earth, and even ants and fish in their nests pray to people who teach the good.

Words of Muhammad from Tirmidhi

With the intelligence test, the Royal Academy recruits students for all fields, primarily social sciences. There is no restriction on the number of students or students at the Royal Academy. Students who are geniuses have priority. The Academy has the right to educate its own students starting from primary education. It is the duty of all teachers in the country, including kindergarten, to take care of students for the Royal Academy. The governor and gentlemen, if necessary, are appointed or assisted by people from the Royal Academy.

23.2 Some tasks

Government jobs are jobs that require serious expertise, and even students need to be selected and trained to work in different tasks for their management. Geniuses are different from normal people. Geniuses can take a job that one can't even imagine, and they won't even look back. This is not in their hands; therefore, the best students should be raised at the Royal Academy, starting from primary school if necessary. They can be taken to the city where the school is with their families.

However, they work in partnership with national and international scientific societies. They both produce and apply knowledge and train all other important statesmen, including the King. This is the right one; because such an academy cannot deal with the ordinary teaching work. They should have determined and necessary solutions to solve both country problems and world problems. It must have the necessary partnerships and opportunities for this. For this reason, such an institution should be autonomous again, like the others, and the issues that we avoid should be determined and taken by law.

Article 24: Working Order

Working is a right as well as non-working according to the form specified in organic laws. People can work under the ownership of someone else or do their own work, except for compulsory service set by organic laws. No one shall be employed in jobs incompatible with age, power and gender. The break is entitled during the working time. Holidays are determined by organic laws. Even if people are not working, the state takes the necessary measures against they are in need. The boy or girl is placed in a separate house when reaches maturity, whether is married or not. Married people are not deprived of this right. The retirement age is 55 years. Service hours are essential for retirement and are retired if they are older. Those who have completed this period or who are of age cannot be called for compulsory service except in cases of war or natural disaster. There is no pension. For employees in private or government agencies, payment is made at the end of each workpiece that does not exceed the daily or daily working hours. The worker is free to ask for the wages he will receive, although it is a crime and cannot be employed without a contract, and the employer is obliged to declare the constitutional rights of the worker. Daily working hours are as specified in organic laws for government and private institutions. Resignation is a right protected according to the manner in organic laws. As well as workers have the right to strike, employers also have the right to collective dismissal according to organic laws. Undisciplined and crafty workers are rented and cannot benefit from free home service.

24.1 General shape

No person is charged with more than his capacity.

Quran 2:233

The verse explicitly states the principle of operation for all the steps of the hierarchical order with its predominant basic condition. Otherwise, cruelty is a crime. Work is the most natural human right, because the only condition to win and live depends on work. This right should be recognized, protected and developed by the state. Barriers to winning must be removed by the state with a servant spirit, and the working conditions should be clearly defined by the state for both managers and workers. The

time spent on labor must return as a gain and the labor spent by the society must be reflected in real life as development. Over time, work times should be shortened and our needs should be reduced by the availability of elements that provide them. All elements, from holidays to breaks, from salary to gender, should be well established with a good focus on winning by the state. It is not worth winning to do the same things all the time and get the same results.

As it is said below, with the construction materials produced, multi-storey buildings can be erected prefabricated without concrete in a short time which can be called tomorrow. There will be no lighting or heating and cooling problems in these buildings as energy is not a problem with the necessary techniques. When the factories that produce the necessary infrastructure, they can produce and increase production far beyond the manpower; therefore, for houses of different status made by the states for their people aside colonial free houses, the state should provide money. This; In order to meet the needs of the building, it will open new job sites, create jobs and these jobs will feed many other companies.

Every human being is in the learning process; therefore, one cannot be held responsible for an untold course, nor can people be held responsible until they are sure that the lessons of unlawful obedience and command are memorized. You cannot make such a counter decision by saying "You must have already known that much."; because theoretically, people are treated as a patient who is inclined to do all sorts of nonsense that may or may not come to mind. This is one of the principles that must be applied in private or state institutions.

24.2 Compulsory service

The state should temporarily look after people who do not want to work; because doing so will bring profit. First of all, in societies that are free of economic worries and only people who do their own work, the level of peace increases due to the indifference towards problems. The quality of work in a tranquil environment will undoubtedly increase depending on this peace. These changes will also directly reduce crime rates. The increasing trust and patience of people and statesmen to each other is of strategic importance for a state.

The right not to work is not unconditional. This right is a declaration that the state is obliged to take care of the people of the state. The government meets all their needs until they find a job and, if necessary, enforces compulsory labor with contracts of 6 months, 1 year, shorter or less, depending on the consultation with employers, even by lot. It is part of the compulsory service and is subject to a fee.

Mandatory service is abusive and, if not, can be misunderstood among people. All religions, if necessary, even gave the state the right to enslave and employ people, but at the same time encouraged the slaves. This is purely discipline-oriented and for the absence of empty people. In the meantime, he nurtures them all. Everything is in balance, and in such cases, the principles of implementation must be clearly and in detail defined by organic laws for the public as well as for state administrators. Both of the paid or free ones.

24.3 Salary

O you who have believed, do not consume one another's wealth unjustly but only [in lawful] business by mutual consent.

Quran 4:29

Salary is the equivalent of labor and a sign of earnings. Money is the most widely used tool and does not have many alternatives. Even in communist systems, for example, a food card

needed to buy flour can be used for the black market or for interest purposes. Salaries must be well organized and dynamic, taking into account such characteristics of money.

Every person has the right to ask for the money will receive before starting work. Nobody has to listen to anyone's life stories or experiences. An employment contract is made for this and the constitutional rights such as resignation must be stated in the employment contract. If the right to resign within the working period of the contract made, the court may intervene to hear the complaints of both parties. The defendant is the oath.

Article 25: Trade Order

Build unauthorized to do your own business; It is forbidden to sell, rent or transfer the workplace. Workplaces are given by the state free of charge to people who want to do business by producing. If necessary, the draw may be withdrawn or withdrawn for others. People who have developed themselves in production; has the right to request a business market or business center from the state. Jobs and workplaces that do not require production are covered by the state for non-profit by the presidency in the colonies. Doctors and Lawyers have rooms in government agencies. Lawyers cannot charge a consultation fee. The state controls trade money. The state shall impose, if necessary, embargo on currencies or commercial potentials, which may, at varying times, go abroad according to the form in organic laws. The state records all the money movement. Movable and immovable goods are also included. Any material cannot be used for money. The government uses electronic money and a programmable citizenship card in accordance with the organic law.

25.1 General shape

O you who have believed, do not consume one another's wealth unjustly but only [in lawful] business by mutual consent.

Quran 4:29

It is forbidden to sell, rent, or transfer the rights of the workplaces in order not to allow second persons who use someone's name. Any constitutional or legal responsibility is the first person to sign an agreement with the state. However, the use of shops as trade goods should be prevented in order to prevent inflation and unfair earnings and to encourage production. The state should give them free to the people who produce.

It is not from us who deceives us.

Words of Muhammad from Muslim

The money earned by commercial businesses can only be taken abroad with the approval of the state. The State has the right to impose an embargo on organic time. The only reason is that it is possible to achieve the potential advantage of commercial success.

Lawyers, if we need to give information about people, we have to disallow it. This is unethical. This is not the same as the examination of doctors.

Except those who fear Allah, do good, and behave honestly, merchants shall be raised from the dead on the Day of Resurrection.

Words of Muhammad from Tirmidhi

If the entire monetary movement is recorded and implemented by other nations, there will be a fairer order all over the world. Illegal work will come to an end and everyone will pursue ordinary business to make money. States that deal with illegal activities in the states plan will look for legal ways to make money. Control of money movements is impossible with paper or coins. Only electronic money must be used for this purpose. The entire transaction should be able to be filed. The software will automatically inform people with certain social status and suspicious actions. It will write reasons such as country and trade pattern in all money movements.

25.2 Export

O you who have believed, spend from the good things which you have earned and from that which We have produced for you from the earth. And do not aim toward the defective therefrom, spending [from that] while you would not take it [yourself] except with closed eyes. And know that Allah is Free of need and Praiseworthy.

Quran 2:267

There is money in the stock exchange method. In the current capital scheme, the money you earn is unique and limited when spending at home. When you buy goods from abroad, you will use the same money again and you will get the goods even if you have losses due to the exchange rate difference and it comes to the domestic cost. The money given in the stock exchange is intended to stimulate domestic trade. The state gives its own money in the expenditures to be made for domestic production and does not set limits according to the need; because in trade, when one needs the labor of another, more work means more direct buyers. You cannot export domestic shopping without reviving and open up more international exchange potential. When you want to invest in foreign countries according to the trade you make and the potential you open, the government buys for you money. This money exchange business is entirely permitted by the bilateral relations of the states. So there is no single and limited money. It doesn't have to be as much as the potential you open to your needs from foreign countries that you have to provide. The government will also allow you to benefit from the greater potential of better companies, which is fair, which is counted even if no direct tax is collected from the money earned. While increasing exports, on the other hand, we must reduce our dependence on the outside in accordance with the socialist order and, if possible, should not be dependent on any element as the main goal. This should be the counterpart of our efforts, which is the secret of winning, not lingering.

As a result of the cash accumulation that will arise in any case, with stock exchange; abundance, fixed price in the long term and, if possible, cheaper goods are targeted at the same price; trade prices will prevent inflation and open up new business potentials, this business owners will be instrumental in winning. No change can be made in this matter.

Administrative Laws

Article 26: Rights and Responsibilities of the King

The King is the highest authority, including the trial. The King does not have to come to court. If a trial is required, the judges come to the King's favor and the King invites people to the same place. No one can stand higher than the king during the trial. The king can judge people in any place and time. The

King is the leader of the Advisory Council and also the Prime Minister of the country. It may reject the decisions of the Advisory Council only twice and the result shall be determined by referendum. He cannot change the constitution alone. Keeping state secrets or dealing with non-duties is a cause of war for the King. Citizenship or deprivation of citizenship, exile and death sentences and pardon of detention shall be binding only upon the vote of the King and the King shall not be entitled to transfer these rights by himself. The King has the right to arrest indefinitely. The King considers the national and international high-esteem of the people's request for pardon forgiveness for intercession. The King's testimony alone would be accepted. The King is obliged to fulfill his religious responsibilities. The king cannot make a war decision alone, except in a compulsory state of war. War decisions require a majority vote of the Advisory Council. The Governor, the Advisory Council Member, Lords and the Sanjak Lords are appointed by the King. The King may also appoint from outside the Royal Academy if he so wishes, and there is no restriction to the King, such as gender, age, tenure or education. The replacement of the Sanjak Lords by the people is binding upon the approval of the King. The King has the right to stay in the head indefinitely.

26.1 General shape

O you who have believed, obey Allah and obey the Messenger and those in authority among you.

Quran 4:59

The kingdom must be the king who owns the country in the world in the space settlements under the Constitution of the Nations. The state being the property of the King is not a gift. It is only a strategic decision and still the property of the public; because all powers are still in the public. The public can change the powers at any time.

The King's family, whose enemies are numerous and capable of being exploited, should not be cared for both in terms of security and for the purpose of avoiding confusion. No state can be consumed by the dynasty or the King. Moreover, the King will not spend money for every dynasty. This is a religious and traditional posture, and the evidence is the following verse.

And what Allah restored to His Messenger from the people of the towns - it is for Allah and for the Messenger and for [his] near relatives and orphans and the [stranded] traveler - so that it will not be a perpetual distribution among the rich from among you. And whatever the Messenger has given you - take; and what he has forbidden you - refrain from. And fear Allah ; indeed, Allah is severe in penalty.

Quran 59:7

26.2 Some responsibilities

The king must have the highest authority as the state's most trusted person. The king, who has the authority to free consultation from vocabularies and to encourage consultation, should be able to make changes to the constitution only when the Advisory Council or the public provides a majority of votes.

The fact that the King is the supreme judicial authority does not mean that he cannot be tried or that he can do whatever he wants. This; Although it is a precautionary right to a person who

represents society, the most trusted by all, and the dignity of people, the constitution, of course, still accepts the final decision as binding when there is a popular vote.

When he is tried, he must be the supreme judicial authority and, if he wishes, he will be tried at his home or at a place he deems appropriate because he has the highest protocol and he has the right to judge and he is innocent just.

Of course, the ability to court within people is important to keep things going and making the King's playground large.

Since the state is basically a team game and is ruled by a family, it is natural for the kingdom to be the eldest male son in the family. It is the state that even a child can manage.

Since the offense should only be imposed on the perpetrator, no sanction should be imposed on the family if the King is punished. That means people play with their dignity.

The King is the most competent person in his state and must be the greatest servant. They should be aware of every business and have the most intelligence information against the moves of malicious people.

Although it has the authority to disrupt decisions alone, it would be best to be able to reject the decision twice, since it does not have absolute authority.

If there is a phenomenon called security, if it is to be ensured by a number of people, the King must be the person most trusted by the people; therefore the state secret cannot be kept from the King. Only the King should be able to decide the necessity of secrets and moves. Otherwise, the King may consider you an enemy.

The King must have the highest authority. Indefinite imprisonment aims discipline and is the best punishment for disruptors who do not comply with the manners of consultation and insist not to do so. The state is respectful to the international courts as there is no decision that cannot be tried. However, the right of the King to persist in such a situation as a violation of human rights such as prolonged detention, which he does not deserve, cannot be found under the constitution; because it does not have absolute authority.

Judges, governors or members of the Advisory Council shall be civil servants. It is expected that their knowledge and abilities will be paid for. No one can be relieved because there is no more than that.

The king, of course, must be the most perfect of all people, especially in terms of knowledge and morality, in the business he represents; therefore, of course, he must fulfill his religious duties.

Taking a war decision alone does not, of course, guarantee victory for the King, nor does it mean that the decision was right at first. Soldiers or ammunition, of course, do not come down randomly from the sky and must be used in the most efficient way in wars; therefore, a war that is unnecessary and will be lost can lead to bankruptcy and collapse. This serious decision is too important to be taken alone.

The king must be able to select the talented names he trusts as the most reliable and competent person, and appoint him as governor, provincial president and district president to the areas of superior and strategic service.

Do not honor yourself in front of the king, and do not stand in the place of great men. For it is better to be told, "Come up here," than to be put down in front of the ruler whom your eyes have seen.

Proverbs of King Solomon 25:6-7

The King must elect members without a promise. People often tend to put aside a stone that they find on the road that can damage a vehicle or a person. In the same way, electing without promises will do the same or similar tasks even if when the King has not already invited to the Assembly. In this case, the King will send these people an invitation to continue with us. The rights and responsibilities of the assignment shall be respected mutually.

Article 27: Advisory Council of the King

The members of the Advisory Council are elected by the King and there are no restrictions on the King's age, sex, education or tenure. The Advisory Council does not accept non-citizens as members. The Advisory Council is responsible for legislative, executive and judicial proceedings. The Council of the Elders are the nationals of the Advisory Council. Each of the ministers of the council of elders is the prime minister. The council of elders consists of the Minister of National Security, Minister of National Economy, Minister of National Education, Minister of National Justice, Minister of National Religion and Governors. These are the most competent people after the King and have no superiority to each other. The King judges unconditionally only. The council of elders is responsible for opening sub-ministries. The sub-ministries established or sub-ministers appointed by them are binding upon the approval of the King. The Elderly Delegation is able to carry out judicial proceedings according to the interests of the public and there are one deputy judges. The King cannot make amendments to the constitution on his own and a majority vote of the Advisory Council is required. The Advisory Assembly elects its chairman and the chairman only conducts the session.

27.1 General shape

She said, "O eminent ones, advise me in my affair. I would not decide a matter until you witness [for] me."

Quran 27:32

The advisory council is the assembly in which the King has chosen his own aides to rule the state. They are originally raised privately, with no age or education restrictions. The king must be able to assist an unlimited number of experts, as he alone cannot suffice. On the legislative, executive and judiciary the King has the right to austerity; but the real work is on the shoulders of the Assembly. The most basic and important functions of the country are legislative, executive and judicial, it can never be allowed to break this seriousness. Continuous public voting is irrelevant and causes both time and material loss. Moreover, it is not suitable in terms of business procedure; because the doctor does not consult with the patient very often. It is enough that everything is in the middle and there is nothing that cannot be prosecuted. Parliaments exist for this reason, and the people who are used not only in the Assembly but also in state affairs in accordance with international law and state law discipline should always be people with the right to citizenship.

27.2 Some limits

The Elders Committee; personal armored aircraft, armored land vehicle and expert close protection, which will provide the fastest and safest transportation, and the provision of these facilities by the state should be a necessity. The use of these facilities to the full extent should be at the discretion of the Board of Elders. The State should build accommodation centers for the members of the Advisory Council in accordance with the standards established in each province. As the most competent and busy people in the state, the Elders must be protected and have the fastest and safest means of transport and facilities for the best occupational health.

It is appropriate to appoint governors from dynasty members. Dynasty rules require it. If there are siblings or relatives from

the dynasty who are not qualified and should be appointed, they should be bestowed upon them.

And what Allah restored to His Messenger from the people of the towns - it is for Allah and for the Messenger and for [his] near relatives and orphans and the [stranded] traveler - so that it will not be a perpetual distribution among the rich from among you. And whatever the Messenger has given you - take; and what he has forbidden you - refrain from. And fear Allah ; indeed, Allah is severe in penalty.

Quran 597

Article 28: Noble Council

Noble Council is the judicial assembly to which all judicial bodies are attached. This Supreme Court is obliged to establish institutional courts. All judicial work has been categorized and divided into small pieces by the Supreme Court as in organic law. There are internal and external threats or international relations that shake the unity and dignity of the state. The leader of the Supreme Court is the Minister of National Justice and can alone decide whether the case meets these requirements. The Supreme Court may, if necessary, use the Council of Elders as helpers for consultation.

28.1 General shape

O you who have believed, be persistently standing firm for Allah, witnesses in justice, and do not let the hatred of a people prevent you from being just. Be just; that is nearer to righteousness. And fear Allah ; indeed, Allah is Acquainted with what you do.

Quran 5:8

The Supreme Court is obliged to develop administrative courts. For the main ministries to which all state institutions are affiliated, judicial work is fragmented under the leadership of more specialized judges in the organic law of that field.

28.2 Some conditions

First, institutional courts do not mean all kinds of cases of people in the institution. It means litigation on institutional matters that belong to that institution.

Second, it refers to ministries. Distinction should be made, such as those dealing with family problems and those dealing with military matters.

Article 29: Rights and Responsibilities of Managers

All persons who have created the law of obedience between them are responsible for the safety of each other's lives, property and rape. Illegal orders and obedience is a crime. Bribery is prohibited. All managers must obtain assistance for consultation. Even if there is no complaint, the state expects its managers to solve the problems. Managers are responsible for accumulated problems. Administrators may remain in the lead until their retirement period expires, unless otherwise required by the organic law. Managers must act daily according to the conditions in organic

laws. The confidentiality of the logs is essential unless the administrator declares otherwise. In recruitment of civil servants, the interview is essential and the interview committee is elected by lot. Governors can make a judicial trial in public. Each governor must obtain a judge's help. The Minister of Religion has no right to punishment other than that required by his institutional leadership. Even in the case of agreements where human rights, international law and constitutional articles are read or unread, the contract may be broken by the courts and the court will make the necessary sanctions. The public is not responsible for inadequate measures that can lead to deliberate or unintentional abuse. The damage suffered by the people belongs to that person or institution.

29.1 General shape

So do not weaken and call for peace while you are superior

Quran 47:35

This verse does not order oppression and does not only speak of war. This verse also means not to relax in a place and to force everyone to walk along the line. Otherwise, the situation is as follows.

If [instead] you show [some] good or conceal it or pardon an offense - indeed, Allah is ever Pardoning and Competent.

Quran 4:149

It is a discipline and should be dedicated to whether it is straightforward as it should be. They won't be perfect. Injuries made on intentional or unintentional issues that will give us experience in a subject should be avoided; because the blessing of states comes from the defense of the people's right, the state has no other business.

Contradictions arising as a result of the polarities of the existence, each person must select and go on individual line, can make decisions on this certain line, and if it is right can give orders. The supervisor who makes an unlawful order is strictly guilty, but it is checked for those who abstained from the various orders and misconceptions given the lessons of unlawful orders. The line of unlawful orders should be clear for each institution. Everyone must know his duty very precisely.

For example, if there is a worker who develops himself in a simple limited number of jobs in a workplace and becomes an engineer with a sense of uniqueness, other workers are responsible for this situation. If the engineer is damaged in a fight that may arise, all workers are taken into account and dismissed if necessary. For this reason, for example, in the event of an attack or threat, bread must protect the place where they earn it at the expense of their lives, and they must also protect their engineers. Of course, if he behaves in amounts that should not be there, the engineer must first be patient and then complain; but it should never be discussed. It is not an excuse I could not help myself. Very few criminals who do not say so.

The prayer and posture determined by God for this and many other reasons, especially for the rulers, are as follows.

Allah does not charge a soul except [with that within] its capacity. It will have [the consequence of] what [good] it has gained, and it will bear [the consequence of] what [evil] it has earned. "Our Lord, do not impose blame upon us if we have forgotten or erred. Our Lord, and lay not upon us a burden like that which You laid upon those before us. Our Lord, and burden us not with that which we have no ability to bear. And pardon us; and forgive us; and have

mercy upon us. You are our protector, so give us victory over the disbelieving people."

Quran 2:286

Interview committees are important in every aspect of the state. If you want to be fair, you should take into consideration the weaknesses of people and develop methods that will not put them in a difficult situation and assume the crime which is not crime as a state so that people cannot break their acquaintances and favoritize them.

Consultation is indispensable, especially for a person who may face aging and prone to error. Despite the complexity, hardship and weariness of state duty, they should always seek helpers to protect their backs and show them their mistakes or give them ideas. Shameless and demon-spirited, spoiled and unconcerned people who like chaos, speak for themselves and judge, disrupt the order and try to get into uncertainty should be punished harshly, whether they are leaders or helpers. Even Allah will not leave their work to the Hereafter.

Indeed, those who like that immorality should be spread [or publicized] among those who have believed will have a painful punishment in this world and the Hereafter. And Allah knows and you do not know.

Quran 24:19

This verse is also good evidence for it, and not only for adultery. It is not an excuse that he believes.

The heads of towns, villages and local administrations may win an unlimited number of elections and remain indefinitely at the head of public and, if internal voting is in accordance with organic laws, by administrative superiors, by the votes of their institutions or by appointments. Continuous change is not appropriate. The replacement of people with different tactics, strategies and ideals is nothing but a waste of time. Instead, ideas should be exchanged and consulted. They are not forced to stay any longer; because the people choose. If it is deemed appropriate by the king, the last word will remain in the first place. If the State considers it appropriate for confidential or explicit reasons, it shall make the change it wishes. He is free to do what he believes will be more strategically efficient.

29.2 Some limits

There is a scourge to denote everything, and the disaster of this religion is bad rulers.

Words of Muhammad from Suyuti

As it can be understood from the hadith, the administrators disrupt society. For example if a child is said to "have a blank paper" during a sweet chat; but the number of prisoners is increasing day by day; If the respect and tolerance of people is also increasing day by day, this is the problem of the state and therefore the managers. If a neighboring state cools you for some reason, it is the problem of the rulers. Crime is always ours.

The fact that the rain is multiplied and the plant is low, the Quranic readers are very poor, the rulers are very reliable and the reliable ones are less.

Words of Muhammad from Suyuti

After me, men will come to your administration so that they will accept things that your religion and you accept as bad, and they will regard the behaviors you accept as good and beautiful as bad. Let any one of you reach such an evil period, that there will be no obedience to those who rebel against Allah. Those who deny them and fight them are saved.

He finds or approaches the peace that departs from them. Among them are those who join among them in their worlds, and fall with them.

Words of Muhammad from Suyuti

I'm not afraid of the fights that will kill my nation, the enemy that will perish. But I fear the catastrophes of perverse presidents. Because if they obey him, they will be subjected to sedition, and if they oppose, they will slaughter my nation.

Words of Muhammad from Suyuti

All these hadiths speak of this.

One of the most important deficiencies of the leaders who lead the branch is unfair favoritism and bribery. Bribery is a cursed phenomenon that makes it impossible to maintain justice and order. No manager can take bribes under any circumstances. It is their duty to defend their work at the expense of their lives, and only then can they be counted manager. Allah says in Quran that unless a nation will not correct themselves, he does not correct. This is possible only by being loyal and bribery is absolutely forbidden.

And do not consume one another's wealth unjustly or send it [in bribery] to the rulers in order that [they might aid] you [to] consume a portion of the wealth of the people in sin, while you know [it is unlawful].

Quran 2:188

29.3 Exclusive features

Although Quran is a book that descended on Muhammad, the most mentioned prophet in it is the Prophet Moses. The reason for this is that a great person has a great experience for all times and even Muhammad has something to learn from him, which the Quran tells us as follows.

Over every possessor of knowledge is one [more] knowing.

Quran 12:76

Even Moses took lessons from a person called in the Quran who gave him knowledge in matters he did not know. For these reasons, even the commandment of Muhammad is as follows.

So be patient, [O Muhammad], as were those of determination among the messengers and do not be impatient for them.

Quran 46:35

Man learns from an animal and sometimes from a natural event. Whoever wants to learn can learn from the most stupid. Even prophets, even Muhammad, have learned some things on the occasion of Omar, sometimes from an ignorant Muslim. Therefore, we must always be open to development, free from prejudices and decisively committed to this issue.

29.3.1 Muhammad

Muhammad is the best manager. God would not have created the world without Him, and He only created from His light. That is the custom of Allah. The hierarchy is very serious and rigid. This is a fixed verse. Just as man is born in a way from his mother as a baby, Muhammad's supremacy is eternally to all beings, and no other creature does. All the prophets, even the mother and the father are leaders who have formed law among us in the aspect of the world. They cannot claim us and pay evenly. They take their wages from Allah, and we are free; but Muhammad's right cannot be paid in Paradise. People receive the blessings of Paradise from him, as the baby is fed from his mother in the womb. This authority, "commendable status" is only sick to Him.

And from [part of] the night, pray with it as additional [worship] for you; it is expected that your Lord will resurrect you to a praised station.

Quran 17:79

This verse is evidence to the "commendable status", and Muhammad mentions it. In this position, the person, even Muhammad is son of Abraham, the prophets do not speak from the authority and says "the righteous brother". Angels and people always live between manifestations of beauty and sublimity. As Muhammad said, Gabriel would shrink as well as lentils as he said in the Quran while covering the sky. For these reasons Muhammad's name was agreed by "Salawat", is his right and "Salat" is obligatory to Muslims.

Indeed, Allah confers blessing upon the Prophet, and His angels [ask Him to do so]. O you who have believed, ask [Allah to confer] blessing upon him and ask [Allah to grant him] peace.

Quran 33:56

This verse indicates this.

Gabriel said to me, "Whoever hears your name does not bring you Salawat, deserves punishment."

Words of Muhammad from Ramuz

This hadith is another proof of this.

And We have enjoined upon man [care] for his parents. His mother carried him, [increasing her] in weakness upon weakness, and his weaning is in two years. Be grateful to Me and to your parents; to Me is the [final] destination.

Quran 31:14

For the same reasons, the Quran included parents and ordered them as the above.

Some of the stories about the creation of Muhammad are listed as follows.

Adam: And, Lord, what is this light? He said: This is the light of a prophet from your freedom, whose name is Ahmed in the heavens and Muhammad in the earth. If it wasn't for him, I wouldn't have made you!

Words of Muhammad from Mavahib

One day, one of the companions: "O Messenger of Allah, what Allah has created before everything, what can you tell me?" said. He replied: "First of all, He created the light of your Prophet from his own light. The light would wander with the might of Allah. Then, there was neither destiny book, nor pen, nor heaven, nor hell, nor angel, nor heaven, nor place, nor sun, nor moon, nor human, and nor gin.

Words of Muhammad from Mavahib

Light upon light. Allah guides to His light whom He wills. And Allah presents examples for the people, and Allah is Knowing of all things.

Quran 24:35

These hadiths point to this.

When I was prophet, Adam was between the soul and the corpse.

Words of Muhammad from Acluni

This means that Muhammad, as the first creation, teaches all angels, even in spiritual life, that he has been praying for many years.

And [mention, O Muhammad], when We took from the prophets their covenant and from you and from Noah and Abraham and Moses and Jesus, the son of Mary; and We took from them a solemn covenant.

Quran 33:7

This verse is evidence for this. Prophets were named according to their order of arrival. All this is not divinity. These are simple divine laws.

And We have not sent you, [O Muhammad], except as a mercy to the worlds.

Quran 21:107

Here is mercy to the worlds, the most distinctive feature of the management. This means service not only for those who believe in themselves but also for those who do not. What's the point of all this? Of course it means taking care of your own piece. The whole world, Muhammad, who is his part, should look and heal the world if he wants to look beautiful so that he can look beautiful himself. This should be the most fundamental duty of managers. The better he can correct the flaws in his own piece, the bad people. Prophets are like this. They accept people as sick, and do not obey them quite, they tolerate them in order to heal their ignorance.

29.3.2 Mahdi

Hazrat Mahdi is one of these blessed individuals and one of the greatest leaders. His qualifications are praised in all holy books. Arabi listed some of his leadership qualities as follows.

Foresight, understanding the holy book, knowing the meaning of the verses, knowing the state and movements of the people to be appointed, not leaving the mercy and justice even when angry, knowing the classes of beings, knowing the intricate sides of the works, the need for people be aware of the sciences.

Arabi

Foresight is one of the top priorities of every leader; but it develops with knowledge and thought, as with every feature. Thought alone is experience. There is no stupidity as great as learning only by living. Mind; it is the only place where you can make countless mistakes in army administration, science, government or all other work; so you can experience with jigsaw puzzles there.

The person who does not make mistakes is unwise, and does not judge without experience.

Words of Muhammad from Bukhari

This hadith is good evidence for this, and if possible we should stumble in our minds before playing a move in real life. It is essential for a ruler to understand holy books; because the world is governed by these rules, and the account is according to these rules.

And We have certainly presented for the people in this Quran from every [kind of] example - that they might remember. [It is] an Arabic Quran, without any deviance that they might become righteous.

Quran 39:27-28

You can also find all the existing human morality there and know people and know their behavior, what they can do, their limits.

This [Quran] is enlightenment from your Lord and guidance and mercy for a people who believe.

Quran 7:203

This verse is good evidence for this, and other holy books can be read and narrated according to Muhammad; but Muhammad says that in these books, some things have been falsified and the inventor of lies will go to hell. It is very important for a leader not to leave mercy and justice even when he is angry; because the leaders are "bought" in the words of Quran and Bible.

Indeed, Allah has purchased from the believers their lives and their properties [in exchange] for that they will have Paradise. They fight in the cause of Allah, so they kill and are killed. [It is] a true promise [binding] upon Him in the Torah and the Gospel and the Quran. And who is truer to his covenant than Allah? So rejoice in your transaction which you have contracted. And it is that which is the great attainment.

Quran 9:111

This verse is a good example. In Enoch, when he talks about the Gog and Magog incident, he mentions it as follows, and for the elite it is considered only a ordeal agreement or game.

It will be an agreement for the elected, and a test day for the sinners.

Enoch

They should be far from being asserted that they deserve the title of leadership.

And not equal are the good deed and the bad. Repel [evil] by that [deed] which is better; and thereupon the one whom between you and him is enmity [will become] as though he was a devoted friend. But none is granted it except those who are patient, and none is granted it except one having a great portion [of good].

Quran 41:34-35

It is also important for a leader to know the intricate sides of things; because deciding according to conscience does not mean that there is a reward for error. Muhammad said that the ruler who ruled or obeyed his enthusiasm is in hell fire. He must know the intricate sides of things in order to foresee the events or to provide the balance of profit and loss in case he has to judge according to his conscience so that he does not fall under the avalanche. Understanding the needs of people is a sine qua non of leaders; because no problem can be solved without empathy. According to Muhammad, he cannot ask for something that he does not want for himself; therefore, he should know other people from himself, and at the same time know the limits and needs of people outside his own body, so that he can satisfy them, and in this way he can sustain the social order as far as he can and grow better generations. In its own time, like people and scientists, in short, managers should have the information and solutions that are needed by the states and have solutions that are not yet known so that they can keep up with themselves and society.

These qualifications can be gained by educating managers, which again requires a cultural state structure. Managers that we have gained such qualifications are as valuable as the state. We can give an example.

One day, Omar asked the people what they wanted most. Some wanted a house full of gold, some wanted a house full of money, and some wanted a house full of jewelry. They wanted to spend these golds and jewels in the way of Allah. When it came to Omar, he said: "I would like to have men like that house full of Abu Ubaidah bin Jarrah, Muaz bin Jabal and Abu Huzaifa's freed slave Salim and to assign them to the exaltation of the name of Allah.

from Bukhari

These people are also geniuses.

Quraysh has two geniuses. These are Abu Bakr and Abu Ubaidah bin Jarrah.

Words of Muhammad from ibn Asakir

This hadith is good evidence for this. For these reasons, it is absolutely the duty of every teacher to find geniuses in the Royal Academy and the schools affiliated with. It should be grown and raised from an early age.

Again, some of the features of these people are as follows.

There are three people from the Quraysh who are the most prominent of this ummah, the most beautiful of morality, the most of the sense of life. They never lie to you when they talk, and they don't want you to speak. These are Abu Bakr, Osman and Abu Ubaydah b. Jerrah.

Words of Muhammad from ibn Hajar

They are men of law. Muhammad says he does not care who helped him for Mahdi. They can't escape the law. It is also so; Because you play your move is the bouncing enemy.

Don't worry if someone turns your back on you, so you can distinguish between your friend and your enemy.

Khalifa Ali

This requires great knowledge and ability. At the same time, these people alone would be accepted to testify. For this reason, they get under every job and they can easily do things you can't imagine, and even at this time they have peace of mind. Nobody has a chance against them. It is therefore not difficult for such persons to prevent corruption. These are real lions and the end of the game with the lion is death. These features do not mean unconditionally careless.

29.4 Wisdom

Recite, and your Lord is the most Generous Who taught by the pen.

Quran 96:3-4

Almighty Allah, the owner of generosity, did not compel people from generosity to the difficult slopes of the Inspirational Divine, which required close loyalty and knowledge each moment, and taught him to write with pen.

Who remember Allah while standing or sitting or [lying] on their sides.

Quran 3:191

In doing so, he used the devil to preserve the glory of man; for man is as great as he is in need of God, and is commanded to beg Him for every need that the essence and commandments of the Quran are bound to the one that is already.

It is You we worship and You we ask for help.

Quran 1:5

Of course, the best evidence for this devotion should be from Surah al-Fatihah, the summary of the Quran, aside from the hundreds of verses that can be given as examples.

If humankind was not afraid of anyone other than Allah, Allah would not have plagued anyone else. Humankind is bound to what he hopes to connect. If humankind had not given hope to anyone other than Allah, Allah would not have left in need.

Words of Muhammad from Tirmidhi

Another reason is God's self-esteem; because the interlocutor received; the most honorable of the creatures and the person whom he called the caliph, of course, must be protected by Allah again and in the same way a human being should be the honor of all human beings.

We have certainly created man in the best of stature.

Quran 95:4

For these reasons, Muhammad, as the greatest wise, is an illiterate prophet; the devil is far from Him.

Those who follow the Messenger, the unlettered prophet, whom they find written in what they have of the Torah and the Gospel.

Quran 7:157

Prophets also have demons; but after the prophethood, he is removed, and all of them qualify as "trusted", which means sure in knowledge and judgment. That means he doesn't follow the devil and doesn't say anything of his own. This is the real surrender.

Like everyone else, I had a demon, but he surrendered to me.

Words of Muhammad from Tirmidhi

And if Muhammad had made up about Us some [false] sayings, We would have seized him by the right hand; Then We would have cut from him the aorta.

Quran 69:44-46

Nor does he speak from [his own] inclination. It is not but a revelation revealed.

Quran 53:3-4

Other proofs are as follows.

Allah, who holds my soul with power and might.

Words of Muhammad from Muslim

In many places, Muhammad makes a beginning like in the hadith above, and this is one of many examples.

Don't you believe that I am in the Father, and that the Father is in me? The words I say to you I do not speak on my own authority. Rather, it is the Father, living in me, who is doing his work.

John 14:10

This is the Bible from Jesus. It is the same in all other prophets and in the people who really follow their path, and another alternative is impossible and paradoxical.

[That is Our] established way for those We had sent before you of Our messengers; and you will not find in Our way any alteration.

Quran 17:77

The people who are away from blindness and with God every time he breathes, are like sinless angels, more like prophets. Allah is the One who does not forget and is perfect. In this case, it is a law that the prophets who want Allah from every request forget it; because otherwise it becomes divinity.

Adam forgot, so his lineage forgot.

Words of Muhammad from Tirmidhi

I'm just a person like you. I'm gonna forget how you forget it. Remind me if I ever forget.

Words of Muhammad from Bukhari

These hadith also speak of this. Adam was inclined to forget; because he was a man, not a deity, and he forgot about freedom.

I do not forget, but I forgot, until circumcision through me is circumcised. Remind me if I ever forget.

Words of Muhammad from Shifa

For these reasons, Muhammad says in this city as in the hadith. Otherwise, in the case of this, human becomes God or God's appreciation he becomes an angel who owns a private property, that there are different things person likes according to own will and nature, and these are impossible.

We will make you recite, [O Muhammad], and you will not forget. Except what Allah should will. Indeed, He knows what is declared and what is hidden.

Quran 87:6-7

Even though this state of forgetting is from Allah, Allah does so as He wishes and makes it the means of Satan, which is also important.

[O Muhammad], and if Satan should cause you to forget.

Quran 6:68

This verse also shows us the form of forgetting. Why can Satan make Muhammad forget something despite a devotion that has been alienated from Satan and whose work belongs to God, and believing in it is a religious duty and otherwise requires eternal fire? This is not a contradiction; because the devil has been made an instrument to preserve the honor of man because they will be away from teaching to read and write. This is not sin; because man is doomed to forget. Satan or something that Allah has forgotten does not change. Satan cannot confuse only the servants and deeds of the Prophets.

The fourth devil's name was Penemue. He taught human beings the pain and the sweet and all the secrets of the wisdom of the angels. He taught people to write with ink and paper; so many have entered into sin. For such a purpose, people were not created to show their beliefs with pen and ink. Humans were created like angels so that they could remain righteous and pure, and that death that destroyed everything would not touch them; but now they are disappearing because of their knowledge, and this power is consuming them.

Enoch

These above lines confirm the above-mentioned things. Allah has taught to write with a pen from his generosity; but this caused the devil to be means. On this occasion mankind stayed away from Allah and other evil virtues appeared, because of this distance did not resolve these. And because of their knowledge, they disappear, and this power is consuming them. This was reflected to the human as a side effect.

Knowledge was a point, ignorance replicated it.

Khalifa Ali

The mystery of all heavenly books is in the Quran. Everything in the Quran is in Fatiha. Everything in Fatiha is in Basmala. Everything in Basmala is at the beginning of Basmala. Everything in the head of Basmala is underneath it.

Khalifa Ali

With the words attributed to Ali, He said as above.

God sent down from the sky one hundred and four books. He put the knowledge of a hundred of them into the Torah, the Bible, the Psalms and the Qur'an. Then, these four books carry the sciences to Mufasal surahs; He put the sciences of the surahs in Surah Fatiha. Whoever knows the commentary of Surah al-Fatiha knows all the exegesis of Allah. Whoever reads Surah Fatiha, it is as if he has read the Torah, the Gospel, the Psalms and the Quran

Hussein ibn Ali

Therefore, Khalifa Ali and Some great scholars like Hussein say this as above. Omar, sent by Muhammad to take advice of Uvays, was given the following advice: "Do you know Allah? Then you don't have to know anything else. Does God knows you? Then you don't need to be known by anyone else."

It is possible to come across similar teachings in foreign cultures.

I have heard that one of the ancient gods of that place lived in Egypt near Naukratis, and the holy bird of this god was called Iblis. God's own name was Theuth. These gods had found numbers, arithmetic, geometry and astronomy as well as checkers and dice, and most importantly letters. At that time he was the ruler of all Egypt, Thamos, and lived in the upper part of the country in a big city called the Thebes of the Hellenes and called his god Ammon. One day, Theuth went to him and presented his art; he said that the Egyptians should teach them. Beriki asked what each one of them benefited from. As Theuth explains separately, he says that he finds some beautiful, some not beautiful; so he ate some and praised some. In showing each of the arts, Thamos is said to say a lot to Theuth both as praise and satire, but it takes time to talk about all of this. When they came to the letters, "O monarch," said Theuth, "this doctrine will make the Egyptians wiser and their memory more powerful. I found the medicine of memory and wisdom." The ruler replied: "O the master of masters, Theuth! While some have the ability to give birth to arts, others have the ability to determine whether they will harm or benefit their users. Now you're the father of the letters, because of their good intentions, you're saying exactly what they can do. Because this gives memory to the souls of those who learn to use; relying on signs that no longer belong to them, they forgot to use their own memory. That's why you found the remedy, not the memory. You offer your students the image of the wisdom, not the truth. They will think of themselves as knowledgeable because they learn so much without a guide, but they will be ignorant and incompetent in many ways because they seem to be wise but not wise."

Plato

Socrates, one of the great thinkers, said, "Knowledge is not obtained, it is remembered." and against writing; because people like Him know by inspiration from God.

And it is not for any human being that Allah should speak to him except by revelation or from behind a partition or that He sends a messenger to reveal, by His permission, what He wills. Indeed, He is Most High and Wise.

Quran 42:51

They are not evidence of their salvation or wrongdoing; but this is the case. Tesla says that even though he is God's inspiration. Some great scholars, such as Arabi, therefore say that the source of true knowledge can only be inspired by God.

So high [above all] is Allah, the Sovereign, the Truth. And, [O Muhammad], do not hasten with [recitation of] the Quran before its revelation is completed to you, and say, "My Lord, increase me in knowledge."

Quran 20:114

This verse also points to inspiration for us, and it is necessary not to enter a state of being hasty or as I have been to secrets or to understand wisdom or to be wise.

The servant says a word without thinking and moving, so he goes to a place farther away from the east and west of Hell.

Words of Muhammad from Bukhari

Anyone who speaks a word against the Son of Man will be forgiven, but anyone who speaks against the Holy Spirit will not be forgiven, either in this age or in the age to come. "Make a tree good and its fruit will be good, or make a tree bad and its fruit will be bad, for a tree is recognized by its fruit. You brood of vipers, how can you who are evil say anything good? For the mouth speaks what the heart is full of. A good man brings good things out of the good stored up in him, and an evil man brings evil things out of the evil stored up in him. But I tell you that everyone will have to give account on the day of judgment for every empty word they have spoken. For by your words you will be acquitted, and by your words you will be condemned."

Matthew 12:32-38

29.5 Beneficence

Sometimes it may be undecided to choose between trained generals or other high-ranking statesmen. In such cases, managers who are not promoted or retired should be bestowed. In this case, people have the task can earn less, while the retired wins more. Villa can be given as a gift in suitable places, that already they will be on duty if necessary again. There is nothing wrong with that. Already the emirate is not something to be desired and in some cases is not given to the one who wants it. The following hadith is also scary enough.

O Abdurrahman, do not ask for a commandment! If you are unintentionally brought to a post, God will help you. If you become a commander of your own accord, you may be deprived of God's help.

Words of Muhammad from Hakim

Our standard stance on this issue must also be Islamic, and our admission is again "We accept Allah as Lord, Islam as religion, Muhammad as prophet." Muhammad must have obeyed the superiors. "A little disobedient dies as an infidel." He said. Beyond that, it should be far from the claim of existence and it should be remembered that a Muslim does not do something that he does not want to be done to anyone else, and the feelings of brotherhood should be sought. Otherwise, it is the claim of being and the Roman principle. There is no room for such nonsense in Islam.

I will be the first to be removed from the grave on the day of the people's resurrection. When people reach Allah, I am the orator. When they give up their hopes of everything, I am the herald. The flag of praise is in my hands that day. I am the most valuable of the children of Adam, but I do not brag.

Words of Muhammad from Tirmidhi

I am the commander of the prophets. I'm not saying this to brag. I am the last of the prophets. No brags! I am the first to intercede and the first to intercede. No brags!

Words of Muhammad from Muqaddimah

On the Day of Judgment I am the Lord of the Adamites, and the flag of Praise is in my hands. No praise, that day Adam and others are all under my banner. I'm the first one to break up the earth, but no boast.

Words of Muhammad from Tirmidhi

Muslims are like pilgrims who are far away from their claims of existence, almost as if they are on top of each other and pretending to be self-immersed, that their stance cannot be more fragile, otherwise they will easily fall to blasphemy. Their motivation is the Hereafter that if they were the king of the world, they would remember and consoled the day they were free and lonely, free from all bad emotions. We must find and bestow ways to keep them entertained in this world.

You are fond of being an manager. However, except for those who respect their rights, stewardship is repentance in the Resurrection.

Words of Muhammad from Bukhari

Dying without being ruler is of course salvation for you.

Words of Muhammad from Abu David

On the apocalypse day, manager of ten people, his hands are brought tied. If he is just, he is saved, otherwise he will perish because of his persecution.

Words of Muhammad from Tabarani

These hadiths are enough to be consolation and are quite scary. We can wipe out eternal life for only one whim.

Article 30: Courts

The courts are autonomous. Every citizen has the right to a fair trial at no cost. If the court decision is not liked, only the right to reapply for the same case is granted twice, and each time different judges have the right to reject the case without re-trial. No one shall be brought before a court other than the court to which he is bound by law. Courts other than the official courts have no binding obligation. No decision shall be binding without express or confidential reasoning. Hidden reasons cannot be hidden from the public indefinitely and misused. People of different religions have their own independent courts, despite possible contradictions between laws. Trial of people from different religions; as long as they are not contrary to human rights, their own religion or the constitution, they are made in these courts, including the death order, and the conditions are the same as in organic laws. Judges have the right to prosecute according to their conscience according to the constitutional and organic laws. Judges cannot be put under pressure and cannot be harassed for consensus or clarification except as required by judges, and cannot be tried unless they are intentional or negligent. The trial of judges is based on the hierarchical order in the judicial bodies. The course and outcome

of the proceedings are at the discretion of the judge. The judge is entitled to mediation if both parties are voluntary. All the elements of the state, which have created a labor law, have the rights required by the business to be tried even after the termination of this law for any reason. Waiting for revenge is an offense as well as disrespect for human rights and the sanctity of justice.

Words of Muhammad from Haysam

If a scholar jurisprudence and hits it in jurisprudence, he wins two wages, and if he fails, he wins one.

Words of Muhammad from Muslim

Nevertheless, as can be seen from the above hadiths, judges are human beings and they can make self-sacrificing decisions. This does not justify them and prevent them from being tried. Finally, they are also civil servants. Judgment does not require school, and the public can appoint judges and judges where appropriate. The state does not change because it raises judges in the name of professionalism.

There is no person or institution that cannot be tried for his work from doctors to engineers, from heads of state to military service. The same applies to judges. The autonomy of an institution does not mean that it is independent. Autonomy is a purely methodological feature for ensuring health and comfort. However, the judiciary has a form. Judges can only be judged on the basis of hierarchical order among themselves or through parliament.

30.1 General shape

O you who have believed, be persistently standing firm for Allah, witnesses in justice, and do not let the hatred of a people prevent you from being just. Be just; that is nearer to righteousness. And fear Allah; indeed, Allah is Acquainted with what you do.

Quran 5:8

Courts are one of the most important elements of order in society. They either disrupt society or make man. They either gnaw or conserve all the labor spent. The state should not receive money in accordance with its philosophy to become a divine arbitrator or to share when necessary.

People who belong to different religions should be able to establish their own colonies and be judged according to their own religions.

If there is a crime, it must be punished without any other reason for the honor and rule of justice. Delaying this for personal reasons is a crime in itself.

Of course, judges should only walk along the line drawn when they are entitled as experts of the matter. The judges, who maintain the dignity of justice and are expected to protect in the first place, determine the course and results of the cases on their own.

Judges, governors or members of the Advisory Council shall be civil servants. It is expected that their knowledge and abilities will be paid for. Since there is no more than that, no one can be dismissed or judged.

Where people can show unjust decisions such as arrogance, envy and jealousy, no unjustified decision can be made, which requires that every business be categorized as a matter of protection of information. The state may show hidden reasons for occupational health and society not to be confused.

30.2 Judges

Judges should be as free as possible and in consultation with each other. Although they have the right to decide according to their conscience, this is still within the legal range. They can make mistakes or be tried. When they make mistakes, their apologies may be criminal reductions or freedoms and even monetary compensation, which the state has to undertake.

You guys bring your cases to me. Some of you may be able to articulate your claims and proofs even though they are unjust, and I can judge them in favor of these regular expressions I have heard from him. So don't let any one of you give you something that someone else has this right to. Because I have taken a piece of fire with this provision I have given according to the grain and gave it to him.

Words of Muhammad from Muslim

Although he was a prophet, Muhammad said these words.

Judges are three classes. One goes to heaven, two to hell. The ruler who fits own desire is hellish. The judge who does not know the subject, but judges about hell. The judge who judges in accordance with right and truth is in heaven.

30.3 Practical Transition

The practical transition to religious rule is very simple, even for existing schemes. As mentioned above, religion is not entirely foreign to rules as rules are not as well. Punishment is still a matter for the courts and is decided only by religion in religious colonies.

General Cultural Legal Principles

Article 31: State of Emergency

State of emergency, martial law, mobilization, war law, mandatory war conditions and practices are determined by organic laws. Unconditionally, the civilian population cannot be taken to the streets collectively without arms. The King, who gives orders to the people collectively, is judged with high betrayal and has no right to life. Even under compulsory warfare, even under attack, there is no collective war without the King's order. Internal rebellions cannot be considered war. The state must have taken the prevailing measures against the rebellions. There is no person or institution that cannot be tried, and the state suspends the constitutional rights of all persons and institutions by a decision of the assembly.

31.1 General shape

O you who have believed, upon you is [responsibility for] yourselves. Those who have gone astray will not harm you when you have been guided. To Allah is your return all together; then He will inform you of what you used to do.

Quran 5:105

State of emergency and the action plans are phenomena that have to be predetermined to the extent. It is one of the most important phenomena for the survival of the state. In these cases, the State must punish those who violate the rules.

31.2 General attitude of the public

In rebellion and other kinds of sedition, people should not act hastily. Religious orders on this subject, with absolute certainty, always order not to interfere with corruption.

When events and corruption occur, avoid being a murderer and become killed.

Words of Muhammad from Abu Nu'aym

Don't leave home when it's time for sedition! Be like Abel the son of Adam.

Words of Muhammad from Tirmidhi

These hadiths are good evidence for this. People should never go to the streets, especially in cases of war or rebellion. Under no circumstances can the chain of command-obedience be broken. It can be occupied for months and can be difficult. Despite this, the people do not take to the streets on their own. These works can only be done in consultation.

Article 32: Marriage

A man cannot marry a man or a woman cannot marry a woman. Marriage is a right for a man or woman, and divorce is a right according to the conditions in organic laws for both. The minimum age of marriage for men and women is 16. Having a child or adoption is a protected right and is encouraged by the state and is not limited by numbers unless measures are taken by organic laws. According to organic laws, a man can have multiple marriages. The State has the right to divorce the persons it considers guilty according to organic laws.

32.1 General shape

Men are in charge of women by [right of] what Allah has given one over the other and what they spend [for maintenance] from their wealth. So righteous women are devoutly obedient, guarding in [the husband's] absence what Allah would have them guard. But those [wives] from whom you fear arrogance - [first] advise them; [then if they persist], forsake them in bed; and [finally], strike them. But if they obey you [once more], seek no means against them. Indeed, Allah is ever Exalted and Grand.

Quran 4:34

Marriage is a sacred association that keeps people alive both within the family, the paradise in the world and the society, and to protect and develop all our labor.

Exalted is He who created all pairs - from what the earth grows and from themselves and from that which they do not know.

Quran 36:36

And of all things We created two mates; perhaps you will remember.

Quran 51:49

As it is said in the verses, everything is created as a couple and because everything has an opposite, it gains meaning by this way, and gets rid of loneliness. So are women for men and men for women; but marriage is not presupposed, and is circumcised.

Youth! Whoever has the means, get married immediately. And who fasts if he cannot find financial means. For fasting is for him his lust.

Words of Muhammad from Bukhari

Four things are the circumcision of all the prophets. A sense of shame, creeping fragrance, use miswak and marry.

Words of Muhammad from Tirmidhi

Although not prescribed, it should be encouraged by the state and offered to people by the environment. It is also forbidden to devote himself to religion, to retire to a corner and not to marry.

I swear to you that I am the most feared and the most resilient of Allah. However, I also fast. I pray, but I sleep in the middle of the night. I marry women. This is my circumcision, this is my way of life. Whoever turns away from my circumcision, it is not from me!

Words of Muhammad from Bukhari

Women are weak people by their creation and have their own particular circumstances. They are phenomena. Due to their creation, they may not easily agree with men and even their own sex in every subject. They are easily caught up in evil feelings such as jealousy, hatred, and anger, and may not get rid of them easily.

O you who have believed, it is not lawful for you to inherit women by compulsion. And do not make difficulties for them in order to take [back] part of what you gave them unless they commit a clear immorality. And live with them in kindness. For if you dislike them - perhaps you dislike a thing and Allah makes therein much good.

Quran 4:19

A believer does not condemn a woman because of an attitude that he does not like. If he doesn't like one of her, she might like another attitude.

Words of Muhammad from Muslim

For these reasons, Allah and His Messenger ordered as above. Men were ordered to be patient. So are the prophets and those who followed his path. Beating them except for extreme situations is not halal and humiliated.

Do not know those who beat their wives as good ones.

Words of Muhammad from ibn Majah

However, there is also that women will be punished for what they do to men.

But the men have a degree over them [in responsibility and authority].

Quran 2:228

I've seen hell. I've never seen a hideous sight in my life. I saw that the majority of the people of hell are women. They asked: "Why, messenger of God?" He replied: "What they swear" Again "Do they swear to Allah?" they asked. In response, "They are ungrateful to their husbands and their good deeds. If one of them is good to the world as long as it stops, then if she sees something she will not like and says: I have never seen any good from you."

Words of Muhammad from Bukhari

This hadith is a good example of this, and men must be patient with them and women must also educate themselves.

32.2 Divorce

Divorce is twice. Then, either keep [her] in an acceptable manner or release [her] with good treatment.

Quran 2:229

Although divorce is deserved for men and women, it is restricted by men's leadership and therefore because of the witness and approval features. The woman is also limited in terms of witnessing that she is inclined to defeat because of her weak creation.

Apart from that, it is already ordered to be loyal and always loyal to both men and women. Divorce, although halal, is not well cared for, and if deemed necessary both by society and by the courts, it is ordered to protect family law.

In the eyes of Allah, the most unlovable of halal is divorce.

Words of Muhammad from Abu David

This hadith also mentions this. In the case of possible family problems, spouses should not throw them in, and if necessary, ask for help from the family circle or familiar friends or coy older people close to them. This is not weakness or condemnation and is something that can happen to everyone and is naturally welcomed by everyone.

And if you fear dissension between the two, send an arbitrator from his people and an arbitrator from her people. If they both desire reconciliation, Allah will cause it between them. Indeed, Allah is ever Knowing and Acquainted [with all things].

Quran 4:35

32.3 Mother and father

Allah's approval is attained by pleasing the mother and father. The wrath of Allah is drawn through anger of the mother and father.

Words of Muhammad from Tirmidhi

Mother and father are two beings who are considered sacred duty to be obeyed as long as they are right. The disrespect of many to them is seen as the end of society and a sign of the Resurrection. Muhammad; When people disobeyed and opposed mother, he accepted the time when people brought friend near and make father away, and when they bowed to own wife, and when the girl came to his mother as rebellious, as apocalyptic time.

32.3.1 Carer service

And your Lord has decreed that you not worship except Him, and to parents, good treatment. Whether one or both of them reach old age [while] with you, say not to them [so much as], "uff," and do not repel them but speak to them a noble word.

Quran 17:23

Taking care of older people requires professionalism. Every person sees amateur people in his family who are interested in this kind of elderly people who are in desperation and are actually persecuting. The state should accept this situation and provide caregiver assistance if necessary.

32.3.2 Retirement homes

And We have enjoined upon man [care] for his parents. His mother carried him, [increasing her] in weakness upon weakness, and his weaning is in two years. Be grateful to Me and to your parents; to Me is the [final] destination.

Quran 31:14

Best of all, they are retirement homes where the state will constantly check and force older people to stay there. In a colonial system away from people and in a forested area with large gardens and all kinds of social facilities, retirement homes will be quite good for people to live the rest of their lives.

There should be hot and cold water pools, showers, television and internet, movie theaters and all other social facilities as well as all the necessary professional people and equipment for mental and physical health. If necessary, they can be watched from a screen where they go in the garden or forest with the watch they put on their arms and if necessary, sudden intervention is performed. Unmanned small drones are addressed to them if necessary without going to them, and they also address us.

Article 33: Migration Status

Traveling at home or abroad, moving to home or abroad, is a right protected by this constitution according to the form in organic laws. Foreign visitors or permanent foreigners are responsible for the constitution, except for the conditions in organic laws. Those who remain in the foreign country for more than the time specified by organic laws are expelled from citizenship. The time spent abroad may be deleted by the time spent domestically according to the form in organic laws. The state recognizes international asylum requests and owes criminal extradition. The state recognizes and assists international security units. The state respects the laws of that state for its people living in foreign states.

33.1 General shape

And of His signs is the creation of the heavens and the earth and the diversity of your languages and your colors. Indeed in that are signs for those of knowledge.

Quran 30:22

States use all their time, effort and money to protect their culture and to educate their people. All the work done to achieve peace can, of course, lead to jealousy towards foreigners. States should be respected in this respect. Foreign states should not stay for a long time due to the corruption that may be experienced due to religious and cultural reasons or the uneasiness that may arise from continuous seeing. This is so even between two people who love each other. Moreover, every citizen has to think about own homeland in order to give labor.

Considering that the colonial order is accepted, it is not a problem for them to stay in the colonies of their own religions when they live their religious beliefs in foreign states as they do in Muslim states. Famous people or other imperative people, for example due to a government job, can remain in their secular colonies if their environment or business requires it.

33.2 Right to protection

People must stick to their own races up to their language and clothing, which are the verses of Allah and must be protected.

Every man's clothing is the flag of his body country. It is a flag that a man raises on the door of his own body house, declaring which culture he is attached to.

Words of Muhammad from Tirmidhi

The apocalypse does not break unless my ummah follows the course of the previous ummah and follows it step by step.

Words of Muhammad from Bukhari

Every society requires devotion and service to its religion. It protects itself against foreign thoughts; therefore, in a conflict that can be entered, the crime will always belong to the foreigners, as the religion of the society will be dominant, but in this case it is a rebellion, and the penalty is only penalty in this case.

33.3 Immigration law

The order I am referring to, with all its rules, will provide welfare for people; but this will, of course, make the countries of attraction a center of attraction. This means that if you do not have a solid immigration law, national labor will be used by people who do not deserve it. However, we must of course create a safe immigration law.

Article 34: Heritage and Testament

The state recognizes the right to inherit and applies it according to the form in organic laws. The state itself determines the elements that can be inherited according to the social and economic order it determines. State; recognizes the right of testament and applies according to the form in organic laws. Everyone has the right to receive shelter in exchange for his or her own labor other than the state's free shelter.

34.1 Heritage

Prescribed for you when death approaches [any] one of you if he leaves wealth [is that he should make] a bequest for the parents and near relatives according to what is acceptable - a duty upon the righteous.

Quran 2:180

Inheritance, as can be understood from the verse is obligatory. People must share their assets in some way before they die. Inheritance will be kept in the personal belongings protection cabinets which banks have to build, and in case of death they are taken there by the lawyers of the suburbs.

Unlike the current situation in colony and stock exchange order, some assets cannot be left as inheritance; because the state allocates them. It is taken back to be given to someone else in a situation like death. All these details should be determined by the state.

34.2 Testament

Then whoever alters the bequest after he has heard it - the sin is only upon those who have altered it. Indeed, Allah is Hearing and Knowing.

Quran 2:181

As it is understood here, it is obligatory to leave a will. People should always have their wills ready, regardless of age, and change them over time if necessary. The wills are kept in the personal belongings protection cabinets that banks have to build, and in case of death they are taken there by the lawyers of the suburbs.

Article 35: Loyalty and Witness

The state expects loyalty and testimony from its people under all circumstances.

35.1 Loyalty

That Allah may reward the truthful for their truth and punish the hypocrites if He wills or accept their repentance. Indeed, Allah is ever Forgiving and Merciful.

Quran 33:24

Loyalty is a difficult task. Muhammad swore to fight with his own descendants and relatives. He was expelled from his homeland. As a result, he returned as the victor and established a better order. David said in Psalms that he did not betray any of his friends for the same reasons. This is an indicator of loyalty that can only be done by civil servants. Otherwise, all religious orders are to sit unconditionally in the house and be killed, if not killed. After all moral and knowledge accumulation in ordinary people, judges or opinion leaders do not have the authority to decide according to the conscience that they officially recognize or will not recognize.

Loyalty is a must for the public; but it is not unconditional. It is unconditional, according to the rules of loyalty. It does not mean obedience in all circumstances. What makes the wrong state is to stand before the state and seek its right in a right way. The state is neither for statesmen nor for spoiled rich people. They are all servants and loyalty to the state is possible by bringing them on the right path by law. Every individual of the state is not loyal to the state, but can be an enemy even in giving patriotic messages. States hold even the police force against their own people, and the greatest enemies always come out of our own.

The greatest jihad is to tell the truth to the melika.

Words of Muhammad from Abu David

35.2 Testimony

When one of you encounters a situation that requires a word for Allah, do not let him humiliate himself by hiding the word.

Words of Muhammad from Musnad

Witnessing is one of virtuous behaviors. According to Muhammad neither shortens life nor narrows the supply. Allah will not correct their condition unless a people correct themselves.

Indeed, Allah will not change the condition of a people until they change what is in themselves. And when Allah intends for a people ill, there is no repelling it. And there is not for them besides Him any patron.

Quran 13:11

This verse proves this. In order to correct oneself, each individual must know own social responsibilities separately and believe in it and follow it with determination. Only one person can change a nation.

Not to testify was condemned and almost counted as a false witness.

When he is called to testify, the person who is afraid of witnessing is like a false witness.

Words of Muhammad from Tabarani

Whoever abandons his witnesses or hides his witnesses, Allah will make him eat his flesh in front of the creatures on the Day of Resurrection and put him to hell in chewing tongue. And whosoever shall testify against a believer or a disbeliever, he shall be hanged from the tongue of the Day of Judgment and shall be with the hypocrites at the lowest level of hell. Whoever tells a dream that he has not seen, as if he has witnessed a lie.

Words of Muhammad from Al-Haris

The perjury is cursed and condemned. It is one of the most dishonorable behaviors beyond even witnessing.

People lie and act perjury, testify that they are partners of Allah.

Words of Muhammad from Musnad

And [they are] those who do not testify to falsehood, and when they pass near ill speech, they pass by with dignity.

Quran 25:72

Whoever testifies to a lie and with this testimony takes the property of a Muslim person or causes his blood to be shed, he deserves hell.

Words of Muhammad from Al-Haris

Whoever testifies against a Muslim about what does not know, prepare place in hell

Words of Muhammad from Musnad

Article 36: Social Citizen Rights

State; recognizes the right of the people to establish associations, unions, foundations or societies and supports them in the form of organic laws. Rallies and demonstrations cannot be held without asking except where allowed. Excessive body modifications and clothing that do not comply with the general public opinion cannot be used. Constitutional and legal rights must be clearly posted in a place that can be seen in the relevant institutions. Institutions periodically apply these laws. Applications must be notified in advance and pulse detection is prohibited. Citizens have the right to information or to file a petition. Art and science are rights protected and encouraged by the constitution. According to organic laws, freedom of religion, conscience and expression or freedom of dissemination are constitutionally protected rights. Torture and behaviors incompatible with human dignity are prohibited in all formal or informal work. The state considers it compelling to enforce religion on the basis of organic law in religious colonies, which is deemed appropriate, and constitutes a crime. It makes necessary sanctions for extremists on both secular or religious sides. No unconstitutional decision shall be taken for all decisions that may be taken in formal or informal works. The public is responsible for the implementation of the constitution along with the administrators. Within the same apartment, the majority

must visit the new neighbors at the same time in the newly moved house, in the apartment garden or in a meeting room with gifts. It is mandatory for the new carrier to provide identification and business information. This work is under the control of the village headman who has the right to bear arms. Non-social private shelters also control the neighborhood mukhtar.

36.1 General shape

[Adhere to it], turning in repentance to Him, and fear Him and establish prayer and do not be of those who associate others with Allah. [Or] of those who have divided their religion and become sects, every faction rejoicing in what it has.

Quran 30:31-32

"Do not be among those who disintegrate their religions and leave each group to their liking." beautiful orders. People are the mirror of each other in the name of perfection, they make mistakes and thrive. They take and take the necessary measures for this and they do not accept the rest.

36.2 Some conditions

It is most appropriate for each person to get to know each other in order to prevent illegal marriages or illegal works and to provide intelligence to the state when necessary.

The public has the right to form associations for the purpose of being social as defined by organic laws or to establish trade unions in order to protect, seek and improve their legal rights. Workers have the right to strike as defined by organic law, as well as the right to collective dismissal.

The right to make news through press and broadcasting except for special cases determined by organic law is preserved. Press, enlightenment of people; protection, development and dissemination of information; it is quite strategic for people to engage in entertainment and learning or to provide intelligence to the state; but of course there should be some limits. Press; Confidentiality of private life, the sanctity of justice and respect for one's rights and freedoms. Confidentiality of communication is essential except for special cases determined by organic laws and confidential and open communication is a right protected by the constitution. The freedom of religion, conscience, thought, opinion, expression and dissemination of thought as defined by organic laws is a right protected by the constitution. The confidentiality of private life is essential as it may be restricted in cases where legal procedures require it. Private, official or personal press and publication elements may never share information about people without their permission, and they cannot capture and publish their images. It is also one of the most dishonest behaviors that harsh measures should be implemented to prevent false news, lie news. The possibility of addressing all people cannot be exploited so easily. This is the biggest shamelessness and one of the biggest crimes.

The love of science and art, by the nature of man, is always together with people. If a person lived alone, this need would arise automatically. There is also a potential in science and art to develop civilization from engineering to mathematics in all areas; therefore, the state is obliged to take the necessary measures to develop and maintain.

Article 37: Socialist Public Elements

Public transport, park and park building, toilets, roads and highways, bridges and other elements determined by organic laws are completely free and the

state has the duty to protect, develop and disseminate these elements. There is no vehicle tax. The sale of oil is prohibited, except for special permits, as set out in organic laws. State; supports, uses, develops and disseminates electricity and electrical elements. The state is obliged to open special facilities for elderly people in need of care. The state is obliged to provide free health services and to take necessary environmental measures to protect human health. It takes special care and removes the barriers in the society in order to provide definitive solutions to the health problems of people with special health problems determined by organic laws. Except for state planning, the center of attraction cannot be created. There is no city center. The public has no right to save on the coastline. The coastline may not be used for any purpose other than as permitted by state affairs or by law.

37.1 General shape

Here you are - those invited to spend in the cause of Allah - but among you are those who withhold [out of greed]. And whoever withholds only withholds [benefit] from himself; and Allah is the Free of need, while you are the needy. And if you turn away, He will replace you with another people; then they will not be the likes of you.

Quran 47:38

On the basis of the state's philosophy of being a state, there is solidarity. Always one needs to be absorbed and helped by the other. In this case, some of the works give rise to certain phenomena, which are legally the right to labor arising from mutual interests and some of them are virtues or necessities to be done for everyone. Although all these are done according to different references in different societies, in fact, the main purpose is to develop over time and create opportunities for itself. Instead of lingering with the right transformations, we can provide ourselves with more comfortable and wider possibilities; therefore, some state elements should not be unnecessary burdens on us and must be completely free of charge, which requires the necessary transformations.

37.2 Some limits

Although it is not considered as a center of attraction and does not allow workplaces and accommodation centers that can make a difference in economic terms and is not considered as a center of attraction, attraction centers cannot be created except for the places deemed appropriate by the state in terms of jealousy due to the immovables purchased for the same price. Having the same value all over the country and having the same opportunities all over the country will prevent the fluctuations in the economy and will alleviate unnecessary burdens on economists. On the other hand, the gap between the people will be removed very efficiently. In addition to all this, it is small in terms of encouraging science for scientists only; but special attractions can be made. For example, a region with all kinds of social facilities and detached houses can be built for doctors. For example, there are servants in this region at regular intervals and are obliged to meet every need of people by phone.

The beach lanes have only reached the prestigious reputation of a parkland or wise title, and are reserved for luxury mansions where servants are laid by the state. Cannot be used for home construction. It can also be used for government offices or private enterprises. It can also be reserved for foreign heads of state.

Fighting for the need for raw materials is also irrelevant. We can separate and produce any matter in the electric field without

a problem of energy, or we can bring asteroids such as mountains into the world without a problem of energy and propulsion, or make Mars and other favorable worlds a habitable world without energy problems. There is no work that cannot be done with electricity. All existing and inventable machines can also work with electricity, which is clean energy.

Article 38: Civil Defense Rights

The protection of private, institutional or foundation property is essential. In these properties, if there is a garden limit, otherwise in the building it creates the right to self-defense according to the organic laws. People can attack foreign people anywhere in their shelters to kill them without asking. The state raises guards for those neighborhoods. The guards have the right to ask for identification. Possession of firearms is a constitutional right and its application is in accordance with organic laws.

38.1 General shape

You will see the wrongdoers fearful of what they have earned, and it will [certainly] befall them.

Quran 42:22

This verse reflects the guilty psychology very well. They both know the future, and they continue to commit crimes in a reckless manner. Criminals may be in a shameless mood, especially in crimes such as home invasion. This means that everything is actually over. Even expecting a warning from the landlords will persecute them.

38.2 Firearm

Except for three, no game is praised. These are training one's horse, having fun with his wife, throwing arrows and spears.

Words of Muhammad from Suyuti

As stated in the hadith, learning to use weapons is among the duties of men. This is the prerequisite and the most natural right of people to defend themselves, their families, friends and relatives or their states against the enemy when necessary; however, this right may also vary according to the strategies determined by the states and should be shown to prevent possible casualties. Weapon training should be taught during military service or polygons should be opened, but not everyone should be given a license to carry weapons, even if they are given possession licenses. Which types of weapons can be used by whom, must be determined clearly.

The most basic right of people in state or free social order is that they can ensure their safety; therefore, people should be allowed to carry weapons regardless of the consequences. This right of transport should be limited to a number of people and should be able to carry it after giving written notice to the village headman when going out of the city, for example to the village or district. Otherwise you can only have it. Besides, everyone should be able to carry a knife provided that it is in its case. According to the Constitution, the punishment of a number of crimes is death and one of them is to attack each other with the aim of killing instead of yawning for reasons that will not exist. In a death between the two sides, both sides will eventually go to the ground through justice. Even for mitigating reasons, they cannot be released from prison for many years.

Article 39: Confidentiality of Private Life

The privacy of private life is essential. Contact, contact information and identity information are protected by the relevant institutions and cannot be requested except under special conditions set out in organic laws. The media cannot share, record and share pictures and videos without asking, except for the conditions specified in organic laws.

39.1 General shape

The privacy of private life is one of the most important elements and laxity is a phenomenon that disrupts the character of the society and increases the loss of life. The state should take measures and implement or punish sanctions without loosening the privacy of private life.

O you who have believed, avoid much [negative] assumption. Indeed, some assumption is sin. And do not spy or backbite each other. Would one of you like to eat the flesh of his brother when dead? You would detest it. And fear Allah ; indeed, Allah is Accepting of repentance and Merciful.

Quran 49:12

And do not pursue that of which you have no knowledge. Indeed, the hearing, the sight and the heart - about all those [one] will be questioned.

Quran 17:36

These verses that tell people to prevent their evil urine, is a good proof that we should respect people's private lives. Defamation is certainly a crime, and all government agencies are obliged to protect such information in their work due to their duties.

If you attempt to investigate the shame and secret of Muslims, you will bring them against each other or you will bring them closer to each other.

Words of Muhammad from Abu David

39.2 Press

The concept of freedom of the press is one of the most serious issues that need to be emphasized in order to govern the state and educate the public. A man lives for his glory.

And sedition is worse than killing.

Quran 2:191

This verse is a good example. Some accusations cause people to be oppressed and despised for the rest of their lives, killing only once is incomparably better. This is how man was created.

And those who accuse chaste women and then do not produce four witnesses - lash them with eighty lashes and do not accept from them testimony ever after. And those are the defiantly disobedient.

Quran 24:4

This verse is a good example of punishment in a similar situation. The slander of adultery requires trial in the high criminal courts. If he still lives after being practiced, his testimony is never accepted. They're misguided. While the situation is so serious, the press, like all other elements, should definitely be suppressed by open laws.

Article 40: Absurdity

Absurdity is crime. It is a crime according to the form in the organic laws to discuss and act in a way that does not bring any results of any state element or action within the state. Misuse is an act of absurdity.

40.1 General shape

And this worldly life is not but play and amusement.

Quran 29:64

Then did you think that We created you for play and amusement?

Quran 23:115

The opposite verse, which seems to deny each other, reveals this situation. Not every word is acceptable from every person. Deeds are according to intentions. This principle applies both in the court of Allah and in the courts of the world. Abusive people should not be allowed. This is a very basic forensic principle. Even if he's right, one's fault can make him guilty. In this case pity means to allow opportunities for two-faced and dishonest people. This is not the standard posture. Everyone must be anxious about the consequences of his work.

You will see the wrongdoers fearful of what they have earned, and it will [certainly] befall them.

Quran 42:22

Courts and statesmen have a lot to do in this regard; because they disrupt or correct society and order.

Like snow in summer and like rain at gathering time, so honor is not right for a fool. Like a sparrow in its traveling, like a swallow in its flying, so bad words said against someone without reason do not come to rest. A whip is for the horse, leather ropes are for the donkey, and a stick is for the back of fools.

Proverbs of King Solomon 25:1-3

Abuse of duty or engaging in a job that is not a duty is deemed to be a absurdity and is a crime. Sometimes, requires dismissal without asking and justification.

40.2 Consultation

Whose affair is [determined by] consultation among themselves.

Quran 42:38

Consultation is essential at all levels of the hierarchical order. Absurdity also applies to consultations. The decision on a consulted matter should always be respected. The sad thing is that when the decisions made as a result of the consultation do not have impeccable results, people who voted against them may be more accurate. This makes no sense; because everyone needs time and a number of issues are not known without trying. Instead of only staying in the prosecution, a case of proof is created for both parties. Therefore, it should not increase its role in winning or losing and make any claims in consultations except for obvious and criminal mistakes. They should not enter into inconclusive opposition and reduce their majesty. However, inconclusive works are a cause of hostility to some extent since they are considered to be mischievous.

Article 41: Technology Policy

The state shall take the necessary measures for the immediate realization of the technologies obtained outside the slow development period arising from the impossibility of another alternative in terms of materials and methods in the natural development of technology. It does not accept any commercial agreements. It determines the required period. The state has a space policy. The state takes the necessary precautions for space colonies. The state is obliged to open hospitals, health and science research centers in space colonies and to control the practices there.

41.1 General shape

The Most Merciful. Taught the Quran. Created man. [And] taught him eloquence.

Quran 55:1-4

In the basic stance of science, there is the case that science is not made just so that it works; because when a job is started, it cannot be predicted which outcome will end and what other side effects will occur in this process. It is unknown what benefits it will bring; but science work, which is known to be absolutely beneficial, can be done only for pleasure or out of curiosity. Looking back, there is no other work to be done.

41.2 Measures

Who remember Allah while standing or sitting or [lying] on their sides and give thought to the creation of the heavens and the earth, [saying], "Our Lord, You did not create this aimlessly; exalted are You [above such a thing]; then protect us from the punishment of the Fire."

Quran 3:191

States should follow technology closely and take measures to increase competition in their incentives. Commercial agreements are prohibited by the Constitution of the Nations as well as within the state. Consultations with the producers should be made in such a way that no one can harm; because it takes quite some time to create infrastructure, but it is also very full in financial terms. It is impossible to apply the technology that changes from today to tomorrow.

The future is in space. Space is an endless sea and cannot be predicted. A remedy for a disease, a mine or a new world. In any case, the state must establish space colonies and do the necessary research. This will both contribute to the development of science and bring economic comfort. One of the phenomena that should be taken first for economic independence is space.

Article 42: Environmental and Animal Rights

The state protects and develops nature with all its elements. Stray animals cannot be killed and cannot disturb people. The state will build shelter for them. Those who want to have an animal can have an animal according to the shelter standards determined by organic laws. It is a constitutional crime to fail to comply with the rules of animal ownership as defined by organic laws. Games that torture animals are prohibited.

42.1 General shape

Corruption has appeared throughout the land and sea by [reason of] what the hands of people have earned so He may let them taste part of [the consequence of] what they have done that perhaps they will return [to righteousness].

Quran 30:41

And the stars and trees prostrate. And the heaven He raised and imposed the balance. That you not transgress within the balance.

Quran 55:6-8

Nature is the trust of Allah in us. We are grateful to Him for our respect for Allah; because it allows us to live, shelter, and continue our lives from the air we receive to the food we eat. As it can be understood from the verse, the natural balance can be deteriorated over time, even if it is not today, because of what people do with their own hands. This is strictly prohibited and a religious obligation to be sensitive to the environment.

And We have tamed them for them, so some of them they ride, and some of them they eat.

Quran 36:72

Animals are people's friends and servants. We use some to make things easier. Some of us become friends and have fun. Whatever they are, they are alive and carry exquisite. They should be given due care. Both livestock and domestic animals should be used and adopted in accordance with the principles laid down by law.

42.2 Religious duties

That [has been commanded], and whoever honors the sacred ordinances of Allah - it is best for him in the sight of his Lord. And permitted to you are the grazing livestock, except what is recited to you. So avoid the uncleanness of idols and avoid false statement,

Quran 22:30

Allah has also created some of the animals as food for us. Some of the animals can therefore be slaughtered and carried out periodically as a religious responsibility.

Their unjust killing is a great crime.

Whoever kills a sparrow for nothing, just for fun, he calls out to Allah on the Day of Resurrection: O my Lord! He didn't kill me for any benefit.

Words of Muhammad from Nasai

This hadith speaks of this.

A woman went to hell because of a cat she had imprisoned in the house. He did not give food by imprisoning the cat, nor did he release it from the vermin of the earth.

Words of Muhammad from Bukhari

This hadith also mentions the punishment of a human being who persecutes animals, which is a good reference for us. They have been encouraged to treat them well and there is absolutely share in the sight of Allah.

Chapter 2

Constitution of Nations

In cultural world administrations, kings act in consensus and apply international decisions to their people. People also seek an international binding body in which all kinds of international problems are discussed and solved. In this case, the House of Kings can be very effective in giving people what they want. Not only issues like security, technology development, economic issues, and all issues for people like possible new states are discussed and resolved in the House of Kings. Below, there are also some general legal recommendations of this Assembly.

Article 1: General shape

The highest and most respected assembly in the world is the Assembly of Kings. All existing states regard the Assembly of Kings as the sole binding authority on all international matters. The Assembly of Kings is composed of the co-chairs of the Ministers of National Economy, Ministers of National Religion, Ministers of National Justice, and Ministers of National Security, and they always remain abroad. Foreign language is not an obligation. A majority vote is essential in the Assembly of Kings. The House of Kings elects its own speaker. The task of the President of the Assembly is to manage the session. Kings can only reject twice the decisions of the House of Kings and states can then hold referendums within themselves. Volunteering is the basis for the Assembly of Kings; but when necessary, it waits for sacrifice and has the right to sanction. Under these conditions, the House of Kings aims for absolute world unity.

And do not walk upon the earth exultantly. Indeed, you will never tear the earth [apart], and you will never reach the mountains in height.

Quran 17:37

Aside from strict nationalism and authentic leaders, even countries that are overly cynical and discreet can be burdened by us to maintain order in the world. For this we must break our arrogance and ultimately seek ways of peace and agreement, even in wars. Most of the problems of ordinary people are the problems they create in their brains. They ask themselves problems that are not problems. States should act as professionally as possible, considering the well-being and future of societies. For this, we should always have a common assembly where we can talk and decide every question.

Article 2: Religious Responsibilities

The House of Kings protects religious freedoms and makes necessary sanctions if necessary. The Assembly accepts the majority of religious leaders and official ministers as binding in possible religious dis-

putes. The House of Kings does not recognize religions that contain unlawful orders and obedience. Assembly of Kings recognize prophets, religious leaders or religious representatives, as universal values. They cannot be reconciled with just one race. The House of Kings does not accept the expansion war with the army to spread religion, and in every country's constitution it accepts or promises in writing. The dissemination of religion in an informative way is limited but preserved and is the main religion of states. The House of Kings recognizes the right of minorities of different religions in foreign countries to protect themselves and to protect themselves and their future, and sets standards for them.

We have not sent down to you the Quran that you be distressed

Quran 20:2

The concept of jihad, as described above, is not a simple concept and we do not have to teach all people according to the laws of God. God did not create us for his own revenge. The main thing is to know and introduce God. This can be done easily and in every way in our revolution. It is only our duty to design and implement laws in the name of excellence. Already conquering countries, the need to serve in all religions is considered a chore.

Article 3: Social Responsibility

The House of Kings recognizes the civil service as an international duty and imposes certain responsibilities. The House of Kings promotes the independence of people of their own race and language, looks for a sample land for them and makes the necessary consultations. If necessary, the House of Kings opens new places by filling sea or ocean.

The best of people is the most beneficial to people.

Words of Muhammad from Bukhari

In cultural state and world structures, people are raised according to certain patterns. In this case, of course, besides a nationalist stance, a certain moral stance should be attained in international relations. In this case, the Royal Assembly will put some responsibilities on the officials of all nations.

Article 4: Civil Responsibilities

The Assembly of Kings recognizes the right of states to fill the sea or ocean and applies them according to the standards set, and re-determines the territorial waters. Prohibit the production of nuclear bombs to fight. Nuclear bombs, but with the permission of the

Assembly of Kings can be used in space and industrial work in the world. Fairly distributes the territory of space and sets the standards necessary for sharing; it does not recognize bilateral agreements between individuals, institutions or states. The Assembly of Kings determines the tonnage for asteroid mining and space mining. Individuals or organizations that find a larger than this tonnage have to make declarations and then work on an infinite number of mining companies. The person or institution that makes the notification receives a share from the sales and the share rate is determined by the House of Kings. If the declaration is not made, the Assembly of Kings makes the necessary sanctions. The Assembly of Kings encourages persons or institutions seeking mines for the purpose of making declarations and shares. Assembly of Kings; war, natural disasters or diseases in case of situations such as foreign immigration to each country has established standards and establishes campus even if used or not currently.

And cooperate in righteousness and piety, but do not cooperate in sin and aggression. And fear Allah ; indeed, Allah is severe in penalty.

Quran 5:2

Sea or ocean filling will be inevitable for today and tomorrow. Playing with land forms seems inevitable given the growing population and needs. In this case, this right should be granted to the countries which have coasts and the land waters should be redefined.

States need each other just as people need each other. Theoretically, there is no difference. Our world is very open to natural disasters, which are highly destructive from space or space, at almost certain intervals. In addition, people can be shifted due to epidemics or war. When such negativity occurs, the obligatory foreign settlements will not be courtesy, but the same applies to everyone.

Article 5: Legal Rights and Responsibilities

The House of Kings recognizes and develops international laws and agreements. It respects the immigration laws of the countries. There is no action by any person or entity that cannot be prosecuted under international agreements. People are responsible for the laws of the states in which they reside due to travel or migration. The House of Kings does not recognize the amborg outside its decision; but if he sees fit, he applies it himself. It does not recognize any international strategic partnership or commercial agreement except under the conditions it determines. The House of Kings considers the internationally highly respected people's or the existing states' request for amnesty for intercession and takes the necessary burden on itself.

O you who have believed, be persistently standing firm for Allah, witnesses in justice, and do not let the hatred of a people prevent you from being just. Be just; that is nearer to righteousness. And fear Allah ; indeed, Allah is Acquainted with what you do.

Quran 5:8

Justice cannot be achieved without sacrifice; therefore, all states should voluntarily, otherwise make sacrifices. This condition should be united. There is no theoretical benefit in terms of the classical structures of the unions. We must condition the concept of unity and turn to bilateral relations through more fair laws.

Article 6: Rights and Responsibilities Related to War

The House of Kings does not feel responsible for the consequences of the civil war and the people's desire for separation and attachment to another country, as a result of the desire to leave by referendum. The House of Kings accepts the attacked country as the homeland for the attacker, regardless of the outcome of the war; accepts as crime exploitation, rape and damage to public property; to take women, children and elderly people captive, except for coercion against they are in need; it does not recognize the release of criminals in the enemy country and knows high betrayal. It does not recognize colonialism and sets standards of contractual commitment.

Fight in the way of Allah those who fight you but do not transgress. Indeed. Allah does not like transgressors.

Quran 2:190

Since the main purpose is to sustain life, the House of Kings must respect people's choices; but they must also protect all nations from chaos. It must clearly define and apply war law. No matter who acts otherwise, it should make the necessary sanctions.

Aside from the relative interpretation, crime is a universal concept and criminals are considered guilty for all. In this case, criminals belonging to another state cannot be released without any justification. Nobody can talk about this right while the right is someone else's right.

Part II
Technological Upgrades

Chapter 4

Scientific Infrastructure

The Basic Functions

There are 3 basic functions which all created elements of the entity work and drive over. These; pure energy, heat and mobility. If you are not having trouble getting any of these elements or changing their values, there is no obstacle to building an advanced civilization; however, despite all the improvements made in our age, there is no way to use natural resources in the most effective way. Some natural resources are also running out. For these reasons, scientists have been busy developing engineering materials and methods for years to save time, materials, money and labor. I have summarized briefly below some of the articles I have published below and there are some solutions to these basic functions. Links: <https://osf.io/tw52w/> and <https://osf.io/t8zqw/>

4.1 Energy

O company of jinn and mankind, if you are able to pass beyond the regions of the heavens and the earth, then pass. You will not pass except by a massive power. So which of the favors of your Lord would you deny?

Quran 55:33-34

The great power in the verse is energy. Matter and space are both energy. Matter is the wave over space, that these are the more intense space regions that are formed due to folding in space and whose vibration decreases and opens due to constant energy and density over time, where the most dense objects lose vibration and mass in time and start to transform into space.

By the sky and Tariq - And what can make you know what is Tariq? It is the star of piercing darkness.

Quran 86:1-3

As stated in Article 1, space is flexible. Potential difference occurs in space. Because of this potential, movement, and therefore mass and energy, is formed from very dense to less dense. You can change the value of this flexibility with an external effect. The energy given by an external fiction may require more space, and all possible distances approach you with the energy you give from your location. Matter occurs in the same way, and only the amount of space collected is low and is not sufficient to move beyond the heavens.

Matter is in motion even when it is apparently stagnant. This is the movement that causes the total energy of mc^2 of matter and repeats itself every second. It is necessary to repeat every second; because matter can gain energy if there is an opposite work against resistance. The work is done against a resistance. Otherwise, the smallest force available has the potential to do endless work, making it impossible to form movement and matter. The tension created when the work against the resistance is released opens itself and returns to empty and waveless space. This high frequency repetition gives the material its energy and mass and makes it visible. Matter is formed as uncertain over infinite and

absolute space with these conditions as an imaginary part of it, and this is the only rule for all possible universes exist or does not exist yet, which also Hermes mentions.

Tis true without lying, certain- most true. That wch is below is like that wch is above - that wch is above is like yt wch is below to do ye miracles of one only thing. And as all things have been - arose from one by ye mediation of one: so all things have their birth from this one thing by adaptation. The Sun is its father, the moon its mother, the wind hath carried it in its belly, the earth its nurse. The father of all perfection in ye whole world is here. Its force or power is entire if it be converted into earth. Seperate thou ye earth from ye fire, ye subtile from the gross sweetly wth great industry. It ascends from ye earth to ye heaven - again it desends to ye earth and receives ye force of things superior - inferior. By this means you shall have ye glory of ye whole world - thereby all obscurity shall fly from you. Its force is above all force. ffor it vanquishes every subtile thing - penetrates every solid thing. So was ye world created. From this are - do come admirable adaptaions whereof ye means (Or process) is here in this. Hence I am called Hermes Trismegist, having the three parts of ye philosophy of ye whole world. That wch I have said of ye operation of ye Sun is accomplished - ended.

Hermes: Emerald Tablet [Translated by Isaac Newton]

During this occurrence, you cannot detect movement by eye due to the high frequency; but you see it as matter. When matter moves between two points in space, the formation movement actually moves. This is like a marbled rotating circle around a hub, that moving at the same time with the hub horizontally.

All work is equal to the total motion energy of the substance mc^2 . The substance can only be used until its existence. You can't expect a gram of matter to burn stars. This also applies to the generation of electricity or heat. Matter produces electricity with a fiction, using it's total energy. The amount of electricity produced can be up to the total energy of the materials used. During electricity generation, the total energy of the material is considered unchanged if you neglect the expansion. Matter produces the same amount of energy when it is still emerging. In short, when you produce electricity, when you ask "what you are doing" it will only say that "I am doing a formation movement"; but it will be generating electricity at that time. There is no energy change.

These conditions actually mean that it is possible for self-rotating producers, just as the substance itself forms and returns. What causes motion is a potential difference, and as long as every point of space is present, it has energy and therefore motion and potential. This means that the law of Faraday must be 4.1 for each

point of space as the substance exists and therefore the motion.

$$\varepsilon = N_2 - N_1 \left((\phi_2 - \phi_1) / (t_2 - t_1) \right) \quad (4.1)$$

This always means $\varepsilon > 0$, which means electricity. To better understand this, we should examine its mathematical structure.

4.1.1 Sacred Geometry

There exist many exact proofs about the rules of right triangle in abstract math; but what are the actual geometry and mechanism in real physical medium and for real math? What an undertaking can give a triangle about existence to understand it? Actually, it is able to explain everything.

Figure 4.1: This is an Euclidean right triangle. Euclidean geometry is the geometry which areas, angles and lengths are related together as equality by whole and certain numbers and there are no complex, uncertain or irrational numbers, irrational numbers are with a limit. Instead of this right triangle, it can be used a triangle which there is no right angle occurs in it. The shape is random. It does not mean actual geometry. For example, BD length can be longer than AD length in the below stated calculations.

There is a representation of an Euclidean geometry. In this case, being BD and BC are fixed, assume that AB is lengthened to any other AB_2 length. Here A point can be assumed as moving body in free space, B point is a fixed point which its coordinate is known in space and C is an observer.

For the lengthened hypotenuse on Fig. 4.1, over the inequality and definition of $AB_2 > AB$, it becomes (4.2) over the inequality of $BD_2^2 - BD^2 > AD^2 - AD_2^2$,

$$1 > \frac{AD^2 - AD_2^2}{BD_2^2 - BD^2} \quad (4.2)$$

where $BD^2 + AD^2 = AB^2$ and $BD_2^2 + AD_2^2 = AB_2^2$ are the equations over Pythagorean theorem. In the same manner, it becomes (4.3),

$$BD^2 + DC^2 = BD_2^2 + DC_2^2 \quad (4.3)$$

where $h^2 + t^2 = y^2$ and $h_2^2 + t_2^2 = y^2$ are the equations over Pythagorean theorem. If (4.3) is edited, it becomes $DC^2 - DC_2^2 = BD_2^2 - BD^2$; thus if $DC^2 - DC_2^2$ is used instead of $BD_2^2 - BD^2$ on (4.2), also it becomes (4.4) over $DC^2 - DC_2^2 > AD^2 - AD_2^2$

inequality.

$$1 > \frac{AD^2 - AD_2^2}{DC^2 - DC_2^2} \quad (4.4)$$

Now the actual displacement inequalities have been determined. Right this point, assume that there is no displacement, namely there is no lengthening. For this condition, it becomes $AB_2 = 0$, $DC_2 = 0$ and $AD_2 = 0$; thus (4.4) becomes (4.5),

$$DC^2 > AD^2 \quad (4.5)$$

and (4.2) becomes (4.6).

$$-BD^2 > AD^2 \quad (4.6)$$

4.1.2 Some results of the inequality

The inequality of (4.6) actually means it is impossible to be $AD=DC$ that means perpendicularity is impossible in universe. This also means that at the same time no lengths can be the same. From physical perspective, it means each point of free space has the same speed and energy magnitude at the end of 1 second but the same time, and emergence is one by one for the total of universe. Each point emerges by order. This also means, for any force-applied, since there is no middle point the natural motion is always circular as there is no alternative. Because of circular displacement, centrifugal force is always together with motion.

The inequality of (4.6) has another results, and are as the below stated ones.

- Exactly there is no middle point place.
- A right angle cannot emerge. It is only close to right angle due to the energy which area holds.
- It cannot be drawn two line segments which have the same length from a point in space to other two points. Namely, 3 or more objects cannot take place in space being the distance between each of them is the same. There is a time difference between each point of space at the same assumed global time.
- For $AD \neq DC$, it also becomes $AB \neq BC$, $BD \neq DC$, $BD \neq AD$, $BD \neq AB$ and more. Namely, while AB is lengthened, BC or the other lengths cannot protect own actual length. The medium is conservative. This also means, that length and thus 1 dimension do not exist alone; because 2 objects cannot take place at a distance relatively to each other. Namely, length is not absolute since is relative. Length occurs in a limited time interval and gets lost constantly, and cannot be independent on speed. Higher dimension parts of lower dimensions have different size than lower dimensional parts. Namely a 2 dimensional square cannot be used by the same size to create a 3 dimensional cube.
- The shortest distance between 2 objects is not a line segment. This distance is an arc so close to a line segment.
- Parallel two line segments cannot be drawn beyond drawing line segment. They are exactly intersected, and the intersection point occurs due to area multitude of conservative area.
- A closed curve is not possible. Only infinite space closes curve. Limited space is not closed but is conservative.

4.1.3 Progressive image

For the lengthened hypotenuse of Fig. 4.1, over the inequality of $(AD_2 + DC_2)^2 > (AD + DC)^2$ where $AB_2^2 + BC_2^2 = (AD_2 +$

$DC_2)^2$ and $AB^2 + BC^2 = (AD + DC)^2$, it becomes (4.7) for $AB_2 = 0$ that means no lengthening.

$$0 > (AD + DC)^2 \quad (4.7)$$

It means, that $AD + DC \notin \mathbb{R}$. If you assume, that $AD + DC = 0$, it becomes $0 > 0$; thus actually non of them can be 0. It means, that even if there would be no lengthening and thus no motion, there were already area and motion. They are deterministic and cannot be 0. $AD + DC$ is always an imaginary number for the condition of (4.7).

Area and thus all the information which area holds are deterministic. They cannot be created afterwards.

Proposition

In accordance with conservative space, over the components of the right triangle, it becomes $AB + BC + m = n$ and $AB^2 + BC^2 = m^2$ where $m = AD + DC$; thus becomes $\tau + DC + m = n$ and $\tau^2 + t^2 = m^2$ where τ and t are time here, and is $m = \sqrt{\tau^2 + t^2}$. It seems, that AB and BC or τ and t cannot take random values, that they take certain values in accordance with a rule. If $\tau + t + m = n$ is edited, it becomes $(\tau + t)^2 = (n - m)^2$ and thus it becomes $\tau^2 + t^2 + 2\tau t = n^2 - 2nm + m^2$. Since it is $\tau^2 + t^2 = m^2$, finally it becomes (4.8),

$$2(\tau t - nm) - n^2 = 0 \quad (4.8)$$

where $n = \tau + t + \sqrt{\tau^2 + t^2}$. For this equation of (4.8), the roots become (4.9) as imaginary time since it cannot be 0 over (4.7).

$$\tau = \mp it \quad (4.9)$$

With a motion, information in the imaginary time emerges in our universe. As constant speed and so $x = vt$ is not possible, because of $x = at^2$, when real time is emerged over t^2 in $x = at^2$ by using imaginary time of (4.9) instead of the t^2 , the distance and time emerge in opposite ways over the time on $x = at^2$, and know, that image appears as illusion in 3D because of the complex roots and thus complex plane which is perpendicular to (x, y) plane. After that, if you want to express the motion as average, you do not have to use imaginary time since is real time after this, just use its multitude on $x = vt$ and it becomes $x = -vt$.

4.2 Motility

4.2.1 Centrifugal Force

Do you not see that Allah has subjected to you whatever is on the earth and the ships which run through the sea by His command? And He restrains the sky from falling upon the earth, unless by His permission. Indeed Allah, to the people, is Kind and Merciful.

Quran 22:65

It is Allah who erected the heavens without pillars that you [can] see; then He established Himself above the Throne and made subject the sun and the moon, each running [its course] for a specified term. He arranges [each] matter; He details the signs that you may, of the meeting with your Lord, be certain.

Quran 13:2

The form of creation mentioned in the verses is creation by centrifugal force. This creation is created by the centrifugal force since it is always associated with the centrifugal force due to the

circular displacement that occurs even at the smallest moment of movement, as mentioned above. The universe gains volume according to the centrifugal force generated for the total energy used when it is at a singularity point in the smallest time and does not expand after 1 second expansion.

Have those who disbelieved not considered that the heavens and the earth were a joined entity, and We separated them and made from water every living thing? Then will they not believe?

Quran 21:30

In the beginning God created the heavens and the earth. Now the earth was formless and empty, darkness was over the surface of the deep, and the Spirit of God was hovering over the waters. And God said, "Let there be light," and there was light. God saw that the light was good, and he separated the light from the darkness. God called the light "day," and the darkness he called "night." And there was evening, and there was morning—the first day.

And God said, "Let the water under the sky be gathered to one place, and let dry ground appear." And it was so. God called the dry ground "land," and the gathered waters he called "seas." And God saw that it was good.

Genesis 1:1-5, 9-10

Are you a more difficult creation or is the heaven? Allah constructed it. He raised its ceiling and proportioned it. And He darkened its night and extracted its brightness. And after that He spread the earth.

Quran 79:27-30

This force is good enough to be the heart of any machine in need of movement and can be used as 4.10 for thrust.

$$F = \frac{mv^2 \sin(\alpha)}{r} \quad (4.10)$$

This force can be used in space, submarine or air since it is a closed system motor independent of air or water. Thrust close to the tensile force of the material used can be produced; however, the load must be spread over multiple bearings to prevent heat when producing high speed and thus high force. Instead of bearings, fixed or electromagnets can also be used.

It is not possible to produce thrust by fixed blades. You must use movable blades which create different angle as long as rpm increased. By high enough voltage signals which carry enough current, some pulses make motors create this force by these blades. Right this point, in a limited area small motors are used numerously instead of 1 motor, and a phase difference is created. When one of them gets signal, then suddenly signal is cut, and the other one gets signal. First motor which gets first signal stops oneself or made it stopped by opposite current, for example when 10th motor gets signal, by order. This phase difference allows creating this huge force, and a loop is created. Already, since centrifugal force is dependent on speed by v^2 , not mass, lower mass of blades creates huge force, and small motors are used to gain more thrust in the same volume. It is already more suitable.

WARNING

A thrust motor can also be produced with this force. With a gear system, you can convert small energies into large energies over time, and after a while you only waste energy to maintain

4.3 Heating and Cooling

Heating and cooling are not a problem as energy is not a problem. There are many different ways to do this.

4.3.1 Heating

For heating work, the superheating method can be used. For this reason, high self-resistance; however, an object with a lower resistance than the circuit is connected and superheated. This is the same logic as pear lamps. If the superheating method is carried out with a solenoid coil wound from a sufficiently long tube, heating can be provided in a narrower space along the tube. In addition, induction can be used. The highest magnetic field is the center of the solenoid coil. If there is a metal in it, if it changes direction too often, the magnetic field induces a high amount of electricity in varying directions on the metal in it, causing heat. Friction and pressure can also be used as other heating methods. One of these methods can be naturally more efficient than the other.

4.3.2 Cooling

For cooling work, one of the conventional methods can be used to change the volume of gases or vacuum. A vacuumed closed area makes cooling more severe in accordance with vacuuming magnitude. A sufficiently long solenoid wound tube to be used in such an environment can cool materials such as air or liquid passing through the tube.

Figure 4.2: Side view of the propulsion motor with inclined blade. The blades on the left belong to a conventional propeller and produce thrust only perpendicular to the center of rotation and do not cause movement because the wrist is 0. On the right is a propeller with an inclined blade, which causes one of the components to push in the direction of inclination.

speed. When you place this geared motor around for a second time, the E energy is set for 10 seconds. then you turn into an energy of 10E and now you spend every second of E for a motor that has 10E of energy every second. Even if you slow down the whole system, the engine will not slow down, so it still transmits the maximum energy it gains.

If you want to compare energy storage, you have a liquid-propelled rocket that delivers 1 million kilograms of thrust. If you attach this rocket to a 1 million-ton object, you will never be able to remove the frictions if you spend years of world-wide fuel or fuel in total; but you can only reduce the weight. The total amount of energy spent on this fuel would fire this 1 million tonne of ineligible. If this rocket of 1 million kilograms had been connected to the end of a huge propeller, which was ideal for example and supposedly unbreakable, and had rotated it continuously, you would be able to convert the resulting mv^2/r force by an angle to thrust; thus, by an angled propeller 1 ton and with 45 degree, 10,000 revolutions per minute can lift this 1 million ton object. With this method, the object could be removed. You have no right to drive a square wheeled vehicle and complain about fuel. The way the work is done is extremely important.

4.2.2 Imbalance

Performing one of the $+ Ft$ and $-Ft$ works with the same force and time value before the other creates displacement, changes the direction of displacement. When you apply $+ Ft$ to an object, if you apply $-Ft$ in the opposite direction at the end of time t , the object only slows down and is now displaced.

$$F_R = mv \frac{t_d - t_a}{t_d t_a} \quad (4.11)$$

For example, if you accelerate a particle between two plates, you get a thrust. If you slow down this accelerated particle at the end of the acceleration time by spreading the time between two other plates, that is, opening the distance between the plates for the same voltage, you get a thrust in the amount of recoil you extend the deceleration. This is an example and applies to all other imbalances that obtain water repulsion or explosion repulsion.

Chapter 5

Adaptations

Civil Engineering Elements Working on the Basic Functions

Since there is no problem with energy, mobility, heating and cooling, and only at the expense of one-time material, this means we have more playgrounds to use new methods. This also means that we can incorporate the weak systems that already exist. There are many different ways to do this, and some of the technological updates that I own are listed below.

5.1 Construction methods of structures

In the basic structure of ships, vehicles, roads or buildings, unique construction techniques are used.

Steel and concrete are used as the classical method for buildings. Although concrete has its own side effects for human health, it can also cause significant harm to the environment. However, building skeletons made with classical methods are more wasteful due to the methods used when evaluated physically and mathematically. One of the skeleton frame methods can make profit from the material even when concrete is not used. Necessary methods can be applied to make weight.

Materials can lift even millions of tons if they have sufficient surface area. The same amount of material can withstand excessive loads according to the distributed load principle, depending on the size of the surface area. Such a structure may be, for example, a structure constructed of steel or silicon carbide rods having dimensions of 5 mm x 1 mm x 1 mm.

Silicon is the most abundant element on earth. Approximately a quarter of the earth's crust consists of this element alone. Carbon is also an abundant element. When these two elements are properly combined, miracle element silicon carbide is formed and has superior capabilities in terms of both durability and lightness. It is also very effective against heat transfer, heat changes and does not change size easily. For these reasons it is also used in the space industry. There is no place where this material cannot be used; therefore, we must take the necessary measures to produce and shape this material.

WARNING

Or it can also be knitted seamlessly and a vector-lock method can be used to keep them together instead of welding. This will save material and be robust and light, although it has some unique drawbacks. If the above steel rods are taken into consideration, a 200 m x 20 m x 20 m structure constructed from these rods will weigh only 1 tonne, even if the total load spans millions of tons.

5.2 Civil Environment

Such methods should be developed strictly for the construction of buildings, ships, roads or vehicles.

5.2.1 Buildings

This method; It can be used for apartment buildings, private houses and factories as it will be very strong and light. We can use our natural resources more efficiently. These structures can be built layer by layer, for example from 10 cm x 10 cm x 10 cm knitted bricks, as in 3D printers, which lock each other in a vector without welds. In fact, bricks can be placed automatically with the 3D printer logic with a machine which is installed on the foundation of the apartment and moves on 2 axis. The wall thickness will be very thick, for example even 1 meter. Since there will be no beams and columns, the rooms will be perfectly rectangular and the walls between the rooms will be of the same thickness and quite thick. It will not pose any problem up to a certain height.

We can use stones of the same volume as bricks to make weight, and we place these stones in places. Buildings can be constructed in reverse T-shape against shaking by wind. If the stones are not used, instead, very tight steel ropes stretched at low angles and almost perpendicular in all directions can be used, and are concealed. We can use adhesive or somehow-mounted internal and external facade coatings, which have no limit in terms of variety. These are limited to your imagination, which can be given the appearance of a historical building with very fine stones.

We can use industrial 3D printers for bricks. A more specific and inexpensive, quick version can be developed which is adequate but not only of excellent quality for brick production, although current ones are too expensive. So we can produce bricks very quickly.

Each of the apartments in each of the buildings will have personal generators. Heating and cooling for both air and water in buildings will be provided by using electricity. When all these are included, a 7-8 KW personal generators will be enough for a 4-person house. The fact that the generators are personal will also have a significant impact on wars. Neither the destruction of the dams, the damage to the electrical wires nor the damage to the transformers will result in a power failure. Generators can be used from any house if necessary. The generators can run quietly with a vacuum pump that takes in the ambient air when they are started.

The same method can be used for one-piece buildings without tie-bars, except for apartment buildings, provided that you are a layer additive. Indoor stadiums, for example, are a good example. Even if it is completely filled, a 500 m x 500 m x 100 m structure constructed with the mentioned steel rods weighs up to 250 tons. Besides the robustness of these kinds of buildings, having a very large capacity will be quite attractive considering the price and time of construction. The same method can be used for one-piece bridges such as the Bosphorus. These bridges will be quite thick and will be like a lying post. Being flexible enough can lead to a pleasant experience. Since it will be knitted, it will pass air all over and it will not be a problem against the wind. These methods have great potential for architecture and advanced engineering.

The same method can be used for one-piece campuses. The campuses, which are gigantic structures, may have, for example, 15 m gates and 20 m columns. The interior is quite large and high and can make the student feel the seriousness of own work.

It can also be used for example rally stadiums. A stadium can be built in the size of a 40-50 km long road with the condition of being storied, and people can watch races both against time and the races held together.

It is also an ideal method for airports. One-piece gigantic multi-storey airports can be built, which are built for vertical landing and takeoff and safe passenger aircraft, as I mentioned below. There are circular areas where each plane will land, such as balconies. Circles lined around a large ring, circles lined around a smaller diameter ring on the second floor, and so on the other floors. In the center there is a huge free space and a high tower in the center. It's a big building in one piece.

5.2.2 Roads

The same method can be used for road construction, plus heaters and generators. We have the Earth-sized land, and we have almost no alternative to travel. Despite this, our roads are always narrow and inadequate. And they're not long-lived. Even the most expensive one is necessarily damaged in time.

For this purpose, silicon carbide or steel rods can be used to build roads, which will be durable, durable and inexpensive. For example you should build a width of 200 m paths. One of the most important factors that determine the size of vehicles is the width of the roads and the robustness. These wide paths also lead to the production of cheaper and more efficient tools for engineering purposes.

A steel road constructed with this method and measuring 1000 m x 200 m x 0.1 m is approximately 250 Kg, it will be. For such a road with a length of 1 million km, 250.000 tons - 300.000 tons of material will be used; such a path, together with heaters and generators, will be up to 10 billion dollars.

These roads will be used with heaters against rain and snow. Generators are placed at regular intervals along the path and for example by heating the air in a soledoid pipe and blowing through the veins. They don't have to be too big; because it will not be used to melt the ice formed within 1 second, but rather as an early precaution to avoid ice formation. Each can be switched on and off automatically from the required control centers separately. Autonomous weather conditions can also be used. Responsible government agencies can scan areas of hundreds of square kilometers in 1 hour with aircraft using the engine and generator I have mentioned.

There is hardly even an engineering on these roads, including heaters and generators, and it can only be made at the expense of one-time material and the raw material money of the materials.

5.2.3 Vehicles

The same method; Can be used for air, land, sea and space vehicles. As the roads will be very wide, for example, we can produce accident-safe vehicles. For example, personal vehicles can be manufactured in dimensions of 3 m x 6 m x 3 m. When this is done, the empty vehicle can weigh from a few kilograms to a few tens of kilograms. Other vehicles can be produced in the required dimensions and the severity of the collision will spread over a larger surface area, or the entire vehicle can serve as a spring. In addition, since the kinetic energy accumulated due to vehicle speed in accidents will be lower due to low mass, the severity of the collision will be lower and lower; because the amount of kinetic energy that needs to be reset is lower, and even in head-on collisions, the work does not take long. In these cars, additionally, steering wheel can be installed on seat, and the seat also moves in any direction against springs. Naturally, the seat will be placed further back and will be placed higher, against accidents.

We can talk about new technology engines to be used in all vehicles. One of these may have superiority over the other, and of course there will be negative aspects. Although it is generally superior, it can vary according to the intended use and one can be superior to the other.

Wheel independent thrust engine

This thrust motor produces propulsion completely independent of the wheels. Think of it as a thrust engine mounted anywhere on the vehicle. It simply uses the centrifugal force generated by a propeller as stated the above.

This has its drawbacks; because of the size of thrust, exceeding the friction of the wheels to the ground will be dragged. This creates a dangerous situation which means that the vehicle will be out of control. In braking, the same method can be used by turning the blades in the opposite direction, or by using a second motor in the opposite direction as this will require much energy and can generate lethal G forces. During braking, the vehicle can rub uncontrollably on the road, which leaves the vehicle out of balance. A balance system is required. It also can create pressure to land to balance the car.

Torque and pressure motor

This motor is the motor in which the thrust produced by the thrust motor is somehow controlled in a rotating area.

Figure 5.1: Torque generating motor. E is the propulsion motor. It generates torque in the T direction and the arms move in and out of the page to produce pressure.

The figure is simply representative. The pros of this engine are many. First, it stores the energy generated in the motors indicated by E; because the opposite load does not stop the propellers of the propulsion motors indicated by the E, even though they engage the arms. This means that it can store a constant energy by shifting gears with transmission, and more thrust can be generated than the energy that feeds every second. At this time, the energy will only be used to protect the energy gained by the propellers.

It can pressure towards the ground. Its movement towards the air is limited by the necessary methods, so that it can be parallel to the ground. For these reasons, although the vehicle is extremely light, it can increase the friction between the wheels and the ground due to the increased pressure as the speed increases, and may, for example, even go on the wall or ceiling if necessary.

It can also provide stability for the vehicle if supported by intelligent software. Prevents rolling over when the vehicle is thrown. Recognizes the changes in the balance of the vehicle according to a wave function and plays with the engine's levers separately at the required angles, and with rpm naturally as well.

Since the vehicles will already be light, a 10 KW -20 KW power supply is sufficient so that the engine already stores energy. Such a vehicle will weigh more than 100 Kg, even though it has more volume than the vehicles available, and land pressure will be used to protect the car against flying. Tires also do not burst and should be quite wide. Because the vehicle is light enough and has less kinetic energy at the same speed relatively to existing vehicles, braking with a single central disc can be achieved. Since

heating and cooling are not a problem in energy, electricity is supplied by the generator that generates its own energy.

Electrolysis motor

This is a motor that divides water into hydrogen and oxygen, converts hydrogen back into water and uses electricity to generate motion energy indirectly.

There are some negative aspects. Hydrogen is one of the elements with the best heat capacity; therefore, it will force the materials used in conventional engines. Besides, it can not be almost depot; because it is the smallest element and can escape even among the atoms of the vessel it is in. In addition, electrolysis requires high energy. Since hydrogen cannot be stored, it must be sent to the engine as soon as it is produced, which requires considerable energy. It is almost impossible to create space for large vehicles with super engines.

Electric motor

This is the classic electric motor. It either sends the electricity generated by the generators directly to an electric motor or transmits it to the separate electric motor on the wheel. In this engine, braking can be done by disk system or by preparing the energy given and playing with it.

5.3 New construction equipment

Said energy and motion generation methods can also be used to produce new and efficient machines. Energy generators are 5 KW - 10 KW; but parallel to each other. All other parts must be manufactured without any parts that cannot be carried by hand. The same parts should be used more than one-piece. If necessary, layer by layer knitting method should be built and prefabricated. Everything should fit into its own slot. On this occasion, we can easily replace their backups or, for example, if a part fails, it will continue to operate at a lower efficiency without entering service. For example; however, if there are several engines, the replacement engines should be able to be replaced manually and by a passenger. In addition, for example, in spite of partial deterioration of excavating aircraft, it is possible to continue to work with lower efficiency while waiting for the service line. The cable line must be roughly and interchangeable, for example it must be mounted randomly on the surface of the wall, but only under the inner liner. If necessary, the devices should be longer than necessary despite the relocation. Aircrafts should be able to take off and landing vertically.

5.3.1 Drilling machines

These properties can easily be used to produce liquid air, since energy and propulsion are no problem and can be produced at extreme levels even in small spaces. The thrust produced by the motor has the potential to generate a very high torque when controlled in a rotating field as mentioned above. This makes it possible for a machine to compress the air without difficulty and liquefy it instantly and in series of repetitions.

As is known, about 78% of the air is nitrogen and 21% is oxygen. Nitrogen is neither flammable nor combustible. It has extinguishing effect. When 1 cubic meter of air is compressed to 1 liter volume, it liquefies. When the liquefied air is sprayed with high pressure, it has a drilling effect. After spraying the liquefied air, it rapidly enters the gas phase. This simple method can be used with simple and cheap machines as drilling method. A vacuum pump can draw back the liquid air and evaporates it in a hot boiler instantly.

Tunnel boring machine

Connect your fingertips like an umbrella. Imagine that there are sprayers with 120 degrees between them at your fingertips.

Figure 5.2: Tuning machine with changing angle. The 3 circles in the figure are nozzles and can rotate around itself. The angle between the arms is constant and 120 degrees. The arms can approach each other like joining the fingertips to reduce or enlarge the diameter.

Fig. 5.2 shows a representation of this machine. Since the arms can be tilted forward all at once, new tunnels will be able to enter tunnels of different diameters, regardless of their diameter. These nozzles have nozzles at many points. There are also several vacuum nozzles. All 3 sprayers can also rotate around itself. The platform with these 3 heads can also rotate around itself. This method can even drill steel. It does not require much repairs and parts replacement; Because this machine almost does not experience contact and does not rub. Only splashes on the nozzles can cause damage, if the surface area of the spray is not large. The powder coming out of the sprays merges with the liquid air and becomes sludge. Laser distance meters can be found at the ends.

The vehicle is controlled by an armored vehicle with remote control and life support. In this vehicle, carbon dioxide can be ionized and converted back to oxygen.

Drilling machine

With the same spraying method, we can extract water or oil. We only need a long and robust vacuum hose, which is actually an aircraft, so there will be no burden on the hose. For example, when we set up circular torque motors with a diameter of 50 cm and layer-by-side parallel thrust motors, we can get enough torque to liquefy air and enough pressure to spray. Because the diameter is small, many parallel motors will be required to provide the energy required to produce pressure and torque, and the backhoe will therefore be extremely long; but that doesn't matter. Can be suspended from the tripod.

This drilling machine will actually be an air vehicle. It's the same thing if it's 100 km below ground or in space. The above-mentioned vehicle engine, which provides pressure to the ground, will be used and the thrust generated by the spray will be compensated by playing with the angles of the arms of the engine and held in the air with the desired precision. Temporary weights are not required. The engine will be able to produce both torque, and keep the vehicle in the air against any intensity of spraying.

The same tool can be used to remove the diamond mine; because the eruption will not be strong enough to pierce diamond; therefore, the diamonds can be clearly separated from the sludge sieved.

Backhoe-carrier aircraft

A larger aerial vehicle can be built with the same drilling machine logic. For example, it can be large enough to carry a piece of land measuring 30 m x 30 m x 30 m. There are spray and vacuum tips under the vehicle. If a cone-shaped spray is provided, the intersection with the other ends is achieved and the entire surface is excavated at the same time. The tips can also be moved at small angles in all directions without conical spray.

A vehicle like this, on this occasion, turns the soil into sludge despite all its hardness and vacuums the sludge. The sludge is filtered, and collectively converts liquid air from the sludge into air by diffusion explosion, for example by pouring it into superheated tungsten boilers. Soil accumulates in a separate reservoir.

Some of these tools must be unmanned and move from space. There must be certain routes and speed up in that route, wherever it takes the load, so that there is no damage in case of a fall. It should be designed so that it can unload all the load in seconds if necessary.

5.3.2 Fire Truck

The same aircraft can be used to extinguish forest fires of sufficient size. As is known, nitrogen in the air is an extremely high vapor pressure gas. Even at room temperature, the liquid nitrogen quickly returns to the gas phase and enters the air. At the required temperature it collectively returns to the gas phase, which manifests itself as a diffusion explosion. A very violent shock emerges, which can be used to extinguish forest fires. The temperature of forest fires is quite high and the fire, which is caught in liquid nitrogen rain, extinguishes due to the shock caused by the explosion of nitrogen particles. Nitrogen is neither burner nor combustible. Even if there is no explosion it has extinguishing effect.

In the aircraft, liquefied air is separated from the oxygen by the required method, even filters can be used for this purpose. Even nitrogen with a purity of %90 from roughly filtered air would suffice; because at the same time, even at high temperature, liquid oxygen diffuses and explodes. Although it does not explode, the extinguishing effect will be greater due to nitrogen, so it is not a problem.

5.3.3 Agricultural vehicles

Larger vehicles will be built with changing roads. For example, if a truck with dimensions of 30 m x 10 m x 5 m is thought to be wider in order to spread the load, it can be used even though it has 10-30 wagons. For less; however, this kind of transport can be more effective and will save us both money and time. It can be used not only for agricultural purposes but also for all kinds of cargo transportation.

However, since the thrust motor is very powerful, it will also be an ideal power supplier for the deep plow. A thrust motor, which is positioned in all corners of an equilateral triangle and provides thrust in the same direction, can allow soil removal from meters to depth. Temporary weights are also not required; because there will be a system that provides pressure to the ground.

5.3.4 Transport

Transportation is one of the most important factors for our business, whether from the sea, air or land or from space. Even today, where even minutes are important, faster and safer transport is important enough to guide trade and multiply the revenues of the leading states.

Ships

Vessels constructed by said knitting method can also be used to transport liquids. For this purpose, the entire body must be constructed in one piece and only carry surface elements. Engines

should be positioned in different regions so that they do not stress the ship as it is extremely strong.

Aircraft

This thrust engine can make passenger aircraft safer. In other words, if the skeleton structure and walls of aircraft are made of a material such as silicon carbide, it may be bulletproof. Thus, it has a powerful armor against abductions or against external threats. It does not affect the impact of any object on the plane.

Smaller and more private aircraft with the same engine can be used to send nuclear waste to the sun, or to replace cranes in ports.

Supersonic train

Since the roads will be very wide, a platform for trains can be built right in the middle of these roads connecting the colonies. These trains may be capable of moving in a closed environment and at supersonic speeds. The platform of the trains must be constructed completely closed and knitted. The thickness of the walls can be even 10-20 meters. The train moves like a snake on 3 rails located on the surface of the walls of the cylindrical hollow center and 120 degrees between them. For supersonic speeds the wheels will rotate at a speed of 20,000 rpm for a radius of 25 cm. The only problem is sound and vibration, which can be greatly prevented by the suspension on each wheel. Sufficient space must be left between the train and the walls so that air explosion and shock does not occur at high speeds and does not cause vibration.

Trains like Maglev need very high energy just as they need an external energy source. These two phenomena are a major drawback. On the trains mentioned, there will only be thrust engines, which can be independent of the wheels.

5.4 Industry

Water and mineral production can be realized in a very efficient and simple way with electricity. Personal generators can lift power transmission lines and do not require dams; therefore, we should use the electricity generated by our dams for purposes such as mineral extraction and water production. Excessive energy is required for these works and dams already have enough energy to cover this energy.

5.4.1 Water production: Type zero

Ionizing water production

We need to develop some ionizing systems to separate the particles of soil or water. Since energy is not a problem, we have to build Giga factories. These factories simply separate the materials into electrons and nuclei in the electric field and separate the elements from the mass difference and collect different elements in different places.

The charge acting on a particle can be simply shown as 5.1.

$$F = qE \quad (5.1)$$

This means that; the acting force is independent of the mass; particles of different mass gain different speeds when rotating in a circular area or linearly moving, for example, up and down. This is the logic of "mass spectrometry" that we know and can be used to produce materials.

The nice thing about this is that the separation from this mass difference can be repeated thousands of times per second for the same particles in a circular area, such as in the "Tokamak", and high purity can be achieved. As more particles enter the magnetic field, some particles shift down due to constant magnetic field energy, and when necessary adjustments are made, the ones that fall and leave the magnetic field can be in a continuous order.

Evaporating water production

Evaporation platforms should also be constructed. For example, on glass platforms, copper pipes are heated to evaporate and cooled to obtain pure water. The obtained pure water is collected in the natural pools which are set up high in the mountains and filtered down slowly from the platform which is built up with the necessary and various stones layer by layer and obtained the necessary minerals.

5.4.2 Mine production

Asteroid mining

Asteroids are extremely rich, even in terms of rare elements in the world. The technology that can take them into the world is still too expensive. These can be easily brought with the closed system thrust motors.

Separation in magnetic field

It can also be used for mineral production, such as water separation, magnetic field. Billions of volts of potential are created between two plates, and the electrical jump is cut by means of a highly insulating material such as "Teflon".

5.5 The Cryptobit

In accordance with the uncertainty, any measurable physical value of matter increases or decreases between absoluteness and absolute absence but its loss. No physical value can take certain value. They can only be expressed as some approaches.

As a result of this condition, for example, if you want to measure process number of a CPU, you can only get some different numbers at least for the numbers after the comma each time of measurement. When ever you want to measure more sensitive, new different numbers emerge after the fixed numbers after the comma. Except this, you can never get a certain number. Additionally for example, if you make a division, for the same operation the processor always performs the operation in different times. Yes it performs by some packets like 32 or 64 and always gives to you the same number that actually this also is not exact, it does not perform at the same time for each repeat. If you set the interval to find out this and if you ask to it over a program, sometimes you can get some results like 31 or 63 by unpredictable changing frequencies like 1 of 50 or 20 for 1 second.

Actually this physical principle and condition can be used as a perfect unpredictable cyberspace security element; because it creates a way to select incalculable and unpredictable codes like the below.

5.5.1 Selecting randomly

Let us use rounding the decimal numbers into closest one. For example, if the number is like x,xxxx6 it is rounded into x,xxxxx and this condition is called as 1. If the number is like x,xxxx4 then it is rounded into x,xxxx and the condition is called as 0. If the number is like x,xxxx5 try again. These 0 and 1 are not bits.

Also there is another way from many other ways that I used this second one. For example while a timer performs countdown, ask the time of counting until a number. If you repeat again and again the countdown, many times you get the same number but some times you get different number which is closest number to the actual number. The following VB codes are for this.

```
Public Class Form1
Private Sub Timer1_Tick(sender As Object, e As
EventArgs)
Handles Timer1.Tick
TextBox1.Text = Val(TextBox1.Text) - 1
If TextBox1.Text = Val(TextBox2.Text) Then
```

```
Timer1.Enabled = False
Timer2.Enabled = False
End If
End Sub
Private Sub Button1_Click(sender As Object, e As
EventArgs)
Handles Button1.Click
TextBox1.Text = 1000
TextBox2.Text = 998
TextBox3.Text = 3
Timer1.Interval = 1
Timer2.Interval = 10
Timer1.Start()
Timer2.Start()
End Sub
Private Sub Timer2_Tick(sender As Object, e As
EventArgs)
Handles Timer2.Tick
TextBox3.Text = Val(TextBox3.Text) - 1
End Sub
End Class
```

Just use 3 text boxes, 2 timers and 1 button, and then copy the code below. It counts from 1000 down to 998 by the interval of 1. Textbox3.Text is set as 3 by the interval of 10. You can change them; but over these values, Textbox3.Text becomes 1 many times but sometimes becomes 2 if you repeat the same operation by the same button. You can use any frequency for the repeats over the same button. Especially use long interval clicks to be sure. You can also generate auto-repeat program. You can download the following program called Single Counter.exe from the following address: SingleCounter

Note

If you do not want to repeat more and thus not to wait, repeat the same event more at the same time like following program. If you increase the number of the counters, probability is going to increase.

```
Public Class Form1
Private Sub Timer1_Tick(sender As Object, e As
EventArgs)
Handles Timer1.Tick
TextBox1.Text = Val(TextBox1.Text) - 1
TextBox4.Text = Val(TextBox4.Text) - 1
TextBox7.Text = Val(TextBox7.Text) - 1
TextBox10.Text = Val(TextBox10.Text) - 1
TextBox13.Text = Val(TextBox13.Text) - 1
TextBox16.Text = Val(TextBox16.Text) - 1
If TextBox1.Text = Val(TextBox2.Text) Then
Timer1.Enabled = False
Timer2.Enabled = False
Timer3.Enabled = False
Timer4.Enabled = False
Timer5.Enabled = False
Timer6.Enabled = False
Timer7.Enabled = False
End If
End Sub
Private Sub Button1_Click(sender As Object, e As
EventArgs)
Handles Button1.Click
TextBox3.Text = 3
TextBox1.Text = 1000
TextBox2.Text = 997
TextBox6.Text = 3
TextBox4.Text = 1000
TextBox5.Text = 997
TextBox9.Text = 3
TextBox7.Text = 1000
TextBox8.Text = 997
```

```

TextBox12.Text = 3
TextBox10.Text = 1000
TextBox11.Text = 997
TextBox15.Text = 3
TextBox13.Text = 1000
TextBox14.Text = 997
TextBox18.Text = 3
TextBox16.Text = 1000
TextBox17.Text = 997
Timer1.Interval = 1
Timer2.Interval = 10
Timer3.Interval = 10
Timer4.Interval = 10
Timer5.Interval = 10
Timer6.Interval = 10
Timer7.Interval = 10
Timer1.Start()
Timer2.Start()
Timer3.Start()
Timer4.Start()
Timer5.Start()
Timer6.Start()
Timer7.Start()
End Sub
Private Sub Timer2_Tick(sender As Object, e As
    EventArgs)
    Handles Timer2.Tick
    TextBox3.Text = Val(TextBox3.Text) - 1
End Sub
Private Sub Timer3_Tick(sender As Object, e As
    EventArgs)
    Handles Timer3.Tick
    TextBox6.Text = Val(TextBox6.Text) - 1
End Sub
Private Sub Timer4_Tick(sender As Object, e As
    EventArgs)
    Handles Timer4.Tick
    TextBox9.Text = Val(TextBox9.Text) - 1
End Sub
Private Sub Timer5_Tick(sender As Object, e As
    EventArgs)
    Handles Timer5.Tick
    TextBox12.Text = Val(TextBox12.Text) - 1
End Sub
Private Sub Timer6_Tick(sender As Object, e As
    EventArgs)
    Handles Timer6.Tick
    TextBox15.Text = Val(TextBox15.Text) - 1
End Sub
Private Sub Timer7_Tick(sender As Object, e As
    EventArgs)
    Handles Timer7.Tick
    TextBox18.Text = Val(TextBox18.Text) - 1
End Sub
End Class

```

This simple program shows us, that randomly changes the countdown time of each group. Sometimes one or more of them and some times the other ones become 1. You cannot guess. Just use 18 text boxes, 7 timers and 1 button, and then copy the code below. It counts from 1000 down to 997 by the interval of 1 over Timer1. Textbox3.Text is set as 3 by the interval of 10. You can change them; but over these values, Textbox3.Text and the other textboxes has numbers 6,9,12,15 and 18 become 0 many times but sometimes become 1 if you repeat the same operation by the same button. Also they do not get the same numbers together at the same time. You can use any frequency for the repeats over the same button. Especially use long interval clicks to be sure. You can also generate auto-repeat program. If you do not want to wait and want certain results, you can increase the number of textboxes by the same rule. You can download the following pro-

gram called Large Counter.exe from the following address: LargeCounter

Note

5.5.2 Encoding

Let us use the second method. Now assume, that English Alphabet is used for the key. 13 of the letters are going to be selected for using instead of 1 and the other 13 of them are going to be used for 0 that these are 0 and 1 of the bits. First of all for example let us choose the letters for 1. For this I wrote a simple program over MS Visual Studio Community as the above. You can write your own timer by using own language and own software or hardware architecture or you can use another language. These would be very sensitive and thus you can get better results. This is just for example.

Now assume that there are 26 pieces of the timers for each letter. Click on the button or repeat the action by an automated program until at least 1 of them becomes 1 over the Large Timer. If more than 1 of them become 1, then you are going to repeat only for the different group until only 1 of them becomes 1. Finally you selected 1 letter for encoding bit 1. Repeat the same for the other 25 letters until there exist only 16 pieces. After that the rest namely the existent other 16 letters are going to be used for encoding bit 0.

5.5.3 Offline Calibration

While determining the key for bit 1 and bit 0 over the letters, two computers which are aimed to be connected to each other for communication, the first key is recorded for both of them at the same time, and then they become online. Even the system architects which are built the machine cannot know the key. Now assume that each communication parts are performed by some certain bit lengths. Namely two computer always send 10 KB data parts even if the data is shorter then this. After each 10 KB packet, the key changes. The changer computer sends the new key; but this new key is also determined for the last time over the previous key. This previous key was already random namely even the system architects do not know. The second computer receives the new key and open it according to the previous key. This repeats itself continual manner in this way. Namely nobody knows what the two computers do. We made them confidants. Even attacks can disrupt communication and packets but also they cannot steal from us even if we cannot perform communication. Nobody is going to know what the key is going to be next time approximately. It is not the solution recording only the calibration. You must save any act always. If you are a thief or a wicked engineer, then if you lost only one 10 KB packet for the life time of the communication during recording from the beginning, you cannot do anything.

5.5.4 Remote Calibration

This may be dangerous if you think that any signal is recorded by a third unknown computer. For the worst possibility, think that a user is recording any act and making a simulation of the communication by some algorithms over any possibility even by using new hardware architecture to catch the copy of the computers and the software. Namely making them sensible.

I could not find an exact solution; but actually a solution is making the data packets smaller and thus making the key change at a high frequency at last only during remote calibration..

5.5.5 Prevention against DDOS attacks: Spartan

A solution can be developed to bring all this communication to a level that cannot be disturbed. In spite of all kinds of pressure,

a Spartan system can be developed to provide data exchange that the Spartan deserves.

When a particle passes through an electric field, during passing duration, the particle decreases the electric field's energy for other works; so if you assume that there is a fixed material in the magnetic field, the magnetic field would induce electricity during this passing on this material which is in the electric field as magnetic flux is going to change because of the energy sucking of the particle. As this method is pretty good vibration instrument to vibrate magnetic field by some particles in the magnetic field, also is a pretty good computer processor potential. We can align electrodes which are made of semiconductor or dielectric materials around a circle, and each one of them vibrates at visible light frequency. We can use noble gas nucleus or ion, or can use air particles directly from a magnetic plasma by rotating them in this circular area. It is possible to produce a coin size processor runs at 10^{20-25} Hertz. As this frequency is not because of a single particle, it is not going to be ionizer. To block constant acceleration of particles, we should only accelerate them by some periods. To use more particles or slow particles some time only effect the process number, and some usual fluctuation are not so important. Even its energy will not be as much as a toy laser.

To be smaller of data which is sent, will directly make energy and work done to send data smaller; so these processors must be used to process data before sending data. For example, we can record a data group like in the Table 5.1 by the most appropriate function or changing functions which are for remaining bits.

Table 5.1: The current data bits to be cut

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
A	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0

This record would be according to $f(x) = 3x - 2$ function for Table 5.1 data, and for example it is recorded as A124. This means that there are 4 pieces of 0 which the distance between each one of them is 2. As this code is going to get bigger by increasing number of bits, the same will be done for the code itself again and again. It should be made as the smallest as possible by using new hardware or software characters, or by using uppercase and lowercase letters together with a required combination.